

Summary Reports

Missing Data

For 2263 publications extracted from file “Master.9.13.xlsm”, 20 publications per journal per year were randomly selected; together with the 554 publications from the file “9.13.Supplemental TBJ Extraction.xlsm”, as well as 38 publications from the file “12.09 Supplemental Data Extraction AY.JK .xlsx”, 1080 publications in total were kept. Here is the frequency table of these records by journal and year:

Table 0: Frequency table of final data by journal and year

Journal	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	Total
JAMA	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	360
LANCET	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	360
NEJM	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	360
Total	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	1080

Note: Proportion of female/male among all authors, as well as p-values comparing female vs. male were based on data after excluding unknown gender.

Authors with multiple publications

MP11 = multiple first author roles (within journal)

Here is the frequency table for number of 1st author publications per author within journal:

Table 1.1: Frequency table for # of publications per author as 1st author within journal

			# of publications per author as 1st author within journal				2+ vs. 1		3+ vs. 1-2
Journal	Gender	Total	1	2	3	6	P-value*	OR (95% CI)	P-value*
JAMA	Unknown	4	4 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0.4271	0.35 (0.04, 3.07)	.
	Male	225	220 (97.78%)	5 (2.22%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			
	Female	125	124 (99.20%)	1 (0.80%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			
LANCET	Unknown	6	6 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0.1116		1.0000
	Male	241	233 (96.68%)	7 (2.90%)	1 (0.41%)	0 (0.00%)			
	Female	104	104 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			
NEJM	Unknown	0	0 (.%)	0 (.%)	0 (.%)	0 (.%)	0.0327	0.39 (0.17, 0.92)	0.3719
	Male	225	159 (70.67%)	57 (25.33%)	8 (3.56%)	1 (0.44%)			
	Female	50	43 (86.00%)	7 (14.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			

*: P-values were based on Fisher's exact test.

MP12 = multiple first author roles (within/across journals)

Here is the frequency table for number of 1st author publications per author within/across journals:

Table 1.2: Frequency table for # of publications per author as 1st author within/across journals

		# of publications per author as 1st author within across journals					2+ vs. 1		3+ vs. 1-2	
Gender	Total	1	2	3	4	7	P-value*	OR (95% CI)	P-value*	OR (95% CI)
Unknown	10	10 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	<.0001	0.19 (0.09, 0.40)	0.0785	0.18 (0.02, 1.41)
Male	674	584 (86.65%)	77 (11.42%)	10 (1.48%)	2 (0.30%)	1 (0.15%)				
Female	278	270 (97.12%)	7 (2.52%)	1 (0.36%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)				

*: P-values were based on Fisher's exact test.

MPL1 = multiple last author roles (within journals)

Here is the frequency table for number of last author publications per author within journal:

Table 1.3: Frequency table for # of publications per author as last author within journal

			# of publications per author as last author within journal					2+ vs. 1		3+ vs. 1-2
Journal	Gender	Total	1	2	3	4	5	P-value*	OR (95% CI)	P-value*
JAMA	Unknown	3	3 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0.7209	1.26 (0.33, 4.80)	1.0000
	Male	267	258 (96.63%)	6 (2.25%)	3 (1.12%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			
	Female	71	68 (95.77%)	3 (4.23%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			
LANCET	Unknown	11	11 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000	0.70 (0.15, 3.26)	1.0000
	Male	263	252 (95.82%)	9 (3.42%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.38%)	1 (0.38%)			
	Female	67	65 (97.01%)	2 (2.99%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			
NEJM	Unknown	2	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0.0858		1.0000
	Male	282	265 (93.97%)	14 (4.96%)	2 (0.71%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.35%)			
	Female	54	54 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			

*: P-values were based on Fisher's exact test.

MPL2 = multiple last author roles (within/across journals)

Here is the frequency table for number of last author publications per author within/across journals:

Table 1.4: Frequency table for # of publications per author as last author within/across journals

		# of publications per author as last author within across journals						2+ vs. 1		3+ vs. 1-2
Gender	Total	1	2	3	4	8	10	P-value*	OR (95% CI)	P-value*
Unknown	16	16 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0.1311	0.53 (0.24, 1.19)	0.3663
Male	788	735 (93.27%)	45 (5.71%)	5 (0.63%)	1 (0.13%)	1 (0.13%)	1 (0.13%)			
Female	190	183 (96.32%)	7 (3.68%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)			

*: P-values were based on Fisher's exact test.

MPAny1 = multiple significant author roles (within journal)

Here is the frequency table for number of significant author publications per author within journal:

Table 1.5: Frequency table for # of publications per author as significant author within journal

			# of publications per author as significant author within journal						2+ vs. 1		3+ vs. 1-2	
Journal	Gender	Total	1	2	3	4	5	7	P-value*	OR (95% CI)	P-value*	OR (95% CI)
JAMA	Unknown	13	13 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0.2465	0.57 (0.24, 1.33)	0.6685	0.49 (0.05, 4.42)
	Male	665	641 (96.39%)	20 (3.01%)	3 (0.45%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.15%)	0 (0.00%)				
	Female	337	330 (97.92%)	6 (1.78%)	1 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)				
LANCET	Unknown	27	27 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000	0.94 (0.46, 1.89)	0.3297	
	Male	711	681 (95.78%)	25 (3.52%)	2 (0.28%)	1 (0.14%)	1 (0.14%)	1 (0.14%)				
	Female	278	267 (96.04%)	11 (3.96%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)				
NEJM	Unknown	6	6 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0.0013	0.42 (0.24, 0.74)	0.0948	0.19 (0.03, 1.45)
	Male	717	597 (83.26%)	101 (14.09%)	14 (1.95%)	3 (0.42%)	1 (0.14%)	1 (0.14%)				
	Female	192	177 (92.19%)	14 (7.29%)	1 (0.52%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)				

*: P-values were based on Fisher's exact test.

MPAny2 = multiple significant author roles (within/across journals)

Here is the frequency table for number of significant author publications per author within/across journals:

Table 1.6: Frequency table for # of publications per author as significant author within/across journals

		# of publications per author as significant author within across journals									2+ vs. 1		3+ vs. 1-2	
Gender	Total	1	2	3	4	5	6	8	10	11	P-value*	OR (95% CI)	P-value*	OR (95% CI)
Unknown	46	46 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	<.0001	0.41 (0.29, 0.58)	0.0007	0.22 (0.08, 0.61)
Male	1999	1765 (88.29%)	189 (9.45%)	31 (1.55%)	8 (0.40%)	2 (0.10%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.05%)				
Female	794	753 (94.84%)	37 (4.66%)	1 (0.13%)	3 (0.38%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)				

*: P-values were based on Fisher’s exact test.

Here is the frequency table for the publication patterns of each author over time. For the patterns listed in this table, the first character “N”=“NEJM”, “J”=“JAMA”, “L”=“LANCET”; the second character “1”=“1st author”, “2”=“2nd author”, “L”=“last author”; and publications were separated by “*”. Note that there was 1 author “Haber, Barbara” had 2 publications 25467560, 25467591 as last author in LANCET on the same date 2015-03-21, and these two publications were simply displayed as “LL*LL”.

Table 1.7: Frequency table for author publication patterns over time

Pattern	Total	Unknown	Male	Female
J1	315 (11.10%)	4 (8.70%)	193 (9.65%)	118 (14.86%)
J1*J1	5 (0.18%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (0.20%)	1 (0.13%)
J1*JL	4 (0.14%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	2 (0.25%)
J1*JL*J1*JL*JL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
J1*L2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
J1*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
J1*N1*N1*N1*N1*N1*N1*N1*N1*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
J1*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
J1*N2*N1*N1*LL*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
J1*NL	3 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	1 (0.13%)
J1*NL*N2*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
J2	313 (11.03%)	6 (13.04%)	168 (8.40%)	139 (17.51%)

Pattern	Total	Unknown	Male	Female
J2*J1	3 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	1 (0.13%)
J2*J2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
J2*JL	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
J2*L2	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
J2*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
J2*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
J2*N2*L1*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
JL	291 (10.25%)	3 (6.52%)	224 (11.21%)	64 (8.06%)
JL*J1	3 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.15%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*J1*JL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*JL	6 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (0.20%)	2 (0.25%)
JL*JL*JL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*LL	6 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*N1	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*N1*JL*J2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
JL*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*N2*JL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*NL	3 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	1 (0.13%)
JL*NL*LL*NL*NL*NL*LL*NL*LL*LL*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
JL*NL*NL*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L1	309 (10.88%)	6 (13.04%)	206 (10.31%)	97 (12.22%)
L1*J1	4 (0.14%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (0.20%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*J2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*JL*J1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*L1	5 (0.18%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (0.25%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*L1*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)

Pattern	Total	Unknown	Male	Female
L1*L1*LL*LL*LL*LL*JL*JL*JL*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*L2	7 (0.25%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (0.25%)	2 (0.25%)
L1*LL	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.13%)
L1*N1	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*N2*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L1*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L2	310 (10.92%)	10 (21.74%)	196 (9.80%)	104 (13.10%)
L2*J2	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.13%)
L2*JL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L2*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
L2*L2	6 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.15%)	3 (0.38%)
L2*LL	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.13%)
L2*LL*L1*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L2*N1*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L2*N1*N1*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L2*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
L2*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
LL	293 (10.32%)	11 (23.91%)	223 (11.16%)	59 (7.43%)
LL*J1	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*J2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*JL	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.13%)
LL*JL*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*JL*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
LL*L1*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*L2	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)

Pattern	Total	Unknown	Male	Female
LL*LL	9 (0.32%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (0.35%)	2 (0.25%)
LL*N1	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*N2*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
LL*NL	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
N1	170 (5.99%)	0 (0.00%)	131 (6.55%)	39 (4.91%)
N1*J1*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*J1*N1*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*JL	3 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.15%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*JL*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*L1	3 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.15%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*LL*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*N1	48 (1.69%)	0 (0.00%)	43 (2.15%)	5 (0.63%)
N1*N1*J1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*N1*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*N1*L2	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.13%)
N1*N1*LL	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*N1*N1	6 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*N2	6 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (0.25%)	1 (0.13%)
N1*N2*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N1*NL	4 (0.14%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.15%)	1 (0.13%)
N1*NL*N1*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N2	285 (10.04%)	4 (8.70%)	196 (9.80%)	85 (10.71%)
N2*J1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N2*J2	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	1 (0.13%)
N2*JL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N2*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)

Pattern	Total	Unknown	Male	Female
N2*L1*N1*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)
N2*L2	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
N2*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N2*N1	5 (0.18%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (0.20%)	1 (0.13%)
N2*N1*J2*N2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N2*N2	12 (0.42%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (0.50%)	2 (0.25%)
N2*N2*J2*N1*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
N2*NL	4 (0.14%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.15%)	1 (0.13%)
N2*NL*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
NL	278 (9.79%)	2 (4.35%)	228 (11.41%)	48 (6.05%)
NL*J1	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*J2	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*JL	3 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.15%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*LL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*N1	2 (0.07%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*N1*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*N2	6 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (0.25%)	1 (0.13%)
NL*N2*L1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*NL	11 (0.39%)	0 (0.00%)	11 (0.55%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*NL*J2	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*NL*L2*N1	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)
NL*NL*NL	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)

Descriptive analysis

Note that there were 46 unique significant authors in 40 publications having “unknown” gender in the data, and they were included in the following descriptive tables but excluded when calculating p-values.

Table 2.0 below showed the descriptive table for the gender of 1st/2nd/last/significant author in publications by journals. It suggested that there were gender disparities in 1st/2nd/significant author roles publication across journals.

Table 2.0: Gender disparity across journals

Author position	Journal	Total	Unknown	Male	Female	P-value* (F vs. M)	P-value* (F vs. M across journals)
1st author	All	1080	10 (0.93%)	783 (73.18%)	287 (26.82%)	<.0001	<.0001
	JAMA	360	4 (1.11%)	230 (64.61%)	126 (35.39%)	<.0001	
	LANCET	360	6 (1.67%)	250 (70.62%)	104 (29.38%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	360	0 (0.00%)	303 (84.17%)	57 (15.83%)	<.0001	
2nd author	All	1046	20 (1.91%)	668 (65.11%)	358 (34.89%)	<.0001	<.0001
	JAMA	337	6 (1.78%)	186 (56.19%)	145 (43.81%)	0.0030	
	LANCET	350	10 (2.86%)	224 (65.88%)	116 (34.12%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	359	4 (1.11%)	258 (72.68%)	97 (27.32%)	<.0001	
Last author	All	1075	16 (1.49%)	862 (81.40%)	197 (18.60%)	<.0001	0.1378
	JAMA	356	3 (0.84%)	279 (79.04%)	74 (20.96%)	<.0001	
	LANCET	359	11 (3.06%)	279 (80.17%)	69 (19.83%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	360	2 (0.56%)	304 (84.92%)	54 (15.08%)	<.0001	
Significant author	All	3201	46 (1.44%)	2313 (73.31%)	842 (26.69%)	<.0001	<.0001
	JAMA	1053	13 (1.23%)	695 (66.83%)	345 (33.17%)	<.0001	
	LANCET	1069	27 (2.53%)	753 (72.26%)	289 (27.74%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	1079	6 (0.56%)	865 (80.62%)	208 (19.38%)	<.0001	

*: For 1st, 2nd, last author, p-values were based on GEE models with authors as clustering effect; for significant author, p-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect.

First Author

Tables 2.1.1 and 2.1.2 below showed the descriptive table for publication-level and author-level first author characteristics by the gender of first author in column percentages and row percentages, respectively. More specifically, Tables 2.1.3 and 2.1.4 showed the descriptive tables within each journal.

Table 2.1.1: Percentage of Female First Author Characteristics (All journals; column percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=783)	Female (N=287)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	420 (38.89%)	5 (50.00%)	298 (38.06%)	117 (40.77%)	0.4138
	2009-2014		360 (33.33%)	2 (20.00%)	273 (34.87%)	85 (29.62%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.78%)	3 (30.00%)	212 (27.08%)	85 (29.62%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	482 (44.63%)	5 (50.00%)	315 (40.23%)	162 (56.45%)	0.0001
	11-20		396 (36.67%)	4 (40.00%)	309 (39.46%)	83 (28.92%)	
	21+		202 (18.70%)	1 (10.00%)	159 (20.31%)	42 (14.63%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	548 (50.74%)	3 (30.00%)	378 (48.28%)	167 (58.19%)	0.0037
	Non-US		532 (49.26%)	7 (70.00%)	405 (51.72%)	120 (41.81%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	502 (46.48%)	4 (40.00%)	320 (40.87%)	178 (62.02%)	<.0001
	Yes		578 (53.52%)	6 (60.00%)	463 (59.13%)	109 (37.98%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	663 (61.39%)	6 (60.00%)	495 (63.22%)	162 (56.45%)	0.0645
	Yes		417 (38.61%)	4 (40.00%)	288 (36.78%)	125 (43.55%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.88±1.23	0.93±1.54	0.96±1.31	0.65±0.90	<.0001
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	61	411 (40.33%)	2 (20.00%)	280 (38.10%)	129 (47.08%)	0.0133
	Non-US		608 (59.67%)	8 (80.00%)	455 (61.90%)	145 (52.92%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	61	410 (40.24%)	2 (20.00%)	280 (38.10%)	128 (46.72%)	0.0114
	Europe		216 (21.20%)	3 (30.00%)	164 (22.31%)	49 (17.88%)	
	Asia		66 (6.48%)	1 (10.00%)	52 (7.07%)	13 (4.74%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.36%)	1 (10.00%)	11 (1.50%)	12 (4.38%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (0.82%)	1 (0.36%)	
	Africa		40 (3.93%)	2 (20.00%)	24 (3.27%)	14 (5.11%)	
	Other/Unknown		256 (25.12%)	1 (10.00%)	198 (26.94%)	57 (20.80%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=783)	Female (N=287)	P-value*
Directionality	Negative	12	153 (14.33%)	3 (30.00%)	99 (12.77%)	51 (18.02%)	0.1945
	Neutral		215 (20.13%)	2 (20.00%)	159 (20.52%)	54 (19.08%)	
	Positive		542 (50.75%)	3 (30.00%)	407 (52.52%)	132 (46.64%)	
	Other		158 (14.79%)	2 (20.00%)	110 (14.19%)	46 (16.25%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=720)	Unknown (N=8)	Male (N=530)	Female (N=182)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	595 (82.64%)	8 (100.00%)	420 (79.25%)	167 (91.76%)	<.0001
	101+		125 (17.36%)	0 (0.00%)	110 (20.75%)	15 (8.24%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=548)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=378)	Female (N=167)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	205 (37.41%)	1 (33.33%)	142 (37.57%)	62 (37.13%)	0.9572
	Midwest		90 (16.42%)	1 (33.33%)	61 (16.14%)	28 (16.77%)	
	South		144 (26.28%)	0 (0.00%)	101 (26.72%)	43 (25.75%)	
	West		109 (19.89%)	1 (33.33%)	74 (19.58%)	34 (20.36%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=962)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=674)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	1	541 (56.30%)	4 (44.44%)	363 (53.86%)	174 (62.59%)	0.0135
	Non-US		420 (43.70%)	5 (55.56%)	311 (46.14%)	104 (37.41%)	
Continent	North America	1	535 (55.67%)	3 (33.33%)	360 (53.41%)	172 (61.87%)	0.1138
	Europe		315 (32.78%)	4 (44.44%)	235 (34.87%)	76 (27.34%)	
	Asia		44 (4.58%)	1 (11.11%)	32 (4.75%)	11 (3.96%)	
	Australia/NZ		40 (4.16%)	1 (11.11%)	25 (3.71%)	14 (5.04%)	
	Central/South America		5 (0.52%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (0.74%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		20 (2.08%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (2.23%)	5 (1.80%)	
	Other/Unknown		2 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=962)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=674)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
Specialty	CVD	0	167 (17.36%)	2 (20.00%)	142 (21.07%)	23 (8.27%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms		89 (9.25%)	0 (0.00%)	67 (9.94%)	22 (7.91%)	
	Infectious Diseases		63 (6.55%)	0 (0.00%)	40 (5.93%)	23 (8.27%)	
	All other		643 (66.84%)	8 (80.00%)	425 (63.06%)	210 (75.54%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	5	164 (17.14%)	1 (12.50%)	121 (18.01%)	42 (15.16%)	0.2971
	Yes		793 (82.86%)	7 (87.50%)	551 (81.99%)	235 (84.84%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	5	92 (9.61%)	1 (12.50%)	65 (9.67%)	26 (9.39%)	0.9012
	Yes		865 (90.39%)	7 (87.50%)	607 (90.33%)	251 (90.61%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	5	106 (11.08%)	2 (25.00%)	62 (9.23%)	42 (15.16%)	0.0094
	Yes		851 (88.92%)	6 (75.00%)	610 (90.77%)	235 (84.84%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	5	957 (100.00%)	8 (100.00%)	672 (100.00%)	277 (100.00%)	.
Degree	MD-only	1	536 (55.78%)	4 (44.44%)	402 (59.64%)	130 (46.76%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		180 (18.73%)	3 (33.33%)	84 (12.46%)	93 (33.45%)	
	Both		200 (20.81%)	1 (11.11%)	163 (24.18%)	36 (12.95%)	
	Neither		45 (4.68%)	1 (11.11%)	25 (3.71%)	19 (6.83%)	
Degree-MD	No	1	225 (23.41%)	4 (44.44%)	109 (16.17%)	112 (40.29%)	<.0001
	Yes		736 (76.59%)	5 (55.56%)	565 (83.83%)	166 (59.71%)	
Degree-Dual	No	1	761 (79.19%)	8 (88.89%)	511 (75.82%)	242 (87.05%)	0.0001
	Yes		200 (20.81%)	1 (11.11%)	163 (24.18%)	36 (12.95%)	
Title	L-only	1	81 (8.43%)	1 (11.11%)	58 (8.61%)	22 (7.91%)	0.0015
	AR-only		228 (23.73%)	1 (11.11%)	145 (21.51%)	82 (29.50%)	
	Both		457 (47.55%)	0 (0.00%)	349 (51.78%)	108 (38.85%)	
	Neither		195 (20.29%)	7 (77.78%)	122 (18.10%)	66 (23.74%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=962)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=674)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
Title-Leadership Position	No	1	423 (44.02%)	8 (88.89%)	267 (39.61%)	148 (53.24%)	0.0001
	Yes		538 (55.98%)	1 (11.11%)	407 (60.39%)	130 (46.76%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	1	276 (28.72%)	8 (88.89%)	180 (26.71%)	88 (31.65%)	0.1227
	Yes		685 (71.28%)	1 (11.11%)	494 (73.29%)	190 (68.35%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with first authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.1.2: Percentage of Female First Author Characteristics (All journals; row percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=783)	Female (N=287)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	420 (38.89%)	5 (1.19%)	298 (71.81%)	117 (28.19%)	0.4138
	2009-2014		360 (33.33%)	2 (0.56%)	273 (76.26%)	85 (23.74%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.78%)	3 (1.00%)	212 (71.38%)	85 (28.62%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	482 (44.63%)	5 (1.04%)	315 (66.04%)	162 (33.96%)	0.0001
	11-20		396 (36.67%)	4 (1.01%)	309 (78.83%)	83 (21.17%)	
	21+		202 (18.70%)	1 (0.50%)	159 (79.10%)	42 (20.90%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	548 (50.74%)	3 (0.55%)	378 (69.36%)	167 (30.64%)	0.0037
	Non-US		532 (49.26%)	7 (1.32%)	405 (77.14%)	120 (22.86%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	502 (46.48%)	4 (0.80%)	320 (64.26%)	178 (35.74%)	<.0001
	Yes		578 (53.52%)	6 (1.04%)	463 (80.94%)	109 (19.06%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	663 (61.39%)	6 (0.90%)	495 (75.34%)	162 (24.66%)	0.0645
	Yes		417 (38.61%)	4 (0.96%)	288 (69.73%)	125 (30.27%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.88±1.23	0.93±1.54	0.96±1.31	0.65±0.90	<.0001
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	61	411 (40.33%)	2 (0.49%)	280 (68.46%)	129 (31.54%)	0.0133
	Non-US		608 (59.67%)	8 (1.32%)	455 (75.83%)	145 (24.17%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	61	410 (40.24%)	2 (0.49%)	280 (68.63%)	128 (31.37%)	0.0114
	Europe		216 (21.20%)	3 (1.39%)	164 (77.00%)	49 (23.00%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=783)	Female (N=287)	P-value*
	Asia		66 (6.48%)	1 (1.52%)	52 (80.00%)	13 (20.00%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.36%)	1 (4.17%)	11 (47.83%)	12 (52.17%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (85.71%)	1 (14.29%)	
	Africa		40 (3.93%)	2 (5.00%)	24 (63.16%)	14 (36.84%)	
	Other/Unknown		256 (25.12%)	1 (0.39%)	198 (77.65%)	57 (22.35%)	
Directionality	Negative	12	153 (14.33%)	3 (1.96%)	99 (66.00%)	51 (34.00%)	0.1945
	Neutral		215 (20.13%)	2 (0.93%)	159 (74.65%)	54 (25.35%)	
	Positive		542 (50.75%)	3 (0.55%)	407 (75.51%)	132 (24.49%)	
	Other		158 (14.79%)	2 (1.27%)	110 (70.51%)	46 (29.49%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=720)	Unknown (N=8)	Male (N=530)	Female (N=182)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	595 (82.64%)	8 (1.34%)	420 (71.55%)	167 (28.45%)	<.0001
	101+		125 (17.36%)	0 (0.00%)	110 (88.00%)	15 (12.00%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=548)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=378)	Female (N=167)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Midwest	0	90 (16.42%)	1 (1.11%)	61 (68.54%)	28 (31.46%)	0.9572
	Northeast		205 (37.41%)	1 (0.49%)	142 (69.61%)	62 (30.39%)	
	South		144 (26.28%)	0 (0.00%)	101 (70.14%)	43 (29.86%)	
	West		109 (19.89%)	1 (0.92%)	74 (68.52%)	34 (31.48%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=962)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=674)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	1	541 (56.30%)	4 (0.74%)	363 (67.60%)	174 (32.40%)	0.0135
	Non-US		420 (43.70%)	5 (1.19%)	311 (74.94%)	104 (25.06%)	
Continent	North America	1	535 (55.67%)	3 (0.56%)	360 (67.67%)	172 (32.33%)	0.1138
	Europe		315 (32.78%)	4 (1.27%)	235 (75.56%)	76 (24.44%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=962)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=674)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
	Asia		44 (4.58%)	1 (2.27%)	32 (74.42%)	11 (25.58%)	
	Australia/NZ		40 (4.16%)	1 (2.50%)	25 (64.10%)	14 (35.90%)	
	Central/South America		5 (0.52%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		20 (2.08%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	
	Other/Unknown		2 (0.21%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	167 (17.36%)	2 (1.20%)	142 (86.06%)	23 (13.94%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms		89 (9.25%)	0 (0.00%)	67 (75.28%)	22 (24.72%)	
	Infectious Diseases		63 (6.55%)	0 (0.00%)	40 (63.49%)	23 (36.51%)	
	All other		643 (66.84%)	8 (1.24%)	425 (66.93%)	210 (33.07%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	5	164 (17.14%)	1 (0.61%)	121 (74.23%)	42 (25.77%)	0.2971
	Yes		793 (82.86%)	7 (0.88%)	551 (70.10%)	235 (29.90%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	5	92 (9.61%)	1 (1.09%)	65 (71.43%)	26 (28.57%)	0.9012
	Yes		865 (90.39%)	7 (0.81%)	607 (70.75%)	251 (29.25%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	5	106 (11.08%)	2 (1.89%)	62 (59.62%)	42 (40.38%)	0.0094
	Yes		851 (88.92%)	6 (0.71%)	610 (72.19%)	235 (27.81%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	5	957 (100.00%)	8 (0.84%)	672 (70.81%)	277 (29.19%)	.
Degree	MD-only	1	536 (55.78%)	4 (0.75%)	402 (75.56%)	130 (24.44%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		180 (18.73%)	3 (1.67%)	84 (47.46%)	93 (52.54%)	
	Both		200 (20.81%)	1 (0.50%)	163 (81.91%)	36 (18.09%)	
	Neither		45 (4.68%)	1 (2.22%)	25 (56.82%)	19 (43.18%)	
Degree-MD	No	1	225 (23.41%)	4 (1.78%)	109 (49.32%)	112 (50.68%)	<.0001
	Yes		736 (76.59%)	5 (0.68%)	565 (77.29%)	166 (22.71%)	
Degree-Dual	No	1	761 (79.19%)	8 (1.05%)	511 (67.86%)	242 (32.14%)	0.0001

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=962)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=674)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
	Yes		200 (20.81%)	1 (0.50%)	163 (81.91%)	36 (18.09%)	
Title	L-only	1	81 (8.43%)	1 (1.23%)	58 (72.50%)	22 (27.50%)	0.0015
	AR-only		228 (23.73%)	1 (0.44%)	145 (63.88%)	82 (36.12%)	
	Both		457 (47.55%)	0 (0.00%)	349 (76.37%)	108 (23.63%)	
	Neither		195 (20.29%)	7 (3.59%)	122 (64.89%)	66 (35.11%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	1	423 (44.02%)	8 (1.89%)	267 (64.34%)	148 (35.66%)	0.0001
	Yes		538 (55.98%)	1 (0.19%)	407 (75.79%)	130 (24.21%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	1	276 (28.72%)	8 (2.90%)	180 (67.16%)	88 (32.84%)	0.1227
	Yes		685 (71.28%)	1 (0.15%)	494 (72.22%)	190 (27.78%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with first authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.1.3: Percentage of Female First Author Characteristics (column percentages)

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Male (N=303)	Female (N=57)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=230)	Female (N=126)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=250)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	140 (38.89%)	113 (37.29%)	27 (47.37%)	0.0027	0	140 (38.89%)	1 (25.00%)	85 (36.96%)	54 (42.86%)	0.1441	0	140 (38.89%)	4 (66.67%)	100 (40.00%)	36 (34.62%)	0.2315
	2009-2014	120 (33.33%)	111 (36.63%)	9 (15.79%)	120 (33.33%)			1 (25.00%)	85 (36.96%)	34 (26.98%)	120 (33.33%)			1 (16.67%)	77 (30.80%)	42 (40.38%)		
	2015-2019	100 (27.78%)	79 (26.07%)	21 (36.84%)	100 (27.78%)			2 (50.00%)	60 (26.09%)	38 (30.16%)	100 (27.78%)			1 (16.67%)	73 (29.20%)	26 (25.00%)		
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	101 (28.06%)	80 (26.40%)	21 (36.84%)	0.2188	0	214 (59.44%)	1 (25.00%)	129 (56.09%)	84 (66.67%)	0.0651	0	167 (46.39%)	4 (66.67%)	106 (42.40%)	57 (54.81%)	0.0837
	11-20	163 (45.28%)	143 (47.19%)	20 (35.09%)	105 (29.17%)			2 (50.00%)	70 (30.43%)	33 (26.19%)	128 (35.56%)			2 (33.33%)	96 (38.40%)	30 (28.85%)		
	21+	96 (26.67%)	80 (26.40%)	16 (28.07%)	41 (11.39%)			1 (25.00%)	31 (13.48%)	9 (7.14%)	65 (18.06%)			0 (0.00%)	48 (19.20%)	17 (16.35%)		
Institution Region (at time of Publication) ²	US	0	200 (55.56%)	165 (54.46%)	35 (61.40%)	0.3039	0	250 (69.44%)	2 (50.00%)	146 (63.48%)	102 (80.95%)	0.0004	0	98 (27.22%)	1 (16.67%)	67 (26.80%)	30 (28.85%)	0.7378
	Non-US	160 (44.44%)	138 (45.54%)	22 (38.60%)	110 (30.56%)			2 (50.00%)	84 (36.52%)	24 (19.05%)	262 (72.78%)			5 (83.33%)	183 (73.20%)	74 (71.15%)		
Clinical Trial	No	0	63 (17.50%)	44 (14.52%)	19 (33.33%)	0.0113	0	245 (68.06%)	2 (50.00%)	144 (62.61%)	99 (78.57%)	0.0021	0	194 (53.89%)	2 (33.33%)	132 (52.80%)	60 (57.69%)	0.4048
	Yes	297 (82.50%)	259 (85.48%)	38 (66.67%)	115 (31.94%)			2 (50.00%)	86 (37.39%)	27 (21.43%)	166 (46.11%)			4 (66.67%)	118 (47.20%)	44 (42.31%)		
Grant Funding	No	0	232 (64.44%)	201 (66.34%)	31 (54.39%)	0.1563	0	198 (55.00%)	2 (50.00%)	134 (58.26%)	62 (49.21%)	0.0990	0	233 (64.72%)	4 (66.67%)	160 (64.00%)	69 (66.35%)	0.6887
	Yes	128 (35.56%)	102 (33.66%)	26 (45.61%)	162 (45.00%)			2 (50.00%)	96 (41.74%)	64 (50.79%)	127 (35.28%)			2 (33.33%)	90 (36.00%)	35 (33.65%)		
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.17±1.26	1.01±1.51	0.3654	0	0.64±0.73	1.55±2.47	0.66±0.68	0.58±0.71	0.3342	1	0.85±1.47	0.52±0.33	0.99±1.71	0.53±0.55	0.0009
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (43.92%)	124 (43.36%)	24 (47.06%)	0.5991	19	217 (63.64%)	2 (50.00%)	125 (58.41%)	90 (73.17%)	0.0093	19	46 (13.49%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (13.19%)	15 (15.00%)	0.7070
	Non-US	189 (56.08%)	162 (56.64%)	27 (52.94%)	124 (36.36%)			2 (50.00%)	89 (41.59%)	33 (26.83%)	295 (86.51%)			6 (100.00%)	204 (86.81%)	85 (85.00%)		
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (43.92%)	124 (43.36%)	24 (47.06%)	.	19	216 (63.34%)	2 (50.00%)	125 (58.41%)	89 (72.36%)	.	19	46 (13.49%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (13.19%)	15 (15.00%)	0.4635
	Europe	58 (17.21%)	51 (17.83%)	7 (13.73%)	46 (13.49%)			1 (25.00%)	33 (15.42%)	12 (9.76%)	112 (32.84%)			2 (33.33%)	80 (34.04%)	30 (30.00%)		

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Male (N=303)	Female (N=57)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=230)	Female (N=126)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=250)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
	Asia		19 (5.64%)	18 (6.29%)	1 (1.96%)			14 (4.11%)	1 (25.00%)	11 (5.14%)	2 (1.63%)			33 (9.68%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (9.79%)	10 (10.00%)	
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.37%)	5 (1.75%)	3 (5.88%)			6 (1.76%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.40%)	3 (2.44%)			10 (2.93%)	1 (16.67%)	3 (1.28%)	6 (6.00%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.59%)	2 (0.70%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.47%)	0 (0.00%)			4 (1.17%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.28%)	1 (1.00%)	
	Africa		11 (3.26%)	7 (2.45%)	4 (7.84%)			3 (0.88%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.40%)	0 (0.00%)			26 (7.62%)	2 (33.33%)	14 (5.96%)	10 (10.00%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.00%)	79 (27.62%)	12 (23.53%)			55 (16.13%)	0 (0.00%)	38 (17.76%)	17 (13.82%)			110 (32.26%)	1 (16.67%)	81 (34.47%)	28 (28.00%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.50%)	21 (6.93%)	6 (10.53%)	0.6989	2	85 (23.74%)	1 (25.00%)	52 (22.81%)	32 (25.40%)	0.8386	10	41 (11.71%)	2 (33.33%)	26 (10.66%)	13 (13.00%)	0.6911
	Neutral		60 (16.67%)	51 (16.83%)	9 (15.79%)			75 (20.95%)	1 (25.00%)	50 (21.93%)	24 (19.05%)			80 (22.86%)	1 (16.67%)	58 (23.77%)	21 (21.00%)	
	Positive		231 (64.17%)	194 (64.03%)	37 (64.91%)			128 (35.75%)	1 (25.00%)	82 (35.96%)	45 (35.71%)			183 (52.29%)	2 (33.33%)	131 (53.69%)	50 (50.00%)	
	Other		42 (11.67%)	37 (12.21%)	5 (8.77%)			70 (19.55%)	1 (25.00%)	44 (19.30%)	25 (19.84%)			46 (13.14%)	1 (16.67%)	29 (11.89%)	16 (16.00%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Male (N=208)	Female (N=32)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=158)	Female (N=79)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=5)	Male (N=164)	Female (N=71)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	126 (60.58%)	26 (81.25%)	0.0135	0	231 (96.25%)	3 (100.00%)	150 (94.94%)	78 (98.73%)	0.0803	0	212 (88.33%)	5 (100.00%)	144 (87.80%)	63 (88.73%)	0.9075
	101+		88 (36.67%)	82 (39.42%)	6 (18.75%)			9 (3.75%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (5.06%)	1 (1.27%)			28 (11.67%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (12.20%)	8 (11.27%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=200)	Male (N=165)	Female (N=35)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=250)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=146)	Female (N=102)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=98)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=67)	Female (N=30)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	88 (44.00%)	71 (43.03%)	17 (48.57%)	0.5465	0	82 (32.80%)	0 (0.00%)	51 (34.93%)	31 (30.39%)	0.2478	0	35 (35.71%)	1 (100.00%)	20 (29.85%)	14 (46.67%)	0.1627
	Midwest		31 (15.50%)	24 (14.55%)	7 (20.00%)			44 (17.60%)	1 (50.00%)	28 (19.18%)	15 (14.71%)			15 (15.31%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (13.43%)	6 (20.00%)	
	South		42 (21.00%)	35 (21.21%)	7 (20.00%)			73 (29.20%)	0 (0.00%)	44 (30.14%)	29 (28.43%)			29 (29.59%)	0 (0.00%)	22 (32.84%)	7 (23.33%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=200)	Male (N=165)	Female (N=35)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=250)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=146)	Female (N=102)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=98)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=67)	Female (N=30)	P-value*
	West		39 (19.50%)	35 (21.21%)	4 (11.43%)			51 (20.40%)	1 (50.00%)	23 (15.75%)	27 (26.47%)			19 (19.39%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (23.88%)	3 (10.00%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=275)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=50)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=354)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=125)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=351)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=241)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	0	172 (62.55%)	140 (62.22%)	32 (64.00%)	0.8143	0	263 (74.29%)	3 (75.00%)	153 (68.00%)	107 (85.60%)	0.0003	1	117 (33.43%)	1 (20.00%)	81 (33.61%)	35 (33.65%)	0.9937
	Non-US		103 (37.45%)	85 (37.78%)	18 (36.00%)			91 (25.71%)	1 (25.00%)	72 (32.00%)	18 (14.40%)			233 (66.57%)	4 (80.00%)	160 (66.39%)	69 (66.35%)	
Continent	North America	0	173 (62.91%)	141 (62.67%)	32 (64.00%)	0.3937	0	259 (73.16%)	2 (50.00%)	151 (67.11%)	106 (84.80%)	0.0066	1	114 (32.57%)	1 (20.00%)	79 (32.78%)	34 (32.69%)	0.7713
	Europe		76 (27.64%)	65 (28.89%)	11 (22.00%)			74 (20.90%)	1 (25.00%)	57 (25.33%)	16 (12.80%)			171 (48.86%)	3 (60.00%)	118 (48.96%)	50 (48.08%)	
	Asia		8 (2.91%)	7 (3.11%)	1 (2.00%)			11 (3.11%)	1 (25.00%)	9 (4.00%)	1 (0.80%)			25 (7.14%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (6.64%)	9 (8.65%)	
	Australia/NZ		13 (4.73%)	9 (4.00%)	4 (8.00%)			6 (1.69%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (1.78%)	2 (1.60%)			22 (6.29%)	1 (20.00%)	13 (5.39%)	8 (7.69%)	
	Central/South America		1 (0.36%)	1 (0.44%)	0 (0.00%)									4 (1.14%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (1.66%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		4 (1.45%)	2 (0.89%)	2 (4.00%)			3 (0.85%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.33%)	0 (0.00%)			13 (3.71%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (4.15%)	3 (2.88%)	
	Other/Unknown							1 (0.28%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.44%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.41%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	74 (26.91%)	70 (31.11%)	4 (8.00%)	0.0017	0	47 (13.28%)	1 (25.00%)	35 (15.56%)	11 (8.80%)	0.2036	0	53 (15.10%)	1 (16.67%)	44 (18.26%)	8 (7.69%)	0.0399
	Neoplasms		39 (14.18%)	29 (12.89%)	10 (20.00%)			21 (5.93%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (6.67%)	6 (4.80%)			30 (8.55%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (9.54%)	7 (6.73%)	
	Infectious Diseases		25 (9.09%)	16 (7.11%)	9 (18.00%)			17 (4.80%)	0 (0.00%)	12 (5.33%)	5 (4.00%)			22 (6.27%)	0 (0.00%)	13 (5.39%)	9 (8.65%)	
	All other		137 (49.82%)	110 (48.89%)	27 (54.00%)			269 (75.99%)	3 (75.00%)	163 (72.44%)	103 (82.40%)			246 (70.09%)	5 (83.33%)	161 (66.80%)	80 (76.92%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	0	54 (19.64%)	48 (21.33%)	6 (12.00%)	0.1329	3	70 (19.94%)	1 (33.33%)	43 (19.20%)	26 (20.97%)	0.7767	2	44 (12.61%)	0 (0.00%)	34 (14.17%)	10 (9.62%)	0.2968
	Yes		221 (80.36%)	177 (78.67%)	44 (88.00%)			281 (80.06%)	2 (66.67%)	181 (80.80%)	98 (79.03%)			305 (87.39%)	5 (100.00%)	206 (85.83%)	94 (90.38%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=275)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=50)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=354)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=125)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=351)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=241)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	0	26 (9.45%)	22 (9.78%)	4 (8.00%)	0.7966	3	36 (10.26%)	1 (33.33%)	21 (9.38%)	14 (11.29%)	0.5782	2	31 (8.88%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (9.58%)	8 (7.69%)	0.6823
	Yes	249 (90.55%)	203 (90.22%)	46 (92.00%)	315 (89.74%)			2 (66.67%)	203 (90.63%)	110 (88.71%)	318 (91.12%)			5 (100.00%)	217 (90.42%)	96 (92.31%)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	0	24 (8.73%)	18 (8.00%)	6 (12.00%)	0.3647	3	31 (8.83%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (7.14%)	15 (12.10%)	0.1705	2	51 (14.61%)	2 (40.00%)	28 (11.67%)	21 (20.19%)	0.0429
	Yes	251 (91.27%)	207 (92.00%)	44 (88.00%)	320 (91.17%)			3 (100.00%)	208 (92.86%)	109 (87.90%)	298 (85.39%)			3 (60.00%)	212 (88.33%)	83 (79.81%)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	0	275 (100.00%)	225 (100.00%)	50 (100.00%)	.	3	351 (100.00%)	3 (100.00%)	224 (100.00%)	124 (100.00%)	.	2	349 (100.00%)	5 (100.00%)	240 (100.00%)	104 (100.00%)	.
Degree	MD-only	0	196 (71.27%)	166 (73.78%)	30 (60.00%)	0.0002	0	198 (55.93%)	2 (50.00%)	130 (57.78%)	66 (52.80%)	0.0002	1	152 (43.43%)	2 (40.00%)	116 (48.13%)	34 (32.69%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		18 (6.55%)	9 (4.00%)	9 (18.00%)			68 (19.21%)	1 (25.00%)	29 (12.89%)	38 (30.40%)			95 (27.14%)	2 (40.00%)	47 (19.50%)	46 (44.23%)	
	Both		59 (21.45%)	50 (22.22%)	9 (18.00%)			65 (18.36%)	1 (25.00%)	51 (22.67%)	13 (10.40%)			83 (23.71%)	0 (0.00%)	68 (28.22%)	15 (14.42%)	
	Neither		2 (0.73%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (4.00%)			23 (6.50%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (6.67%)	8 (6.40%)			20 (5.71%)	1 (20.00%)	10 (4.15%)	9 (8.65%)	
Degree-MD	No	0	20 (7.27%)	9 (4.00%)	11 (22.00%)	<.0001	0	91 (25.71%)	1 (25.00%)	44 (19.56%)	46 (36.80%)	0.0004	1	115 (32.86%)	3 (60.00%)	57 (23.65%)	55 (52.88%)	<.0001
	Yes		255 (92.73%)	216 (96.00%)	39 (78.00%)			263 (74.29%)	3 (75.00%)	181 (80.44%)	79 (63.20%)			235 (67.14%)	2 (40.00%)	184 (76.35%)	49 (47.12%)	
Degree-Dual	No	0	216 (78.55%)	175 (77.78%)	41 (82.00%)	0.5106	0	289 (81.64%)	3 (75.00%)	174 (77.33%)	112 (89.60%)	0.0044	1	267 (76.29%)	5 (100.00%)	173 (71.78%)	89 (85.58%)	0.0060
	Yes		59 (21.45%)	50 (22.22%)	9 (18.00%)			65 (18.36%)	1 (25.00%)	51 (22.67%)	13 (10.40%)			83 (23.71%)	0 (0.00%)	68 (28.22%)	15 (14.42%)	
Title	L-only	0	24 (8.73%)	19 (8.44%)	5 (10.00%)	0.0261	0	26 (7.34%)	0 (0.00%)	17 (7.56%)	9 (7.20%)	0.9625	1	32 (9.14%)	1 (20.00%)	23 (9.54%)	8 (7.69%)	0.2548
	AR-only		39 (14.18%)	26 (11.56%)	13 (26.00%)			100 (28.25%)	0 (0.00%)	64 (28.44%)	36 (28.80%)			90 (25.71%)	1 (20.00%)	56 (23.24%)	33 (31.73%)	
	Both		193 (70.18%)	166 (73.78%)	27 (54.00%)			120 (33.90%)	0 (0.00%)	79 (35.11%)	41 (32.80%)			159 (45.43%)	0 (0.00%)	118 (48.96%)	41 (39.42%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=275)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=50)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=354)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=125)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=351)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=241)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
	Neither		19 (6.91%)	14 (6.22%)	5 (10.00%)			108 (30.51%)	4 (100.00%)	65 (28.89%)	39 (31.20%)			69 (19.71%)	3 (60.00%)	44 (18.26%)	22 (21.15%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	58 (21.09%)	40 (17.78%)	18 (36.00%)	0.0043	0	208 (58.76%)	4 (100.00%)	129 (57.33%)	75 (60.00%)	0.6278	1	159 (45.43%)	4 (80.00%)	100 (41.49%)	55 (52.88%)	0.0510
	Yes		217 (78.91%)	185 (82.22%)	32 (64.00%)			146 (41.24%)	0 (0.00%)	96 (42.67%)	50 (40.00%)			191 (54.57%)	1 (20.00%)	141 (58.51%)	49 (47.12%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	43 (15.64%)	33 (14.67%)	10 (20.00%)	0.3476	0	134 (37.85%)	4 (100.00%)	82 (36.44%)	48 (38.40%)	0.7168	1	101 (28.86%)	4 (80.00%)	67 (27.80%)	30 (28.85%)	0.8429
	Yes		232 (84.36%)	192 (85.33%)	40 (80.00%)			220 (62.15%)	0 (0.00%)	143 (63.56%)	77 (61.60%)			249 (71.14%)	1 (20.00%)	174 (72.20%)	74 (71.15%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with first authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.1.4: Percentage of Female First Author Characteristics (row percentages)

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Male (N=303)	Female (N=57)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=230)	Female (N=126)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=250)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	140 (38.89%)	113 (80.71%)	27 (19.29%)	0.0027	0	140 (38.89%)	1 (0.71%)	85 (61.15%)	54 (38.85%)	0.1441	0	140 (38.89%)	4 (2.86%)	100 (73.53%)	36 (26.47%)	0.2315
	2009-2014	120 (33.33%)	111 (92.50%)	9 (7.50%)	120 (33.33%)			1 (0.83%)	85 (71.43%)	34 (28.57%)	120 (33.33%)			1 (0.83%)	77 (64.71%)	42 (35.29%)		
	2015-2019	100 (27.78%)	79 (79.00%)	21 (21.00%)	100 (27.78%)			2 (2.00%)	60 (61.22%)	38 (38.78%)	100 (27.78%)			1 (1.00%)	73 (73.74%)	26 (26.26%)		
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	101 (28.06%)	80 (79.21%)	21 (20.79%)	0.2188	0	214 (59.44%)	1 (0.47%)	129 (60.56%)	84 (39.44%)	0.0651	0	167 (46.39%)	4 (2.40%)	106 (65.03%)	57 (34.97%)	0.0837
	11-20	163 (45.28%)	143 (87.73%)	20 (12.27%)	105 (29.17%)			2 (1.90%)	70 (67.96%)	33 (32.04%)	128 (35.56%)			2 (1.56%)	96 (76.19%)	30 (23.81%)		
	21+	96 (26.67%)	80 (83.33%)	16 (16.67%)	41 (11.39%)			1 (2.44%)	31 (77.50%)	9 (22.50%)	65 (18.06%)			0 (0.00%)	48 (73.85%)	17 (26.15%)		
Institution Region (at time of Publication) ²	US	0	200 (55.56%)	165 (82.50%)	35 (17.50%)	0.3039	0	250 (69.44%)	2 (0.80%)	146 (58.87%)	102 (41.13%)	0.0004	0	98 (27.22%)	1 (1.02%)	67 (69.07%)	30 (30.93%)	0.7378
	Non-US	160 (44.44%)	138 (86.25%)	22 (13.75%)	110 (30.56%)			2 (1.82%)	84 (77.78%)	24 (22.22%)	262 (72.78%)			5 (1.91%)	183 (71.21%)	74 (28.79%)		
Clinical Trial	No	0	63 (17.50%)	44 (69.84%)	19 (30.16%)	0.0113	0	245 (68.06%)	2 (0.82%)	144 (59.26%)	99 (40.74%)	0.0021	0	194 (53.89%)	2 (1.03%)	132 (68.75%)	60 (31.25%)	0.4048
	Yes	297 (82.50%)	259 (87.21%)	38 (12.79%)	115 (31.94%)			2 (1.74%)	86 (76.11%)	27 (23.89%)	166 (46.11%)			4 (2.41%)	118 (72.84%)	44 (27.16%)		
Grant Funding	No	0	232 (64.44%)	201 (86.64%)	31 (13.36%)	0.1563	0	198 (55.00%)	2 (1.01%)	134 (68.37%)	62 (31.63%)	0.0990	0	233 (64.72%)	4 (1.72%)	160 (69.87%)	69 (30.13%)	0.6887
	Yes	128 (35.56%)	102 (79.69%)	26 (20.31%)	162 (45.00%)			2 (1.23%)	96 (60.00%)	64 (40.00%)	127 (35.28%)			2 (1.57%)	90 (72.00%)	35 (28.00%)		
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.17±1.26	1.01±1.51	0.3654	0	0.64±0.73	1.55±2.47	0.66±0.68	0.58±0.71	0.3342	1	0.85±1.47	0.52±0.33	0.99±1.71	0.53±0.55	0.0009
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (43.92%)	124 (83.78%)	24 (16.22%)	0.5991	19	217 (63.64%)	2 (0.92%)	125 (58.14%)	90 (41.86%)	0.0093	19	46 (13.49%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (67.39%)	15 (32.61%)	0.7070
	Non-US	189 (56.08%)	162 (85.71%)	27 (14.29%)	124 (36.36%)			2 (1.61%)	89 (72.95%)	33 (27.05%)	295 (86.51%)			6 (2.03%)	204 (70.59%)	85 (29.41%)		
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (43.92%)	124 (83.78%)	24 (16.22%)	.	19	216 (63.34%)	2 (0.93%)	125 (58.41%)	89 (41.59%)	.	19	46 (13.49%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (67.39%)	15 (32.61%)	0.4635
	Europe	58 (17.21%)	51 (87.93%)	7 (12.07%)	46 (13.49%)			1 (2.17%)	33 (73.33%)	12 (26.67%)	112 (32.84%)			2 (1.79%)	80 (72.73%)	30 (27.27%)		

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Male (N=303)	Female (N=57)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=230)	Female (N=126)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=250)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
	Asia		19 (5.64%)	18 (94.74%)	1 (5.26%)			14 (4.11%)	1 (7.14%)	11 (84.62%)	2 (15.38%)			33 (9.68%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (69.70%)	10 (30.30%)	
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.37%)	5 (62.50%)	3 (37.50%)			6 (1.76%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (50.00%)	3 (50.00%)			10 (2.93%)	1 (10.00%)	3 (33.33%)	6 (66.67%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.59%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			4 (1.17%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (75.00%)	1 (25.00%)	
	Africa		11 (3.26%)	7 (63.64%)	4 (36.36%)			3 (0.88%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			26 (7.62%)	2 (7.69%)	14 (58.33%)	10 (41.67%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.00%)	79 (86.81%)	12 (13.19%)			55 (16.13%)	0 (0.00%)	38 (69.09%)	17 (30.91%)			110 (32.26%)	1 (0.91%)	81 (74.31%)	28 (25.69%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.50%)	21 (77.78%)	6 (22.22%)	0.6989	2	85 (23.74%)	1 (1.18%)	52 (61.90%)	32 (38.10%)	0.8386	10	41 (11.71%)	2 (4.88%)	26 (66.67%)	13 (33.33%)	0.6911
	Neutral		60 (16.67%)	51 (85.00%)	9 (15.00%)			75 (20.95%)	1 (1.33%)	50 (67.57%)	24 (32.43%)			80 (22.86%)	1 (1.25%)	58 (73.42%)	21 (26.58%)	
	Positive		231 (64.17%)	194 (83.98%)	37 (16.02%)			128 (35.75%)	1 (0.78%)	82 (64.57%)	45 (35.43%)			183 (52.29%)	2 (1.09%)	131 (72.38%)	50 (27.62%)	
	Other		42 (11.67%)	37 (88.10%)	5 (11.90%)			70 (19.55%)	1 (1.43%)	44 (63.77%)	25 (36.23%)			46 (13.14%)	1 (2.17%)	29 (64.44%)	16 (35.56%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Male (N=208)	Female (N=32)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=158)	Female (N=79)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=5)	Male (N=164)	Female (N=71)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	126 (82.89%)	26 (17.11%)	0.0135	0	231 (96.25%)	3 (1.30%)	150 (65.79%)	78 (34.21%)	0.0803	0	212 (88.33%)	5 (2.36%)	144 (69.57%)	63 (30.43%)	0.9075
	101+		88 (36.67%)	82 (93.18%)	6 (6.82%)			9 (3.75%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (88.89%)	1 (11.11%)			28 (11.67%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (71.43%)	8 (28.57%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=200)	Male (N=165)	Female (N=35)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=250)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=146)	Female (N=102)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=98)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=67)	Female (N=30)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	88 (44.00%)	71 (80.68%)	17 (19.32%)	0.5465	0	82 (32.80%)	0 (0.00%)	51 (62.20%)	31 (37.80%)	0.2478	0	35 (35.71%)	1 (2.86%)	20 (58.82%)	14 (41.18%)	0.1627
	Midwest		31 (15.50%)	24 (77.42%)	7 (22.58%)			44 (17.60%)	1 (2.27%)	28 (65.12%)	15 (34.88%)			15 (15.31%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (60.00%)	6 (40.00%)	
	South		42 (21.00%)	35 (83.33%)	7 (16.67%)			73 (29.20%)	0 (0.00%)	44 (60.27%)	29 (39.73%)			29 (29.59%)	0 (0.00%)	22 (75.86%)	7 (24.14%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=200)	Male (N=165)	Female (N=35)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=250)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=146)	Female (N=102)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=98)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=67)	Female (N=30)	P-value*
	West		39 (19.50%)	35 (89.74%)	4 (10.26%)			51 (20.40%)	1 (1.96%)	23 (46.00%)	27 (54.00%)			19 (19.39%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (84.21%)	3 (15.79%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=275)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=50)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=354)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=125)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=351)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=241)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	0	172 (62.55%)	140 (81.40%)	32 (18.60%)	0.8143	0	263 (74.29%)	3 (1.14%)	153 (58.85%)	107 (41.15%)	0.0003	1	117 (33.43%)	1 (0.85%)	81 (69.83%)	35 (30.17%)	0.9937
	Non-US	103 (37.45%)	85 (82.52%)	18 (17.48%)	91 (25.71%)			1 (1.10%)	72 (80.00%)	18 (20.00%)	233 (66.57%)			4 (1.72%)	160 (69.87%)	69 (30.13%)		
Continent	North America	0	173 (62.91%)	141 (81.50%)	32 (18.50%)	0.3937	0	259 (73.16%)	2 (0.77%)	151 (58.75%)	106 (41.25%)	0.0066	1	114 (32.57%)	1 (0.88%)	79 (69.91%)	34 (30.09%)	0.7713
	Europe		76 (27.64%)	65 (85.53%)	11 (14.47%)			74 (20.90%)	1 (1.35%)	57 (78.08%)	16 (21.92%)			171 (48.86%)	3 (1.75%)	118 (70.24%)	50 (29.76%)	
	Asia		8 (2.91%)	7 (87.50%)	1 (12.50%)			11 (3.11%)	1 (9.09%)	9 (90.00%)	1 (10.00%)			25 (7.14%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (64.00%)	9 (36.00%)	
	Australia/NZ		13 (4.73%)	9 (69.23%)	4 (30.77%)			6 (1.69%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)			22 (6.29%)	1 (4.55%)	13 (61.90%)	8 (38.10%)	
	Central/South America		1 (0.36%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)									4 (1.14%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		4 (1.45%)	2 (50.00%)	2 (50.00%)			3 (0.85%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			13 (3.71%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (76.92%)	3 (23.08%)	
	Other/Unknown								1 (0.28%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)			0 (0.00%)	1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	74 (26.91%)	70 (94.59%)	4 (5.41%)	0.0017	0	47 (13.28%)	1 (2.13%)	35 (76.09%)	11 (23.91%)	0.2036	0	53 (15.10%)	1 (1.89%)	44 (84.62%)	8 (15.38%)	0.0399
	Neoplasms		39 (14.18%)	29 (74.36%)	10 (25.64%)			21 (5.93%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (71.43%)	6 (28.57%)			30 (8.55%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (76.67%)	7 (23.33%)	
	Infectious Diseases		25 (9.09%)	16 (64.00%)	9 (36.00%)			17 (4.80%)	0 (0.00%)	12 (70.59%)	5 (29.41%)			22 (6.27%)	0 (0.00%)	13 (59.09%)	9 (40.91%)	
	All other		137 (49.82%)	110 (80.29%)	27 (19.71%)			269 (75.99%)	3 (1.12%)	163 (61.28%)	103 (38.72%)			246 (70.09%)	5 (2.03%)	161 (66.80%)	80 (33.20%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	0	54 (19.64%)	48 (88.89%)	6 (11.11%)	0.1329	3	70 (19.94%)	1 (1.43%)	43 (62.32%)	26 (37.68%)	0.7767	2	44 (12.61%)	0 (0.00%)	34 (77.27%)	10 (22.73%)	0.2968
	Yes		221 (80.36%)	177 (80.09%)	44 (19.91%)			281 (80.06%)	2 (0.71%)	181 (64.87%)	98 (35.13%)			305 (87.39%)	5 (1.64%)	206 (68.67%)	94 (31.33%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=275)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=50)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=354)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=125)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=351)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=241)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	0	26 (9.45%)	22 (84.62%)	4 (15.38%)	0.7966	3	36 (10.26%)	1 (2.78%)	21 (60.00%)	14 (40.00%)	0.5782	2	31 (8.88%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (74.19%)	8 (25.81%)	0.6823
	Yes	249 (90.55%)	203 (81.53%)	46 (18.47%)	315 (89.74%)			2 (0.63%)	203 (64.86%)	110 (35.14%)	318 (91.12%)			5 (1.57%)	217 (69.33%)	96 (30.67%)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	0	24 (8.73%)	18 (75.00%)	6 (25.00%)	0.3647	3	31 (8.83%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (51.61%)	15 (48.39%)	0.1705	2	51 (14.61%)	2 (3.92%)	28 (57.14%)	21 (42.86%)	0.0429
	Yes	251 (91.27%)	207 (82.47%)	44 (17.53%)	320 (91.17%)			3 (0.94%)	208 (65.62%)	109 (34.38%)	298 (85.39%)			3 (1.01%)	212 (71.86%)	83 (28.14%)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	0	275 (100.00%)	225 (81.82%)	50 (18.18%)	.	3	351 (100.00%)	3 (0.85%)	224 (64.37%)	124 (35.63%)	.	2	349 (100.00%)	5 (1.43%)	240 (69.77%)	104 (30.23%)	.
Degree	MD-only	0	196 (71.27%)	166 (84.69%)	30 (15.31%)	0.0002	0	198 (55.93%)	2 (1.01%)	130 (66.33%)	66 (33.67%)	0.0002	1	152 (43.43%)	2 (1.32%)	116 (77.33%)	34 (22.67%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		18 (6.55%)	9 (50.00%)	9 (50.00%)			68 (19.21%)	1 (1.47%)	29 (43.28%)	38 (56.72%)			95 (27.14%)	2 (2.11%)	47 (50.54%)	46 (49.46%)	
	Both		59 (21.45%)	50 (84.75%)	9 (15.25%)			65 (18.36%)	1 (1.54%)	51 (79.69%)	13 (20.31%)			83 (23.71%)	0 (0.00%)	68 (81.93%)	15 (18.07%)	
	Neither		2 (0.73%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)			23 (6.50%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (65.22%)	8 (34.78%)			20 (5.71%)	1 (5.00%)	10 (52.63%)	9 (47.37%)	
Degree-MD	No	0	20 (7.27%)	9 (45.00%)	11 (55.00%)	<.0001	0	91 (25.71%)	1 (1.10%)	44 (48.89%)	46 (51.11%)	0.0004	1	115 (32.86%)	3 (2.61%)	57 (50.89%)	55 (49.11%)	<.0001
	Yes		255 (92.73%)	216 (84.71%)	39 (15.29%)			263 (74.29%)	3 (1.14%)	181 (69.62%)	79 (30.38%)			235 (67.14%)	2 (0.85%)	184 (78.97%)	49 (21.03%)	
Degree-Dual	No	0	216 (78.55%)	175 (81.02%)	41 (18.98%)	0.5106	0	289 (81.64%)	3 (1.04%)	174 (60.84%)	112 (39.16%)	0.0044	1	267 (76.29%)	5 (1.87%)	173 (66.03%)	89 (33.97%)	0.0060
	Yes		59 (21.45%)	50 (84.75%)	9 (15.25%)			65 (18.36%)	1 (1.54%)	51 (79.69%)	13 (20.31%)			83 (23.71%)	0 (0.00%)	68 (81.93%)	15 (18.07%)	
Title	L-only	0	24 (8.73%)	19 (79.17%)	5 (20.83%)	0.0261	0	26 (7.34%)	0 (0.00%)	17 (65.38%)	9 (34.62%)	0.9625	1	32 (9.14%)	1 (3.13%)	23 (74.19%)	8 (25.81%)	0.2548
	AR-only		39 (14.18%)	26 (66.67%)	13 (33.33%)			100 (28.25%)	0 (0.00%)	64 (64.00%)	36 (36.00%)			90 (25.71%)	1 (1.11%)	56 (62.92%)	33 (37.08%)	
	Both		193 (70.18%)	166 (86.01%)	27 (13.99%)			120 (33.90%)	0 (0.00%)	79 (65.83%)	41 (34.17%)			159 (45.43%)	0 (0.00%)	118 (74.21%)	41 (25.79%)	

		NEJM					JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=275)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=50)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=354)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=225)	Female (N=125)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=351)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=241)	Female (N=104)	P-value*
	Neither		19 (6.91%)	14 (73.68%)	5 (26.32%)			108 (30.51%)	4 (3.70%)	65 (62.50%)	39 (37.50%)			69 (19.71%)	3 (4.35%)	44 (66.67%)	22 (33.33%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	58 (21.09%)	40 (68.97%)	18 (31.03%)	0.0043	0	208 (58.76%)	4 (1.92%)	129 (63.24%)	75 (36.76%)	0.6278	1	159 (45.43%)	4 (2.52%)	100 (64.52%)	55 (35.48%)	0.0510
	Yes		217 (78.91%)	185 (85.25%)	32 (14.75%)			146 (41.24%)	0 (0.00%)	96 (65.75%)	50 (34.25%)			191 (54.57%)	1 (0.52%)	141 (74.21%)	49 (25.79%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	43 (15.64%)	33 (76.74%)	10 (23.26%)	0.3476	0	134 (37.85%)	4 (2.99%)	82 (63.08%)	48 (36.92%)	0.7168	1	101 (28.86%)	4 (3.96%)	67 (69.07%)	30 (30.93%)	0.8429
	Yes		232 (84.36%)	192 (82.76%)	40 (17.24%)			220 (62.15%)	0 (0.00%)	143 (65.00%)	77 (35.00%)			249 (71.14%)	1 (0.40%)	174 (70.16%)	74 (29.84%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with first authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Second Author

Tables 2.2.1 and 2.2.2 below showed the descriptive table for publication-level and author-level second author characteristics by the gender of second author in column percentages and row percentages, respectively. More specifically, Tables 2.2.3 and 2.2.4 showed the descriptive tables within each journal.

Table 2.2.1: Percentage of Female Second Author Characteristics (All journals; column percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1046)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=668)	Female (N=358)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	401 (38.34%)	13 (65.00%)	259 (38.77%)	129 (36.03%)	0.6048
	2009-2014		350 (33.46%)	3 (15.00%)	222 (33.23%)	125 (34.92%)	
	2015-2019		295 (28.20%)	4 (20.00%)	187 (27.99%)	104 (29.05%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	448 (42.83%)	10 (50.00%)	269 (40.27%)	169 (47.21%)	0.0680
	11-20		396 (37.86%)	7 (35.00%)	257 (38.47%)	132 (36.87%)	
	21+		202 (19.31%)	3 (15.00%)	142 (21.26%)	57 (15.92%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	505 (48.28%)	3 (15.00%)	321 (48.05%)	181 (50.56%)	0.4322
	Non-US		541 (51.72%)	17 (85.00%)	347 (51.95%)	177 (49.44%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	469 (44.84%)	12 (60.00%)	272 (40.72%)	185 (51.68%)	0.0014
	Yes		577 (55.16%)	8 (40.00%)	396 (59.28%)	173 (48.32%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	635 (60.71%)	17 (85.00%)	416 (62.28%)	202 (56.42%)	0.0705
	Yes		411 (39.29%)	3 (15.00%)	252 (37.72%)	156 (43.58%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.89±1.24	0.79±1.02	0.98±1.37	0.72±0.94	0.0009
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	52	400 (40.24%)	3 (18.75%)	253 (39.66%)	144 (42.35%)	0.4149
	Non-US		594 (59.76%)	13 (81.25%)	385 (60.34%)	196 (57.65%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	52	399 (40.14%)	3 (18.75%)	252 (39.50%)	144 (42.35%)	0.0013
	Europe		210 (21.13%)	4 (25.00%)	118 (18.50%)	88 (25.88%)	
	Asia		65 (6.54%)	4 (25.00%)	39 (6.11%)	22 (6.47%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.41%)	0 (0.00%)	12 (1.88%)	12 (3.53%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.70%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (0.63%)	3 (0.88%)	
	Africa		40 (4.02%)	2 (12.50%)	24 (3.76%)	14 (4.12%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1046)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=668)	Female (N=358)	P-value*
	Other/Unknown		249 (25.05%)	3 (18.75%)	189 (29.62%)	57 (16.76%)	
Directionality	Negative	11	149 (14.40%)	2 (10.00%)	89 (13.48%)	58 (16.34%)	0.1784
	Neutral		207 (20.00%)	8 (40.00%)	128 (19.39%)	71 (20.00%)	
	Positive		532 (51.40%)	5 (25.00%)	359 (54.39%)	168 (47.32%)	
	Other		147 (14.20%)	5 (25.00%)	84 (12.73%)	58 (16.34%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=704)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=446)	Female (N=247)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	579 (82.24%)	11 (100.00%)	353 (79.15%)	215 (87.04%)	0.0132
	101+		125 (17.76%)	0 (0.00%)	93 (20.85%)	32 (12.96%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=505)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=321)	Female (N=181)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	163 (32.28%)	1 (33.33%)	102 (31.78%)	60 (33.15%)	0.0029
	Midwest		89 (17.62%)	1 (33.33%)	70 (21.81%)	18 (9.94%)	
	South		154 (30.50%)	0 (0.00%)	92 (28.66%)	62 (34.25%)	
	West		99 (19.60%)	1 (33.33%)	57 (17.76%)	41 (22.65%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1011)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=641)	Female (N=350)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	4	544 (54.02%)	3 (18.75%)	346 (53.98%)	195 (55.71%)	0.5998
	Non-US		463 (45.98%)	13 (81.25%)	295 (46.02%)	155 (44.29%)	
Continent	North America	4	545 (54.12%)	3 (18.75%)	347 (54.13%)	195 (55.71%)	0.8957
	Europe		326 (32.37%)	8 (50.00%)	205 (31.98%)	113 (32.29%)	
	Asia		50 (4.97%)	5 (31.25%)	29 (4.52%)	16 (4.57%)	
	Australia/NZ		49 (4.87%)	0 (0.00%)	33 (5.15%)	16 (4.57%)	
	Central/South America		8 (0.79%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (0.78%)	3 (0.86%)	
	Africa		27 (2.68%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (3.12%)	7 (2.00%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1011)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=641)	Female (N=350)	P-value*
	Other/Unknown		2 (0.20%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.31%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	152 (15.03%)	1 (5.00%)	124 (19.34%)	27 (7.71%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms		67 (6.63%)	0 (0.00%)	51 (7.96%)	16 (4.57%)	
	Infectious Diseases		43 (4.25%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (3.90%)	18 (5.14%)	
	All other		749 (74.09%)	19 (95.00%)	441 (68.80%)	289 (82.57%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	17	215 (21.63%)	3 (21.43%)	135 (21.23%)	77 (22.38%)	0.6745
	Yes		779 (78.37%)	11 (78.57%)	501 (78.77%)	267 (77.62%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	17	121 (12.17%)	2 (14.29%)	77 (12.11%)	42 (12.21%)	0.9626
	Yes		873 (87.83%)	12 (85.71%)	559 (87.89%)	302 (87.79%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	17	100 (10.06%)	1 (7.14%)	59 (9.28%)	40 (11.63%)	0.2437
	Yes		894 (89.94%)	13 (92.86%)	577 (90.72%)	304 (88.37%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	17	994 (100.00%)	14 (100.00%)	636 (100.00%)	344 (100.00%)	.
Degree	MD-only	3	463 (45.93%)	8 (47.06%)	340 (53.04%)	115 (32.86%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		266 (26.39%)	5 (29.41%)	138 (21.53%)	123 (35.14%)	
	Both		152 (15.08%)	2 (11.76%)	115 (17.94%)	35 (10.00%)	
	Neither		127 (12.60%)	2 (11.76%)	48 (7.49%)	77 (22.00%)	
Degree-MD	No	3	393 (38.99%)	7 (41.18%)	186 (29.02%)	200 (57.14%)	<.0001
	Yes		615 (61.01%)	10 (58.82%)	455 (70.98%)	150 (42.86%)	
Degree-Dual	No	3	856 (84.92%)	15 (88.24%)	526 (82.06%)	315 (90.00%)	0.0009
	Yes		152 (15.08%)	2 (11.76%)	115 (17.94%)	35 (10.00%)	
Title	L-only	3	92 (9.13%)	2 (11.76%)	59 (9.20%)	31 (8.86%)	<.0001
	AR-only		282 (27.98%)	1 (5.88%)	179 (27.93%)	102 (29.14%)	
	Both		355 (35.22%)	1 (5.88%)	273 (42.59%)	81 (23.14%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1011)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=641)	Female (N=350)	P-value*
	Neither		279 (27.68%)	13 (76.47%)	130 (20.28%)	136 (38.86%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	3	561 (55.65%)	14 (82.35%)	309 (48.21%)	238 (68.00%)	<.0001
	Yes		447 (44.35%)	3 (17.65%)	332 (51.79%)	112 (32.00%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	3	371 (36.81%)	15 (88.24%)	189 (29.49%)	167 (47.71%)	<.0001
	Yes		637 (63.19%)	2 (11.76%)	452 (70.51%)	183 (52.29%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with second authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.2.2: Percentage of Female Second Author Characteristics (All journals; row percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1046)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=668)	Female (N=358)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	401 (38.34%)	13 (3.24%)	259 (66.75%)	129 (33.25%)	0.6048
	2009-2014		350 (33.46%)	3 (0.86%)	222 (63.98%)	125 (36.02%)	
	2015-2019		295 (28.20%)	4 (1.36%)	187 (64.26%)	104 (35.74%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	448 (42.83%)	10 (2.23%)	269 (61.42%)	169 (38.58%)	0.0680
	11-20		396 (37.86%)	7 (1.77%)	257 (66.07%)	132 (33.93%)	
	21+		202 (19.31%)	3 (1.49%)	142 (71.36%)	57 (28.64%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	505 (48.28%)	3 (0.59%)	321 (63.94%)	181 (36.06%)	0.4322
	Non-US		541 (51.72%)	17 (3.14%)	347 (66.22%)	177 (33.78%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	469 (44.84%)	12 (2.56%)	272 (59.52%)	185 (40.48%)	0.0014
	Yes		577 (55.16%)	8 (1.39%)	396 (69.60%)	173 (30.40%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	635 (60.71%)	17 (2.68%)	416 (67.31%)	202 (32.69%)	0.0705
	Yes		411 (39.29%)	3 (0.73%)	252 (61.76%)	156 (38.24%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.89±1.24	0.79±1.02	0.98±1.37	0.72±0.94	0.0009
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	52	400 (40.24%)	3 (0.75%)	253 (63.73%)	144 (36.27%)	0.4149
	Non-US		594 (59.76%)	13 (2.19%)	385 (66.27%)	196 (33.73%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	52	399 (40.14%)	3 (0.75%)	252 (63.64%)	144 (36.36%)	0.0013
	Europe		210 (21.13%)	4 (1.90%)	118 (57.28%)	88 (42.72%)	
	Asia		65 (6.54%)	4 (6.15%)	39 (63.93%)	22 (36.07%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.41%)	0 (0.00%)	12 (50.00%)	12 (50.00%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.70%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (57.14%)	3 (42.86%)	
	Africa		40 (4.02%)	2 (5.00%)	24 (63.16%)	14 (36.84%)	
	Other/Unknown		249 (25.05%)	3 (1.20%)	189 (76.83%)	57 (23.17%)	
Directionality	Negative	11	149 (14.40%)	2 (1.34%)	89 (60.54%)	58 (39.46%)	0.1784
	Neutral		207 (20.00%)	8 (3.86%)	128 (64.32%)	71 (35.68%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1046)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=668)	Female (N=358)	P-value*
	Positive		532 (51.40%)	5 (0.94%)	359 (68.12%)	168 (31.88%)	
	Other		147 (14.20%)	5 (3.40%)	84 (59.15%)	58 (40.85%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=704)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=446)	Female (N=247)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	579 (82.24%)	11 (1.90%)	353 (62.15%)	215 (37.85%)	0.0132
	101+		125 (17.76%)	0 (0.00%)	93 (74.40%)	32 (25.60%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=505)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=321)	Female (N=181)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Midwest	0	89 (17.62%)	1 (1.12%)	70 (79.55%)	18 (20.45%)	0.0029
	Northeast		163 (32.28%)	1 (0.61%)	102 (62.96%)	60 (37.04%)	
	South		154 (30.50%)	0 (0.00%)	92 (59.74%)	62 (40.26%)	
	West		99 (19.60%)	1 (1.01%)	57 (58.16%)	41 (41.84%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1011)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=641)	Female (N=350)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	4	544 (54.02%)	3 (0.55%)	346 (63.96%)	195 (36.04%)	0.5998
	Non-US		463 (45.98%)	13 (2.81%)	295 (65.56%)	155 (34.44%)	
Continent	North America	4	545 (54.12%)	3 (0.55%)	347 (64.02%)	195 (35.98%)	0.8957
	Europe		326 (32.37%)	8 (2.45%)	205 (64.47%)	113 (35.53%)	
	Asia		50 (4.97%)	5 (10.00%)	29 (64.44%)	16 (35.56%)	
	Australia/NZ		49 (4.87%)	0 (0.00%)	33 (67.35%)	16 (32.65%)	
	Central/South America		8 (0.79%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (62.50%)	3 (37.50%)	
	Africa		27 (2.68%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (74.07%)	7 (25.93%)	
	Other/Unknown		2 (0.20%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	152 (15.03%)	1 (0.66%)	124 (82.12%)	27 (17.88%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms		67 (6.63%)	0 (0.00%)	51 (76.12%)	16 (23.88%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1011)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=641)	Female (N=350)	P-value*
	Infectious Diseases		43 (4.25%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (58.14%)	18 (41.86%)	
	All other		749 (74.09%)	19 (2.54%)	441 (60.41%)	289 (39.59%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	17	215 (21.63%)	3 (1.40%)	135 (63.68%)	77 (36.32%)	0.6745
	Yes		779 (78.37%)	11 (1.41%)	501 (65.23%)	267 (34.77%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	17	121 (12.17%)	2 (1.65%)	77 (64.71%)	42 (35.29%)	0.9626
	Yes		873 (87.83%)	12 (1.37%)	559 (64.92%)	302 (35.08%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	17	100 (10.06%)	1 (1.00%)	59 (59.60%)	40 (40.40%)	0.2437
	Yes		894 (89.94%)	13 (1.45%)	577 (65.49%)	304 (34.51%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	17	994 (100.00%)	14 (1.41%)	636 (64.90%)	344 (35.10%)	.
Degree	MD-only	3	463 (45.93%)	8 (1.73%)	340 (74.73%)	115 (25.27%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		266 (26.39%)	5 (1.88%)	138 (52.87%)	123 (47.13%)	
	Both		152 (15.08%)	2 (1.32%)	115 (76.67%)	35 (23.33%)	
	Neither		127 (12.60%)	2 (1.57%)	48 (38.40%)	77 (61.60%)	
Degree-MD	No	3	393 (38.99%)	7 (1.78%)	186 (48.19%)	200 (51.81%)	<.0001
	Yes		615 (61.01%)	10 (1.63%)	455 (75.21%)	150 (24.79%)	
Degree-Dual	No	3	856 (84.92%)	15 (1.75%)	526 (62.54%)	315 (37.46%)	0.0009
	Yes		152 (15.08%)	2 (1.32%)	115 (76.67%)	35 (23.33%)	
Title	L-only	3	92 (9.13%)	2 (2.17%)	59 (65.56%)	31 (34.44%)	<.0001
	AR-only		282 (27.98%)	1 (0.35%)	179 (63.70%)	102 (36.30%)	
	Both		355 (35.22%)	1 (0.28%)	273 (77.12%)	81 (22.88%)	
	Neither		279 (27.68%)	13 (4.66%)	130 (48.87%)	136 (51.13%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	3	561 (55.65%)	14 (2.50%)	309 (56.49%)	238 (43.51%)	<.0001
	Yes		447 (44.35%)	3 (0.67%)	332 (74.77%)	112 (25.23%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1011)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=641)	Female (N=350)	P-value*
Title-Academic Rank	No	3	371 (36.81%)	15 (4.04%)	189 (53.09%)	167 (46.91%)	<.0001
	Yes		637 (63.19%)	2 (0.31%)	452 (71.18%)	183 (28.82%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with second authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.2.3: Percentage of Female Second Author Characteristics (column percentages)

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=258)	Female (N=97)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=337)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=186)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=350)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=224)	Female (N=116)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	139 (38.72%)	4 (100.00%)	103 (39.92%)	32 (32.99%)	0.3835	0	128 (37.98%)	2 (33.33%)	74 (39.78%)	52 (35.86%)	0.6890	0	134 (38.29%)	7 (70.00%)	82 (36.61%)	45 (38.79%)	0.8973
	2009-2014		120 (33.43%)	0 (0.00%)	86 (33.33%)	34 (35.05%)			111 (32.94%)	0 (0.00%)	59 (31.72%)	52 (35.86%)			119 (34.00%)	3 (30.00%)	77 (34.38%)	39 (33.62%)	
	2015-2019		100 (27.86%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (26.74%)	31 (31.96%)			98 (29.08%)	4 (66.67%)	53 (28.49%)	41 (28.28%)			97 (27.71%)	0 (0.00%)	65 (29.02%)	32 (27.59%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	100 (27.86%)	2 (50.00%)	63 (24.42%)	35 (36.08%)	0.1309	0	191 (56.68%)	2 (33.33%)	104 (55.91%)	85 (58.62%)	0.7519	0	157 (44.86%)	6 (60.00%)	102 (45.54%)	49 (42.24%)	0.5635
	11-20		163 (45.40%)	1 (25.00%)	122 (47.29%)	40 (41.24%)			105 (31.16%)	2 (33.33%)	58 (31.18%)	45 (31.03%)			128 (36.57%)	4 (40.00%)	77 (34.38%)	47 (40.52%)	
	21+		96 (26.74%)	1 (25.00%)	73 (28.29%)	22 (22.68%)			41 (12.17%)	2 (33.33%)	24 (12.90%)	15 (10.34%)			65 (18.57%)	0 (0.00%)	45 (20.09%)	20 (17.24%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	193 (53.76%)	3 (75.00%)	136 (52.71%)	54 (55.67%)	0.7795	0	226 (67.06%)	0 (0.00%)	121 (65.05%)	105 (72.41%)	0.1420	0	86 (24.57%)	0 (0.00%)	64 (28.57%)	22 (18.97%)	0.0620
	Non-US		166 (46.24%)	1 (25.00%)	122 (47.29%)	43 (44.33%)			111 (32.94%)	6 (100.00%)	65 (34.95%)	40 (27.59%)			264 (75.43%)	10 (100.00%)	160 (71.43%)	94 (81.03%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	62 (17.27%)	3 (75.00%)	39 (15.12%)	20 (20.62%)	0.2799	0	222 (65.88%)	2 (33.33%)	116 (62.37%)	104 (71.72%)	0.0664	0	185 (52.86%)	7 (70.00%)	117 (52.23%)	61 (52.59%)	0.9144
	Yes		297 (82.73%)	1 (25.00%)	219 (84.88%)	77 (79.38%)			115 (34.12%)	4 (66.67%)	70 (37.63%)	41 (28.28%)			165 (47.14%)	3 (30.00%)	107 (47.77%)	55 (47.41%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	231 (64.35%)	4 (100.00%)	172 (66.67%)	55 (56.70%)	0.0839	0	181 (53.71%)	4 (66.67%)	98 (52.69%)	79 (54.48%)	0.7152	0	223 (63.71%)	9 (90.00%)	146 (65.18%)	68 (58.62%)	0.2591
	Yes		128 (35.65%)	0 (0.00%)	86 (33.33%)	42 (43.30%)			156 (46.29%)	2 (33.33%)	88 (47.31%)	66 (45.52%)			127 (36.29%)	1 (10.00%)	78 (34.82%)	48 (41.38%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.74±1.84	1.24±1.39	0.87±0.99	0.0146	0	0.64±0.74	0.45±0.42	0.66±0.73	0.63±0.77	0.6457	1	0.86±1.49	0.62±0.69	0.94±1.68	0.70±1.08	0.1587
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (44.05%)	0 (0.00%)	111 (46.06%)	37 (40.66%)	0.2829	12	206 (63.38%)	2 (40.00%)	109 (60.56%)	95 (67.86%)	0.1650	17	46 (13.81%)	1 (14.29%)	33 (15.21%)	12 (11.01%)	0.3000
	Non-US		188 (55.95%)	4 (100.00%)	130 (53.94%)	54 (59.34%)			119 (36.62%)	3 (60.00%)	71 (39.44%)	45 (32.14%)			287 (86.19%)	6 (85.71%)	184 (84.79%)	97 (88.99%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (44.05%)	0 (0.00%)	111 (46.06%)	37 (40.66%)	.	12	205 (63.08%)	2 (40.00%)	108 (60.00%)	95 (67.86%)	.	17	46 (13.81%)	1 (14.29%)	33 (15.21%)	12 (11.01%)	.
	Europe		57 (16.96%)	1 (25.00%)	36 (14.94%)	20 (21.98%)			46 (14.15%)	1 (20.00%)	24 (13.33%)	21 (15.00%)			107 (32.13%)	2 (28.57%)	58 (26.73%)	47 (43.12%)	
	Asia		19 (5.65%)	1 (25.00%)	11 (4.56%)	7 (7.69%)			14 (4.31%)	2 (40.00%)	9 (5.00%)	3 (2.14%)			32 (9.61%)	1 (14.29%)	19 (8.76%)	12 (11.01%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=258)	Female (N=97)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=337)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=186)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=350)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=224)	Female (N=116)	P-value*
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.38%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (1.66%)	4 (4.40%)			6 (1.85%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (2.22%)	2 (1.43%)			10 (3.00%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (1.84%)	6 (5.50%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.60%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.83%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.31%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.71%)			4 (1.20%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.92%)	2 (1.83%)	
	Africa		11 (3.27%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (1.66%)	7 (7.69%)			3 (0.92%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.11%)	1 (0.71%)			26 (7.81%)	2 (28.57%)	18 (8.29%)	6 (5.50%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.08%)	2 (50.00%)	73 (30.29%)	16 (17.58%)			50 (15.38%)	0 (0.00%)	33 (18.33%)	17 (12.14%)			108 (32.43%)	1 (14.29%)	83 (38.25%)	24 (22.02%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.52%)	0 (0.00%)	19 (7.36%)	8 (8.25%)	0.3626	2	82 (24.48%)	1 (16.67%)	48 (25.95%)	33 (22.92%)	0.9192	9	40 (11.73%)	1 (10.00%)	22 (10.14%)	17 (14.91%)	0.5714
	Neutral		60 (16.71%)	2 (50.00%)	41 (15.89%)	17 (17.53%)			69 (20.60%)	3 (50.00%)	36 (19.46%)	30 (20.83%)			78 (22.87%)	3 (30.00%)	51 (23.50%)	24 (21.05%)	
	Positive		231 (64.35%)	1 (25.00%)	174 (67.44%)	56 (57.73%)			122 (36.42%)	2 (33.33%)	67 (36.22%)	53 (36.81%)			179 (52.49%)	2 (20.00%)	118 (54.38%)	59 (51.75%)	
	Other		41 (11.42%)	1 (25.00%)	24 (9.30%)	16 (16.49%)			62 (18.51%)	0 (0.00%)	34 (18.38%)	28 (19.44%)			44 (12.90%)	4 (40.00%)	26 (11.98%)	14 (12.28%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=168)	Female (N=71)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=229)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=123)	Female (N=99)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=235)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=152)	Female (N=77)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	1 (100.00%)	102 (60.71%)	49 (69.01%)	0.3355	0	220 (96.07%)	4 (100.00%)	119 (94.44%)	97 (97.98%)	0.1538	0	207 (88.09%)	6 (100.00%)	132 (86.84%)	69 (89.61%)	0.5677
	101+		88 (36.67%)	0 (0.00%)	66 (39.29%)	22 (30.99%)				9 (3.93%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (5.56%)			2 (2.02%)		28 (11.91%)	0 (0.00%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET							
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=193)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=136)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=226)	Unknown (N=0)	Male (N=121)	Female (N=105)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=86)	Unknown (N=0)	Male (N=64)	Female (N=22)	P-value*		
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	68 (35.23%)	1 (33.33%)	44 (32.35%)	23 (42.59%)	0.2785	0	63 (27.88%)		35 (28.93%)	28 (26.67%)	0.0005	0	32 (37.21%)		23 (35.94%)	9 (40.91%)	0.9535		
	Midwest		31 (16.06%)	1 (33.33%)	25 (18.38%)	5 (9.26%)				40 (17.70%)		32 (26.45%)			8 (7.62%)		18 (20.93%)			13 (20.31%)	5 (22.73%)
	South		59 (30.57%)	0 (0.00%)	42 (30.88%)	17 (31.48%)				77 (34.07%)		36 (29.75%)			41 (39.05%)		18 (20.93%)			14 (21.88%)	4 (18.18%)
	West		35 (18.13%)	1 (33.33%)	25 (18.38%)	9 (16.67%)				46 (20.35%)		18 (14.88%)			28 (26.67%)		18 (20.93%)			14 (21.88%)	4 (18.18%)

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=245)	Female (N=95)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=336)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=185)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=221)	Female (N=113)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	0	205 (59.59%)	3 (75.00%)	146 (59.59%)	56 (58.95%)	0.9135	0	244 (72.62%)	0 (0.00%)	134 (72.43%)	110 (75.86%)	0.4812	4	102 (30.00%)	0 (0.00%)	72 (32.58%)	30 (26.55%)	0.2576
	Non-US		139 (40.41%)	1 (25.00%)	99 (40.41%)	39 (41.05%)			92 (27.38%)	6 (100.00%)	51 (27.57%)	35 (24.14%)			238 (70.00%)	6 (100.00%)	149 (67.42%)	83 (73.45%)	
Continent	North America	0	207 (60.17%)	3 (75.00%)	148 (60.41%)	56 (58.95%)	0.9692	0	241 (71.73%)	0 (0.00%)	131 (70.81%)	110 (75.86%)	0.4589	4	104 (30.59%)	0 (0.00%)	74 (33.48%)	30 (26.55%)	0.3467
	Europe		97 (28.20%)	1 (25.00%)	70 (28.57%)	26 (27.37%)			74 (22.02%)	3 (50.00%)	40 (21.62%)	31 (21.38%)			159 (46.76%)	4 (66.67%)	98 (44.34%)	57 (50.44%)	
	Asia		11 (3.20%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (3.27%)	3 (3.16%)			13 (3.87%)	3 (50.00%)	8 (4.32%)	2 (1.38%)			27 (7.94%)	2 (33.33%)	13 (5.88%)	12 (10.62%)	
	Australia/NZ		16 (4.65%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (4.08%)	6 (6.32%)			5 (1.49%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (2.16%)	1 (0.69%)			29 (8.53%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (9.05%)	9 (7.96%)	
	Central/South America		4 (1.16%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.22%)	1 (1.05%)									4 (1.18%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.90%)	2 (1.77%)	
	Africa		8 (2.33%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (2.04%)	3 (3.16%)			3 (0.89%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.08%)	1 (0.69%)			16 (4.71%)	0 (0.00%)	13 (5.88%)	3 (2.65%)	
	Other/Unknown		1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.41%)	0 (0.00%)									1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.45%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	79 (22.97%)	0 (0.00%)	66 (26.94%)	13 (13.68%)	0.0121	0	33 (9.82%)	1 (16.67%)	25 (13.51%)	7 (4.83%)	0.0254	0	44 (12.79%)	0 (0.00%)	36 (16.29%)	8 (7.08%)	0.0386
	Neoplasms		37 (10.76%)	0 (0.00%)	29 (11.84%)	8 (8.42%)			13 (3.87%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (4.86%)	4 (2.76%)			17 (4.94%)	0 (0.00%)	13 (5.88%)	4 (3.54%)	
	Infectious Diseases		14 (4.07%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (2.86%)	7 (7.37%)			12 (3.57%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (2.70%)	7 (4.83%)			17 (4.94%)	0 (0.00%)	13 (5.88%)	4 (3.54%)	
	All other		214 (62.21%)	4 (100.00%)	143 (58.37%)	67 (70.53%)			278 (82.74%)	5 (83.33%)	146 (78.92%)	127 (87.59%)			266 (77.33%)	10 (100.00%)	159 (71.95%)	97 (85.84%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	4	84 (24.71%)	1 (50.00%)	57 (23.36%)	26 (27.66%)	0.4767	5	85 (25.68%)	1 (16.67%)	49 (26.92%)	35 (24.48%)	0.7008	8	49 (14.58%)	1 (16.67%)	32 (14.55%)	16 (14.55%)	1.0000
	Yes		256 (75.29%)	1 (50.00%)	187 (76.64%)	68 (72.34%)			246 (74.32%)	5 (83.33%)	133 (73.08%)	108 (75.52%)			287 (85.42%)	5 (83.33%)	188 (85.45%)	94 (85.45%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	4	39 (11.47%)	1 (50.00%)	29 (11.89%)	9 (9.57%)	0.5772	5	43 (12.99%)	0 (0.00%)	21 (11.54%)	22 (15.38%)	0.3188	8	40 (11.90%)	1 (16.67%)	28 (12.73%)	11 (10.00%)	0.5892
	Yes		301 (88.53%)	1 (50.00%)	215 (88.11%)	85 (90.43%)			288 (87.01%)	6 (100.00%)	161 (88.46%)	121 (84.62%)			296 (88.10%)	5 (83.33%)	192 (87.27%)	99 (90.00%)	
Concordance of Specialty	No	4	33 (9.71%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (8.20%)	13 (13.83%)	0.1512	5	26 (7.85%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (8.24%)	11 (7.69%)	1.0000	8	44 (13.10%)	1 (16.67%)	26 (11.82%)	17 (15.45%)	0.3897

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=245)	Female (N=95)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=336)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=185)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=221)	Female (N=113)	P-value*
with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	Yes		307 (90.29%)	2 (100.00%)	224 (91.80%)	81 (86.17%)			305 (92.15%)	6 (100.00%)	167 (91.76%)	132 (92.31%)			292 (86.90%)	5 (83.33%)	194 (88.18%)	93 (84.55%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	4	340 (100.00%)	2 (100.00%)	244 (100.00%)	94 (100.00%)	.	5	331 (100.00%)	6 (100.00%)	182 (100.00%)	143 (100.00%)	.	8	336 (100.00%)	6 (100.00%)	220 (100.00%)	110 (100.00%)	.
Degree	MD-only	0	200 (58.14%)	2 (50.00%)	150 (61.22%)	48 (50.53%)	0.0003	0	138 (41.07%)	2 (33.33%)	93 (50.27%)	43 (29.66%)	<.0001	3	130 (38.12%)	4 (57.14%)	101 (45.70%)	25 (22.12%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		60 (17.44%)	2 (50.00%)	31 (12.65%)	27 (28.42%)			95 (28.27%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (25.95%)	47 (32.41%)			117 (34.31%)	3 (42.86%)	63 (28.51%)	51 (45.13%)	
	Both		65 (18.90%)	0 (0.00%)	54 (22.04%)	11 (11.58%)			43 (12.80%)	2 (33.33%)	28 (15.14%)	13 (8.97%)			46 (13.49%)	0 (0.00%)	35 (15.84%)	11 (9.73%)	
	Neither		19 (5.52%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (4.08%)	9 (9.47%)			60 (17.86%)	2 (33.33%)	16 (8.65%)	42 (28.97%)			48 (14.08%)	0 (0.00%)	22 (9.95%)	26 (23.01%)	
Degree-MD	No	0	79 (22.97%)	2 (50.00%)	41 (16.73%)	36 (37.89%)	<.0001	0	155 (46.13%)	2 (33.33%)	64 (34.59%)	89 (61.38%)	<.0001	3	165 (48.39%)	3 (42.86%)	85 (38.46%)	77 (68.14%)	<.0001
	Yes		265 (77.03%)	2 (50.00%)	204 (83.27%)	59 (62.11%)			181 (53.87%)	4 (66.67%)	121 (65.41%)	56 (38.62%)			176 (51.61%)	4 (57.14%)	136 (61.54%)	36 (31.86%)	
Degree-Dual	No	0	279 (81.10%)	4 (100.00%)	191 (77.96%)	84 (88.42%)	0.0277	0	293 (87.20%)	4 (66.67%)	157 (84.86%)	132 (91.03%)	0.0917	3	295 (86.51%)	7 (100.00%)	186 (84.16%)	102 (90.27%)	0.1257
	Yes		65 (18.90%)	0 (0.00%)	54 (22.04%)	11 (11.58%)			43 (12.80%)	2 (33.33%)	28 (15.14%)	13 (8.97%)			46 (13.49%)	0 (0.00%)	35 (15.84%)	11 (9.73%)	
Title	L-only	0	39 (11.34%)	1 (25.00%)	27 (11.02%)	11 (11.58%)	0.0006	0	27 (8.04%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (7.57%)	13 (8.97%)	0.0014	3	28 (8.21%)	1 (14.29%)	19 (8.60%)	8 (7.08%)	0.0078
	AR-only		89 (25.87%)	0 (0.00%)	58 (23.67%)	31 (32.63%)			82 (24.40%)	0 (0.00%)	50 (27.03%)	32 (22.07%)			114 (33.43%)	1 (14.29%)	74 (33.48%)	39 (34.51%)	
	Both		166 (48.26%)	0 (0.00%)	135 (55.10%)	31 (32.63%)			83 (24.70%)	0 (0.00%)	59 (31.89%)	24 (16.55%)			113 (33.14%)	1 (14.29%)	85 (38.46%)	27 (23.89%)	
	Neither		50 (14.53%)	3 (75.00%)	25 (10.20%)	22 (23.16%)			144 (42.86%)	6 (100.00%)	62 (33.51%)	76 (52.41%)			86 (25.22%)	4 (57.14%)	43 (19.46%)	39 (34.51%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	139 (40.41%)	3 (75.00%)	83 (33.88%)	53 (55.79%)	0.0002	0	226 (67.26%)	6 (100.00%)	112 (60.54%)	108 (74.48%)	0.0077	3	200 (58.65%)	5 (71.43%)	117 (52.94%)	78 (69.03%)	0.0048
	Yes		205 (59.59%)	1 (25.00%)	162 (66.12%)	42 (44.21%)			110 (32.74%)	0 (0.00%)	73 (39.46%)	37 (25.52%)			141 (41.35%)	2 (28.57%)	104 (47.06%)	35 (30.97%)	

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA					LANCET						
		Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=245)	Female (N=95)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=336)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=185)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=221)	Female (N=113)	P-value*
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	89 (25.87%)	4 (100.00%)	52 (21.22%)	33 (34.74%)	0.0098	0	171 (50.89%)	6 (100.00%)	76 (41.08%)	89 (61.38%)	0.0003	3	114 (33.43%)	5 (71.43%)	62 (28.05%)	47 (41.59%)	0.0125
	Yes		255 (74.13%)	0 (0.00%)	193 (78.78%)	62 (65.26%)					165 (49.11%)	0 (0.00%)			109 (58.92%)	56 (38.62%)			

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with second authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.2.4: Percentage of Female Second Author Characteristics (row percentages)

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=258)	Female (N=97)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=337)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=186)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=350)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=224)	Female (N=116)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	139 (38.72%)	4 (2.88%)	103 (76.30%)	32 (23.70%)	0.3835	0	128 (37.98%)	2 (1.56%)	74 (58.73%)	52 (41.27%)	0.6890	0	134 (38.29%)	7 (5.22%)	82 (64.57%)	45 (35.43%)	0.8973
	2009-2014		120 (33.43%)	0 (0.00%)	86 (71.67%)	34 (28.33%)			111 (32.94%)	0 (0.00%)	59 (53.15%)	52 (46.85%)			119 (34.00%)	3 (2.52%)	77 (66.38%)	39 (33.62%)	
	2015-2019		100 (27.86%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (69.00%)	31 (31.00%)			98 (29.08%)	4 (4.08%)	53 (56.38%)	41 (43.62%)			97 (27.71%)	0 (0.00%)	65 (67.01%)	32 (32.99%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	100 (27.86%)	2 (2.00%)	63 (64.29%)	35 (35.71%)	0.1309	0	191 (56.68%)	2 (1.05%)	104 (55.03%)	85 (44.97%)	0.7519	0	157 (44.86%)	6 (3.82%)	102 (67.55%)	49 (32.45%)	0.5635
	11-20		163 (45.40%)	1 (0.61%)	122 (75.31%)	40 (24.69%)			105 (31.16%)	2 (1.90%)	58 (56.31%)	45 (43.69%)			128 (36.57%)	4 (3.13%)	77 (62.10%)	47 (37.90%)	
	21+		96 (26.74%)	1 (1.04%)	73 (76.84%)	22 (23.16%)			41 (12.17%)	2 (4.88%)	24 (61.54%)	15 (38.46%)			65 (18.57%)	0 (0.00%)	45 (69.23%)	20 (30.77%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	193 (53.76%)	3 (1.55%)	136 (71.58%)	54 (28.42%)	0.7795	0	226 (67.06%)	0 (0.00%)	121 (53.54%)	105 (46.46%)	0.1420	0	86 (24.57%)	0 (0.00%)	64 (74.42%)	22 (25.58%)	0.0620
	Non-US		166 (46.24%)	1 (0.60%)	122 (73.94%)	43 (26.06%)			111 (32.94%)	6 (5.41%)	65 (61.90%)	40 (38.10%)			264 (75.43%)	10 (3.79%)	160 (62.99%)	94 (37.01%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	62 (17.27%)	3 (4.84%)	39 (66.10%)	20 (33.90%)	0.2799	0	222 (65.88%)	2 (0.90%)	116 (52.73%)	104 (47.27%)	0.0664	0	185 (52.86%)	7 (3.78%)	117 (65.73%)	61 (34.27%)	0.9144
	Yes		297 (82.73%)	1 (0.34%)	219 (73.99%)	77 (26.01%)			115 (34.12%)	4 (3.48%)	70 (63.06%)	41 (36.94%)			165 (47.14%)	3 (1.82%)	107 (66.05%)	55 (33.95%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	231 (64.35%)	4 (1.73%)	172 (75.77%)	55 (24.23%)	0.0839	0	181 (53.71%)	4 (2.21%)	98 (55.37%)	79 (44.63%)	0.7152	0	223 (63.71%)	9 (4.04%)	146 (68.22%)	68 (31.78%)	0.2591
	Yes		128 (35.65%)	0 (0.00%)	86 (67.19%)	42 (32.81%)			156 (46.29%)	2 (1.28%)	88 (57.14%)	66 (42.86%)			127 (36.29%)	1 (0.79%)	78 (61.90%)	48 (38.10%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.74±1.84	1.24±1.39	0.87±0.99	0.0146	0	0.64±0.74	0.45±0.42	0.66±0.73	0.63±0.77	0.6457	1	0.86±1.49	0.62±0.69	0.94±1.68	0.70±1.08	0.1587
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (44.05%)	0 (0.00%)	111 (75.00%)	37 (25.00%)	0.2829	12	206 (63.38%)	2 (0.97%)	109 (53.43%)	95 (46.57%)	0.1650	17	46 (13.81%)	1 (2.17%)	33 (73.33%)	12 (26.67%)	0.3000
	Non-US		188 (55.95%)	4 (2.13%)	130 (70.65%)	54 (29.35%)			119 (36.62%)	3 (2.52%)	71 (61.21%)	45 (38.79%)			287 (86.19%)	6 (2.09%)	184 (65.48%)	97 (34.52%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (44.05%)	0 (0.00%)	111 (75.00%)	37 (25.00%)	.	12	205 (63.08%)	2 (0.98%)	108 (53.20%)	95 (46.80%)	.	17	46 (13.81%)	1 (2.17%)	33 (73.33%)	12 (26.67%)	.
	Europe		57 (16.96%)	1 (1.75%)	36 (64.29%)	20 (35.71%)			46 (14.15%)	1 (2.17%)	24 (53.33%)	21 (46.67%)			107 (32.13%)	2 (1.87%)	58 (55.24%)	47 (44.76%)	
	Asia		19 (5.65%)	1 (5.26%)	11 (61.11%)	7 (38.89%)			14 (4.31%)	2 (14.29%)	9 (75.00%)	3 (25.00%)			32 (9.61%)	1 (3.13%)	19 (61.29%)	12 (38.71%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=258)	Female (N=97)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=337)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=186)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=350)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=224)	Female (N=116)	P-value*
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.38%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (50.00%)	4 (50.00%)			6 (1.85%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)			10 (3.00%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (40.00%)	6 (60.00%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.60%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.31%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)			4 (1.20%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (50.00%)	2 (50.00%)	
	Africa		11 (3.27%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (36.36%)	7 (63.64%)			3 (0.92%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)			26 (7.81%)	2 (7.69%)	18 (75.00%)	6 (25.00%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.08%)	2 (2.20%)	73 (82.02%)	16 (17.98%)			50 (15.38%)	0 (0.00%)	33 (66.00%)	17 (34.00%)			108 (32.43%)	1 (0.93%)	83 (77.57%)	24 (22.43%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.52%)	0 (0.00%)	19 (70.37%)	8 (29.63%)	0.3626	2	82 (24.48%)	1 (1.22%)	48 (59.26%)	33 (40.74%)	0.9192	9	40 (11.73%)	1 (2.50%)	22 (56.41%)	17 (43.59%)	0.5714
	Neutral		60 (16.71%)	2 (3.33%)	41 (70.69%)	17 (29.31%)			69 (20.60%)	3 (4.35%)	36 (54.55%)	30 (45.45%)			78 (22.87%)	3 (3.85%)	51 (68.00%)	24 (32.00%)	
	Positive		231 (64.35%)	1 (0.43%)	174 (75.65%)	56 (24.35%)			122 (36.42%)	2 (1.64%)	67 (55.83%)	53 (44.17%)			179 (52.49%)	2 (1.12%)	118 (66.67%)	59 (33.33%)	
	Other		41 (11.42%)	1 (2.44%)	24 (60.00%)	16 (40.00%)			62 (18.51%)	0 (0.00%)	34 (54.84%)	28 (45.16%)			44 (12.90%)	4 (9.09%)	26 (65.00%)	14 (35.00%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=168)	Female (N=71)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=229)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=123)	Female (N=99)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=235)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=152)	Female (N=77)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	1 (0.66%)	102 (67.55%)	49 (32.45%)	0.3355	0	220 (96.07%)	4 (1.82%)	119 (55.09%)	97 (44.91%)	0.1538	0	207 (88.09%)	6 (2.90%)	132 (65.67%)	69 (34.33%)	0.5677
	101+		88 (36.67%)	0 (0.00%)	66 (75.00%)	22 (25.00%)			9 (3.93%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (77.78%)	2 (22.22%)			28 (11.91%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (71.43%)	8 (28.57%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=193)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=136)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=226)	Unknown (N=0)	Male (N=121)	Female (N=105)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=86)	Unknown (N=0)	Male (N=64)	Female (N=22)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	68 (35.23%)	1 (1.47%)	44 (65.67%)	23 (34.33%)	0.2785	0	63 (27.88%)		35 (55.56%)	28 (44.44%)	0.0005	0	32 (37.21%)		23 (71.88%)	9 (28.13%)	0.9535
	Midwest		31 (16.06%)	1 (3.23%)	25 (83.33%)	5 (16.67%)			40 (17.70%)		32 (80.00%)	8 (20.00%)			18 (20.93%)		13 (72.22%)	5 (27.78%)	
	South		59 (30.57%)	0 (0.00%)	42 (71.19%)	17 (28.81%)			77 (34.07%)		36 (46.75%)	41 (53.25%)			18 (20.93%)		14 (77.78%)	4 (22.22%)	
	West		35 (18.13%)	1 (2.86%)	25 (73.53%)	9 (26.47%)			46 (20.35%)		18 (39.13%)	28 (60.87%)			18 (20.93%)		14 (77.78%)	4 (22.22%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=245)	Female (N=95)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=336)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=185)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=221)	Female (N=113)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	0	205 (59.59%)	3 (1.46%)	146 (72.28%)	56 (27.72%)	0.9135	0	244 (72.62%)	0 (0.00%)	134 (54.92%)	110 (45.08%)	0.4812	4	102 (30.00%)	0 (0.00%)	72 (70.59%)	30 (29.41%)	0.2576
	Non-US	139 (40.41%)	1 (0.72%)	99 (71.74%)	39 (28.26%)	92 (27.38%)		6 (6.52%)	51 (59.30%)	35 (40.70%)	238 (70.00%)	6 (2.52%)		149 (64.22%)	83 (35.78%)				
Continent	North America	0	207 (60.17%)	3 (1.45%)	148 (72.55%)	56 (27.45%)	0.9692	0	241 (71.73%)	0 (0.00%)	131 (54.36%)	110 (45.64%)	0.4589	4	104 (30.59%)	0 (0.00%)	74 (71.15%)	30 (28.85%)	0.3467
	Europe	97 (28.20%)	1 (1.03%)	70 (72.92%)	26 (27.08%)	74 (22.02%)		3 (4.05%)	40 (56.34%)	31 (43.66%)	159 (46.76%)	4 (2.52%)		98 (63.23%)	57 (36.77%)				
	Asia	11 (3.20%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (72.73%)	3 (27.27%)	13 (3.87%)		3 (23.08%)	8 (80.00%)	2 (20.00%)	27 (7.94%)	2 (7.41%)		13 (52.00%)	12 (48.00%)				
	Australia/NZ	16 (4.65%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (62.50%)	6 (37.50%)	5 (1.49%)		0 (0.00%)	4 (80.00%)	1 (20.00%)	29 (8.53%)	0 (0.00%)		20 (68.97%)	9 (31.03%)				
	Central/South America	4 (1.16%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (75.00%)	1 (25.00%)						4 (1.18%)	0 (0.00%)		2 (50.00%)	2 (50.00%)				
	Africa	8 (2.33%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (62.50%)	3 (37.50%)	3 (0.89%)		0 (0.00%)	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)	16 (4.71%)	0 (0.00%)		13 (81.25%)	3 (18.75%)				
	Other/Unknown	1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)						1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)		1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)				
Specialty	CVD	0	79 (22.97%)	0 (0.00%)	66 (83.54%)	13 (16.46%)	0.0121	0	33 (9.82%)	1 (3.03%)	25 (78.13%)	7 (21.88%)	0.0254	0	44 (12.79%)	0 (0.00%)	36 (81.82%)	8 (18.18%)	0.0386
	Neoplasms	37 (10.76%)	0 (0.00%)	29 (78.38%)	8 (21.62%)	13 (3.87%)		0 (0.00%)	9 (69.23%)	4 (30.77%)	17 (4.94%)	0 (0.00%)		13 (76.47%)	4 (23.53%)				
	Infectious Diseases	14 (4.07%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (50.00%)	7 (50.00%)	12 (3.57%)		0 (0.00%)	5 (41.67%)	7 (58.33%)	17 (4.94%)	0 (0.00%)		13 (76.47%)	4 (23.53%)				
	All other	214 (62.21%)	4 (1.87%)	143 (68.10%)	67 (31.90%)	278 (82.74%)		5 (1.80%)	146 (53.48%)	127 (46.52%)	266 (77.33%)	10 (3.76%)		159 (62.11%)	97 (37.89%)				
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	4	84 (24.71%)	1 (1.19%)	57 (68.67%)	26 (31.33%)	0.4767	5	85 (25.68%)	1 (1.18%)	49 (58.33%)	35 (41.67%)	0.7008	8	49 (14.58%)	1 (2.04%)	32 (66.67%)	16 (33.33%)	1.0000
	Yes	256 (75.29%)	1 (0.39%)	187 (73.33%)	68 (26.67%)	246 (74.32%)		5 (2.03%)	133 (55.19%)	108 (44.81%)	287 (85.42%)	5 (1.74%)		188 (66.67%)	94 (33.33%)				
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	4	39 (11.47%)	1 (2.56%)	29 (76.32%)	9 (23.68%)	0.5772	5	43 (12.99%)	0 (0.00%)	21 (48.84%)	22 (51.16%)	0.3188	8	40 (11.90%)	1 (2.50%)	28 (71.79%)	11 (28.21%)	0.5892
	Yes	301 (88.53%)	1 (0.33%)	215 (71.67%)	85 (28.33%)	288 (87.01%)		6 (2.08%)	161 (57.09%)	121 (42.91%)	296 (88.10%)	5 (1.69%)		192 (65.98%)	99 (34.02%)				
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	4	33 (9.71%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (60.61%)	13 (39.39%)	0.1512	5	26 (7.85%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (57.69%)	11 (42.31%)	1.0000	8	44 (13.10%)	1 (2.27%)	26 (60.47%)	17 (39.53%)	0.3897
	Yes	307 (90.29%)	2 (0.65%)	224 (73.44%)	81 (26.56%)	305 (92.15%)		6 (1.97%)	167 (55.85%)	132 (44.15%)	292 (86.90%)	5 (1.71%)		194 (67.60%)	93 (32.40%)				

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=4)	Male (N=245)	Female (N=95)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=336)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=185)	Female (N=145)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=344)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=221)	Female (N=113)	P-value*
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	Yes	4	340 (100.00%)	2 (0.59%)	244 (72.19%)	94 (27.81%)	.	5	331 (100.00%)	6 (1.81%)	182 (56.00%)	143 (44.00%)	.	8	336 (100.00%)	6 (1.79%)	220 (66.67%)	110 (33.33%)	.
Degree	MD-only	0	200 (58.14%)	2 (1.00%)	150 (75.76%)	48 (24.24%)	0.0003	0	138 (41.07%)	2 (1.45%)	93 (68.38%)	43 (31.62%)	<.0001	3	130 (38.12%)	4 (3.08%)	101 (80.16%)	25 (19.84%)	<.0001
	PhD-only	60 (17.44%)	2 (3.33%)	31 (53.45%)	27 (46.55%)	95 (28.27%)			0 (0.00%)	48 (50.53%)	47 (49.47%)	117 (34.31%)			3 (2.56%)	63 (55.26%)	51 (44.74%)		
	Both	65 (18.90%)	0 (0.00%)	54 (83.08%)	11 (16.92%)	43 (12.80%)			2 (4.65%)	28 (68.29%)	13 (31.71%)	46 (13.49%)			0 (0.00%)	35 (76.09%)	11 (23.91%)		
	Neither	19 (5.52%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (52.63%)	9 (47.37%)	60 (17.86%)			2 (3.33%)	16 (27.59%)	42 (72.41%)	48 (14.08%)			0 (0.00%)	22 (45.83%)	26 (54.17%)		
Degree-MD	No	0	79 (22.97%)	2 (2.53%)	41 (53.25%)	36 (46.75%)	<.0001	0	155 (46.13%)	2 (1.29%)	64 (41.83%)	89 (58.17%)	<.0001	3	165 (48.39%)	3 (1.82%)	85 (52.47%)	77 (47.53%)	<.0001
	Yes	265 (77.03%)	2 (0.75%)	204 (77.57%)	59 (22.43%)	181 (53.87%)			4 (2.21%)	121 (68.36%)	56 (31.64%)	176 (51.61%)			4 (2.27%)	136 (79.07%)	36 (20.93%)		
Degree-Dual	No	0	279 (81.10%)	4 (1.43%)	191 (69.45%)	84 (30.55%)	0.0277	0	293 (87.20%)	4 (1.37%)	157 (54.33%)	132 (45.67%)	0.0917	3	295 (86.51%)	7 (2.37%)	186 (64.58%)	102 (35.42%)	0.1257
	Yes	65 (18.90%)	0 (0.00%)	54 (83.08%)	11 (16.92%)	43 (12.80%)			2 (4.65%)	28 (68.29%)	13 (31.71%)	46 (13.49%)			0 (0.00%)	35 (76.09%)	11 (23.91%)		
Title	L-only	0	39 (11.34%)	1 (2.56%)	27 (71.05%)	11 (28.95%)	0.0006	0	27 (8.04%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (51.85%)	13 (48.15%)	0.0014	3	28 (8.21%)	1 (3.57%)	19 (70.37%)	8 (29.63%)	0.0078
	AR-only	89 (25.87%)	0 (0.00%)	58 (65.17%)	31 (34.83%)	82 (24.40%)			0 (0.00%)	50 (60.98%)	32 (39.02%)	114 (33.43%)			1 (0.88%)	74 (65.49%)	39 (34.51%)		
	Both	166 (48.26%)	0 (0.00%)	135 (81.33%)	31 (18.67%)	83 (24.70%)			0 (0.00%)	59 (71.08%)	24 (28.92%)	113 (33.14%)			1 (0.88%)	85 (75.89%)	27 (24.11%)		
	Neither	50 (14.53%)	3 (6.00%)	25 (53.19%)	22 (46.81%)	144 (42.86%)			6 (4.17%)	62 (44.93%)	76 (55.07%)	86 (25.22%)			4 (4.65%)	43 (52.44%)	39 (47.56%)		
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	139 (40.41%)	3 (2.16%)	83 (61.03%)	53 (38.97%)	0.0002	0	226 (67.26%)	6 (2.65%)	112 (50.91%)	108 (49.09%)	0.0077	3	200 (58.65%)	5 (2.50%)	117 (60.00%)	78 (40.00%)	0.0048
	Yes	205 (59.59%)	1 (0.49%)	162 (79.41%)	42 (20.59%)	110 (32.74%)			0 (0.00%)	73 (66.36%)	37 (33.64%)	141 (41.35%)			2 (1.42%)	104 (74.82%)	35 (25.18%)		
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	89 (25.87%)	4 (4.49%)	52 (61.18%)	33 (38.82%)	0.0098	0	171 (50.89%)	6 (3.51%)	76 (46.06%)	89 (53.94%)	0.0003	3	114 (33.43%)	5 (4.39%)	62 (56.88%)	47 (43.12%)	0.0125
	Yes	255 (74.13%)	0 (0.00%)	193 (75.69%)	62 (24.31%)	165 (49.11%)			0 (0.00%)	109 (66.06%)	56 (33.94%)	227 (66.57%)			2 (0.88%)	159 (70.67%)	66 (29.33%)		

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with second authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Last Author

Tables 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 below showed the descriptive table for publication-level and author-level last author characteristics by the gender of last author in column percentages and row percentages, respectively. More specifically, Tables 2.3.3 and 2.3.4 showed the descriptive tables within each journal.

Table 2.3.1: Percentage of Female Last Author Characteristics (All journals; column percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1075)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=862)	Female (N=197)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	417 (38.79%)	7 (43.75%)	340 (39.44%)	70 (35.53%)	0.2925
	2009-2014		358 (33.30%)	5 (31.25%)	279 (32.37%)	74 (37.56%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.91%)	4 (25.00%)	243 (28.19%)	53 (26.90%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	477 (44.37%)	8 (50.00%)	375 (43.50%)	94 (47.72%)	0.1874
	11-20		396 (36.84%)	4 (25.00%)	317 (36.77%)	75 (38.07%)	
	21+		202 (18.79%)	4 (25.00%)	170 (19.72%)	28 (14.21%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	562 (52.28%)	5 (31.25%)	454 (52.67%)	103 (52.28%)	0.9179
	Non-US		513 (47.72%)	11 (68.75%)	408 (47.33%)	94 (47.72%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	497 (46.23%)	7 (43.75%)	393 (45.59%)	97 (49.24%)	0.4076
	Yes		578 (53.77%)	9 (56.25%)	469 (54.41%)	100 (50.76%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	659 (61.30%)	13 (81.25%)	534 (61.95%)	112 (56.85%)	0.1600
	Yes		416 (38.70%)	3 (18.75%)	328 (38.05%)	85 (43.15%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.88±1.23	0.78±0.67	0.92±1.27	0.72±1.07	0.0765
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	56	411 (40.33%)	5 (38.46%)	320 (39.31%)	86 (44.79%)	0.2338
	Non-US		608 (59.67%)	8 (61.54%)	494 (60.69%)	106 (55.21%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	56	410 (40.24%)	5 (38.46%)	321 (39.43%)	84 (43.75%)	.
	Europe		216 (21.20%)	3 (23.08%)	175 (21.50%)	38 (19.79%)	
	Asia		66 (6.48%)	3 (23.08%)	50 (6.14%)	13 (6.77%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.36%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (1.84%)	9 (4.69%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (0.86%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		40 (3.93%)	1 (7.69%)	28 (3.44%)	11 (5.73%)	
	Other/Unknown		256 (25.12%)	1 (7.69%)	218 (26.78%)	37 (19.27%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1075)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=862)	Female (N=197)	P-value*
Directionality	Negative	12	152 (14.30%)	2 (12.50%)	118 (13.83%)	32 (16.49%)	0.7100
	Neutral		212 (19.94%)	7 (43.75%)	171 (20.05%)	34 (17.53%)	
	Positive		541 (50.89%)	5 (31.25%)	439 (51.47%)	97 (50.00%)	
	Other		158 (14.86%)	2 (12.50%)	125 (14.65%)	31 (15.98%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=718)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=570)	Female (N=135)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	593 (82.59%)	11 (84.62%)	466 (81.75%)	116 (85.93%)	0.4501
	101+		125 (17.41%)	2 (15.38%)	104 (18.25%)	19 (14.07%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=562)	Unknown (N=5)	Male (N=454)	Female (N=103)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	196 (34.88%)	0 (0.00%)	166 (36.56%)	30 (29.13%)	0.3043
	Midwest		81 (14.41%)	2 (40.00%)	64 (14.10%)	15 (14.56%)	
	South		168 (29.89%)	1 (20.00%)	129 (28.41%)	38 (36.89%)	
	West		117 (20.82%)	2 (40.00%)	95 (20.93%)	20 (19.42%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=994)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=788)	Female (N=190)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	4	573 (57.88%)	4 (30.77%)	454 (57.69%)	115 (60.53%)	0.5155
	Non-US		417 (42.12%)	9 (69.23%)	333 (42.31%)	75 (39.47%)	
Continent	North America	4	566 (57.17%)	4 (30.77%)	451 (57.31%)	111 (58.42%)	0.4946
	Europe		335 (33.84%)	7 (53.85%)	272 (34.56%)	56 (29.47%)	
	Asia		37 (3.74%)	1 (7.69%)	26 (3.30%)	10 (5.26%)	
	Australia/NZ		34 (3.43%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (3.18%)	9 (4.74%)	
	Central/South America		3 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.25%)	1 (0.53%)	
	Africa		12 (1.21%)	1 (7.69%)	8 (1.02%)	3 (1.58%)	
	Other/Unknown		3 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.38%)	0 (0.00%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=994)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=788)	Female (N=190)	P-value*
Specialty	CVD	0	162 (16.30%)	1 (6.25%)	144 (18.27%)	17 (8.95%)	0.0044
	Neoplasms		75 (7.55%)	0 (0.00%)	65 (8.25%)	10 (5.26%)	
	Infectious Diseases		75 (7.55%)	0 (0.00%)	60 (7.61%)	15 (7.89%)	
	All other		682 (68.61%)	15 (93.75%)	519 (65.86%)	148 (77.89%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	11	186 (18.92%)	3 (25.00%)	147 (18.77%)	36 (19.15%)	0.9175
	Yes		797 (81.08%)	9 (75.00%)	636 (81.23%)	152 (80.85%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	11	105 (10.68%)	1 (8.33%)	79 (10.09%)	25 (13.30%)	0.2414
	Yes		878 (89.32%)	11 (91.67%)	704 (89.91%)	163 (86.70%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	11	100 (10.17%)	2 (16.67%)	67 (8.56%)	31 (16.49%)	0.0011
	Yes		883 (89.83%)	10 (83.33%)	716 (91.44%)	157 (83.51%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	11	1 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.13%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000
	Yes		982 (99.90%)	12 (100.00%)	782 (99.87%)	188 (100.00%)	
Degree	MD-only	2	563 (56.75%)	9 (64.29%)	467 (59.26%)	87 (45.79%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		188 (18.95%)	3 (21.43%)	119 (15.10%)	66 (34.74%)	
	Both		205 (20.67%)	0 (0.00%)	182 (23.10%)	23 (12.11%)	
	Neither		36 (3.63%)	2 (14.29%)	20 (2.54%)	14 (7.37%)	
Degree-MD	No	2	224 (22.58%)	5 (35.71%)	139 (17.64%)	80 (42.11%)	<.0001
	Yes		768 (77.42%)	9 (64.29%)	649 (82.36%)	110 (57.89%)	
Degree-Dual	No	2	787 (79.33%)	14 (100.00%)	606 (76.90%)	167 (87.89%)	0.0008
	Yes		205 (20.67%)	0 (0.00%)	182 (23.10%)	23 (12.11%)	
Title	L-only	1	130 (13.09%)	1 (6.67%)	106 (13.45%)	23 (12.11%)	0.0288
	AR-only		225 (22.66%)	1 (6.67%)	176 (22.34%)	48 (25.26%)	
	Both		507 (51.06%)	2 (13.33%)	420 (53.30%)	85 (44.74%)	
	Neither		131 (13.19%)	11 (73.33%)	86 (10.91%)	34 (17.89%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=994)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=788)	Female (N=190)	P-value*
Title-Leadership Position	No	1	356 (35.85%)	12 (80.00%)	262 (33.25%)	82 (43.16%)	0.0102
	Yes		637 (64.15%)	3 (20.00%)	526 (66.75%)	108 (56.84%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	1	261 (26.28%)	12 (80.00%)	192 (24.37%)	57 (30.00%)	0.1095
	Yes		732 (73.72%)	3 (20.00%)	596 (75.63%)	133 (70.00%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with last authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.3.2: Percentage of Female Last Author Characteristics (All journals; row percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1075)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=862)	Female (N=197)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	417 (38.79%)	7 (1.68%)	340 (82.93%)	70 (17.07%)	0.2925
	2009-2014		358 (33.30%)	5 (1.40%)	279 (79.04%)	74 (20.96%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.91%)	4 (1.33%)	243 (82.09%)	53 (17.91%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	477 (44.37%)	8 (1.68%)	375 (79.96%)	94 (20.04%)	0.1874
	11-20		396 (36.84%)	4 (1.01%)	317 (80.87%)	75 (19.13%)	
	21+		202 (18.79%)	4 (1.98%)	170 (85.86%)	28 (14.14%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	562 (52.28%)	5 (0.89%)	454 (81.51%)	103 (18.49%)	0.9179
	Non-US		513 (47.72%)	11 (2.14%)	408 (81.27%)	94 (18.73%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	497 (46.23%)	7 (1.41%)	393 (80.20%)	97 (19.80%)	0.4076
	Yes		578 (53.77%)	9 (1.56%)	469 (82.43%)	100 (17.57%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	659 (61.30%)	13 (1.97%)	534 (82.66%)	112 (17.34%)	0.1600
	Yes		416 (38.70%)	3 (0.72%)	328 (79.42%)	85 (20.58%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.88±1.23	0.78±0.67	0.92±1.27	0.72±1.07	0.0765
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	56	411 (40.33%)	5 (1.22%)	320 (78.82%)	86 (21.18%)	0.2338
	Non-US		608 (59.67%)	8 (1.32%)	494 (82.33%)	106 (17.67%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	56	410 (40.24%)	5 (1.22%)	321 (79.26%)	84 (20.74%)	.
	Europe		216 (21.20%)	3 (1.39%)	175 (82.16%)	38 (17.84%)	
	Asia		66 (6.48%)	3 (4.55%)	50 (79.37%)	13 (20.63%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.36%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (62.50%)	9 (37.50%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		40 (3.93%)	1 (2.50%)	28 (71.79%)	11 (28.21%)	
	Other/Unknown		256 (25.12%)	1 (0.39%)	218 (85.49%)	37 (14.51%)	
Directionality	Negative	12	152 (14.30%)	2 (1.32%)	118 (78.67%)	32 (21.33%)	0.7100
	Neutral		212 (19.94%)	7 (3.30%)	171 (83.41%)	34 (16.59%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1075)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=862)	Female (N=197)	P-value*
	Positive		541 (50.89%)	5 (0.92%)	439 (81.90%)	97 (18.10%)	
	Other		158 (14.86%)	2 (1.27%)	125 (80.13%)	31 (19.87%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=718)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=570)	Female (N=135)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	593 (82.59%)	11 (1.85%)	466 (80.07%)	116 (19.93%)	0.4501
	101+		125 (17.41%)	2 (1.60%)	104 (84.55%)	19 (15.45%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=562)	Unknown (N=5)	Male (N=454)	Female (N=103)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Midwest	0	81 (14.41%)	2 (2.47%)	64 (81.01%)	15 (18.99%)	0.3043
	Northeast		196 (34.88%)	0 (0.00%)	166 (84.69%)	30 (15.31%)	
	South		168 (29.89%)	1 (0.60%)	129 (77.25%)	38 (22.75%)	
	West		117 (20.82%)	2 (1.71%)	95 (82.61%)	20 (17.39%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=994)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=788)	Female (N=190)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	4	573 (57.88%)	4 (0.70%)	454 (79.79%)	115 (20.21%)	0.5155
	Non-US		417 (42.12%)	9 (2.16%)	333 (81.62%)	75 (18.38%)	
Continent	North America	4	566 (57.17%)	4 (0.71%)	451 (80.25%)	111 (19.75%)	0.4946
	Europe		335 (33.84%)	7 (2.09%)	272 (82.93%)	56 (17.07%)	
	Asia		37 (3.74%)	1 (2.70%)	26 (72.22%)	10 (27.78%)	
	Australia/NZ		34 (3.43%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (73.53%)	9 (26.47%)	
	Central/South America		3 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)	
	Africa		12 (1.21%)	1 (8.33%)	8 (72.73%)	3 (27.27%)	
	Other/Unknown		3 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	162 (16.30%)	1 (0.62%)	144 (89.44%)	17 (10.56%)	0.0044
	Neoplasms		75 (7.55%)	0 (0.00%)	65 (86.67%)	10 (13.33%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=994)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=788)	Female (N=190)	P-value*
	Infectious Diseases		75 (7.55%)	0 (0.00%)	60 (80.00%)	15 (20.00%)	
	All other		682 (68.61%)	15 (2.20%)	519 (77.81%)	148 (22.19%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	11	186 (18.92%)	3 (1.61%)	147 (80.33%)	36 (19.67%)	0.9175
	Yes		797 (81.08%)	9 (1.13%)	636 (80.71%)	152 (19.29%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	11	105 (10.68%)	1 (0.95%)	79 (75.96%)	25 (24.04%)	0.2414
	Yes		878 (89.32%)	11 (1.25%)	704 (81.20%)	163 (18.80%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	11	100 (10.17%)	2 (2.00%)	67 (68.37%)	31 (31.63%)	0.0011
	Yes		883 (89.83%)	10 (1.13%)	716 (82.02%)	157 (17.98%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	11	1 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000
	Yes		982 (99.90%)	12 (1.22%)	782 (80.62%)	188 (19.38%)	
Degree	MD-only	2	563 (56.75%)	9 (1.60%)	467 (84.30%)	87 (15.70%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		188 (18.95%)	3 (1.60%)	119 (64.32%)	66 (35.68%)	
	Both		205 (20.67%)	0 (0.00%)	182 (88.78%)	23 (11.22%)	
	Neither		36 (3.63%)	2 (5.56%)	20 (58.82%)	14 (41.18%)	
Degree-MD	No	2	224 (22.58%)	5 (2.23%)	139 (63.47%)	80 (36.53%)	<.0001
	Yes		768 (77.42%)	9 (1.17%)	649 (85.51%)	110 (14.49%)	
Degree-Dual	No	2	787 (79.33%)	14 (1.78%)	606 (78.40%)	167 (21.60%)	0.0008
	Yes		205 (20.67%)	0 (0.00%)	182 (88.78%)	23 (11.22%)	
Title	L-only	1	130 (13.09%)	1 (0.77%)	106 (82.17%)	23 (17.83%)	0.0288
	AR-only		225 (22.66%)	1 (0.44%)	176 (78.57%)	48 (21.43%)	
	Both		507 (51.06%)	2 (0.39%)	420 (83.17%)	85 (16.83%)	
	Neither		131 (13.19%)	11 (8.40%)	86 (71.67%)	34 (28.33%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	1	356 (35.85%)	12 (3.37%)	262 (76.16%)	82 (23.84%)	0.0102
	Yes		637 (64.15%)	3 (0.47%)	526 (82.97%)	108 (17.03%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=994)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=788)	Female (N=190)	P-value*
Title-Academic Rank	No	1	261 (26.28%)	12 (4.60%)	192 (77.11%)	57 (22.89%)	0.1095
	Yes		732 (73.72%)	3 (0.41%)	596 (81.76%)	133 (18.24%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with last authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.3.3: Percentage of Female Last Author Characteristics (column percentages)

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=304)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=356)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=74)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=69)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	140 (38.89%)	1 (50.00%)	121 (39.80%)	18 (33.33%)	0.5592	0	138 (38.76%)	0 (0.00%)	107 (38.35%)	31 (41.89%)	0.5733	0	139 (38.72%)	6 (54.55%)	112 (40.14%)	21 (30.43%)	0.1760
	2009-2014		120 (33.33%)	1 (50.00%)	101 (33.22%)	18 (33.33%)			118 (33.15%)	0 (0.00%)	91 (32.62%)	27 (36.49%)			120 (33.43%)	4 (36.36%)	87 (31.18%)	29 (42.03%)	
	2015-2019		100 (27.78%)	0 (0.00%)	82 (26.97%)	18 (33.33%)			100 (28.09%)	3 (100.00%)	81 (29.03%)	16 (21.62%)			100 (27.86%)	1 (9.09%)	80 (28.67%)	19 (27.54%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	101 (28.06%)	0 (0.00%)	89 (29.28%)	12 (22.22%)	0.2375	0	210 (58.99%)	1 (33.33%)	162 (58.06%)	47 (63.51%)	0.6009	0	166 (46.24%)	7 (63.64%)	124 (44.44%)	35 (50.72%)	0.4404
	11-20		163 (45.28%)	1 (50.00%)	132 (43.42%)	30 (55.56%)			105 (29.49%)	0 (0.00%)	84 (30.11%)	21 (28.38%)			128 (35.65%)	3 (27.27%)	101 (36.20%)	24 (34.78%)	
	21+		96 (26.67%)	1 (50.00%)	83 (27.30%)	12 (22.22%)			41 (11.52%)	2 (66.67%)	33 (11.83%)	6 (8.11%)			65 (18.11%)	1 (9.09%)	54 (19.35%)	10 (14.49%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	205 (56.94%)	2 (100.00%)	174 (57.24%)	29 (53.70%)	0.5638	0	250 (70.22%)	1 (33.33%)	194 (69.53%)	55 (74.32%)	0.3046	0	107 (29.81%)	2 (18.18%)	86 (30.82%)	19 (27.54%)	0.6142
	Non-US		155 (43.06%)	0 (0.00%)	130 (42.76%)	25 (46.30%)			106 (29.78%)	2 (66.67%)	85 (30.47%)	19 (25.68%)			252 (70.19%)	9 (81.82%)	193 (69.18%)	50 (72.46%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	63 (17.50%)	0 (0.00%)	56 (18.42%)	7 (12.96%)	0.2608	0	241 (67.70%)	1 (33.33%)	187 (67.03%)	53 (71.62%)	0.3611	0	193 (53.76%)	6 (54.55%)	150 (53.76%)	37 (53.62%)	0.9239
	Yes		297 (82.50%)	2 (100.00%)	248 (81.58%)	47 (87.04%)			115 (32.30%)	2 (66.67%)	92 (32.97%)	21 (28.38%)			166 (46.24%)	5 (45.45%)	129 (46.24%)	32 (46.38%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	232 (64.44%)	0 (0.00%)	201 (66.12%)	31 (57.41%)	0.2455	0	195 (54.78%)	3 (100.00%)	156 (55.91%)	36 (48.65%)	0.2102	0	232 (64.62%)	10 (90.91%)	177 (63.44%)	45 (65.22%)	0.8710
	Yes		128 (35.56%)	2 (100.00%)	103 (33.88%)	23 (42.59%)			161 (45.22%)	0 (0.00%)	123 (44.09%)	38 (51.35%)			127 (35.38%)	1 (9.09%)	102 (36.56%)	24 (34.78%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.10±0.57	1.21±1.36	0.75±0.89	0.0026	0	0.64±0.73	0.19±0.08	0.65±0.68	0.64±0.92	0.9949	1	0.85±1.47	0.88±0.71	0.86±1.53	0.79±1.33	0.9563
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (100.00%)	120 (42.55%)	27 (50.00%)	0.3839	15	217 (63.64%)	2 (66.67%)	165 (61.80%)	50 (70.42%)	0.1762	18	46 (13.49%)	2 (22.22%)	35 (13.21%)	9 (13.43%)	0.9740

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=304)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=356)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=74)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=69)	P-value*
	Non-US		189 (56.08%)	0 (0.00%)	162 (57.45%)	27 (50.00%)			124 (36.36%)	1 (33.33%)	102 (38.20%)	21 (29.58%)			295 (86.51%)	7 (77.78%)	230 (86.79%)	58 (86.57%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (100.00%)	121 (42.91%)	26 (48.15%)		15	216 (63.34%)	2 (66.67%)	165 (61.80%)	49 (69.01%)		18	46 (13.49%)	2 (22.22%)	35 (13.21%)	9 (13.43%)	
	Europe		58 (17.21%)	0 (0.00%)	49 (17.38%)	9 (16.67%)			46 (13.49%)	1 (33.33%)	40 (14.98%)	5 (7.04%)			112 (32.84%)	2 (22.22%)	86 (32.45%)	24 (35.82%)	
	Asia		19 (5.64%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (5.67%)	3 (5.56%)			14 (4.11%)	0 (0.00%)	11 (4.12%)	3 (4.23%)			33 (9.68%)	3 (33.33%)	23 (8.68%)	7 (10.45%)	
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.37%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (2.13%)	2 (3.70%)			6 (1.76%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.12%)	3 (4.23%)			10 (2.93%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (2.26%)	4 (5.97%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.59%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.71%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.37%)	0 (0.00%)			4 (1.17%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (1.51%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		11 (3.26%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (2.13%)	5 (9.26%)			3 (0.88%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.75%)	1 (1.41%)			26 (7.62%)	1 (11.11%)	20 (7.55%)	5 (7.46%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.00%)	0 (0.00%)	82 (29.08%)	9 (16.67%)			55 (16.13%)	0 (0.00%)	45 (16.85%)	10 (14.08%)			110 (32.26%)	1 (11.11%)	91 (34.34%)	18 (26.87%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.50%)	0 (0.00%)	22 (7.24%)	5 (9.26%)	0.7596	2	84 (23.73%)	0 (0.00%)	65 (23.38%)	19 (26.03%)	0.6720	10	41 (11.75%)	2 (18.18%)	31 (11.44%)	8 (11.94%)	0.6331
	Neutral		60 (16.67%)	1 (50.00%)	52 (17.11%)	7 (12.96%)			72 (20.34%)	2 (66.67%)	58 (20.86%)	12 (16.44%)			80 (22.92%)	4 (36.36%)	61 (22.51%)	15 (22.39%)	
	Positive		231 (64.17%)	1 (50.00%)	196 (64.47%)	34 (62.96%)			128 (36.16%)	1 (33.33%)	102 (36.69%)	25 (34.25%)			182 (52.15%)	3 (27.27%)	141 (52.03%)	38 (56.72%)	
	Other		42 (11.67%)	0 (0.00%)	34 (11.18%)	8 (14.81%)			70 (19.77%)	0 (0.00%)	53 (19.06%)	17 (23.29%)			46 (13.18%)	2 (18.18%)	38 (14.02%)	6 (8.96%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=201)	Female (N=38)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=238)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=188)	Female (N=47)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=9)	Male (N=181)	Female (N=50)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	0 (0.00%)	127 (63.18%)	25 (65.79%)	0.8773	0	229 (96.22%)	3 (100.00%)	180 (95.74%)	46 (97.87%)	0.3942	0	212 (88.33%)	8 (88.89%)	159 (87.85%)	45 (90.00%)	0.9767
	101+		88 (36.67%)	1 (100.00%)	74 (36.82%)	13 (34.21%)			9 (3.78%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (4.26%)	1 (2.13%)			28 (11.67%)	1 (11.11%)	22 (12.15%)	5 (10.00%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=205)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=174)	Female (N=29)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=250)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=194)	Female (N=55)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=107)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=86)	Female (N=19)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	84 (40.98%)	0 (0.00%)	71 (40.80%)	13 (44.83%)	0.8362	0	81 (32.40%)	0 (0.00%)	70 (36.08%)	11 (20.00%)	0.0811	0	31 (28.97%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (29.07%)	6 (31.58%)	0.7166
	Midwest		28 (13.66%)	1 (50.00%)	22 (12.64%)	5 (17.24%)			40 (16.00%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (15.98%)	9 (16.36%)			13 (12.15%)	1 (50.00%)	11 (12.79%)	1 (5.26%)	
	South		54 (26.34%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (27.59%)	6 (20.69%)			84 (33.60%)	0 (0.00%)	58 (29.90%)	26 (47.27%)			30 (28.04%)	1 (50.00%)	23 (26.74%)	6 (31.58%)	
	West		39 (19.02%)	1 (50.00%)	33 (18.97%)	5 (17.24%)			45 (18.00%)	1 (100.00%)	35 (18.04%)	9 (16.36%)			33 (30.84%)	0 (0.00%)	27 (31.40%)	6 (31.58%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=338)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=282)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=267)	Female (N=71)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=263)	Female (N=67)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	1	222 (65.88%)	2 (100.00%)	185 (65.84%)	35 (64.81%)	1.0000	0	257 (75.37%)	1 (33.33%)	197 (73.78%)	59 (83.10%)	0.1036	3	113 (33.43%)	1 (12.50%)	90 (34.22%)	22 (32.84%)	0.8308
	Non-US		115 (34.12%)	0 (0.00%)	96 (34.16%)	19 (35.19%)			84 (24.63%)	2 (66.67%)	70 (26.22%)	12 (16.90%)			225 (66.57%)	7 (87.50%)	173 (65.78%)	45 (67.16%)	
Continent	North America	1	217 (64.39%)	2 (100.00%)	183 (65.12%)	32 (59.26%)	0.0556	0	256 (75.07%)	1 (33.33%)	197 (73.78%)	58 (81.69%)	0.6604	3	112 (33.14%)	1 (12.50%)	89 (33.84%)	22 (32.84%)	0.6399
	Europe		101 (29.97%)	0 (0.00%)	85 (30.25%)	16 (29.63%)			66 (19.35%)	2 (66.67%)	55 (20.60%)	9 (12.68%)			175 (51.78%)	5 (62.50%)	138 (52.47%)	32 (47.76%)	
	Asia		5 (1.48%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (1.42%)	1 (1.85%)			11 (3.23%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (3.37%)	2 (2.82%)			21 (6.21%)	1 (12.50%)	13 (4.94%)	7 (10.45%)	
	Australia/NZ		10 (2.97%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (2.85%)	2 (3.70%)			5 (1.47%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (1.12%)	2 (2.82%)			19 (5.62%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (5.32%)	5 (7.46%)	
	Central/South America		1 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (1.85%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.37%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.38%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		3 (0.89%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.36%)	2 (3.70%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.37%)	0 (0.00%)			8 (2.37%)	1 (12.50%)	6 (2.28%)	1 (1.49%)	
	Other/Unknown								1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.37%)	0 (0.00%)			2 (0.59%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.76%)	0 (0.00%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=338)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=282)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=267)	Female (N=71)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=263)	Female (N=67)	P-value*
Specialty	CVD	0	74 (21.89%)	0 (0.00%)	67 (23.76%)	7 (12.96%)	0.1690	0	55 (16.13%)	1 (33.33%)	46 (17.23%)	8 (11.27%)	0.6382	0	43 (12.61%)	0 (0.00%)	40 (15.21%)	3 (4.48%)	0.0100
	Neoplasms		37 (10.95%)	0 (0.00%)	33 (11.70%)	4 (7.41%)			23 (6.74%)	0 (0.00%)	18 (6.74%)	5 (7.04%)			19 (5.57%)	0 (0.00%)	18 (6.84%)	1 (1.49%)	
	Infectious Diseases		21 (6.21%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (5.67%)	5 (9.26%)			19 (5.57%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (5.24%)	5 (7.04%)			36 (10.56%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (11.79%)	5 (7.46%)	
	All other		206 (60.95%)	2 (100.00%)	166 (58.87%)	38 (70.37%)			244 (71.55%)	2 (66.67%)	189 (70.79%)	53 (74.65%)			243 (71.26%)	11 (100.00%)	174 (66.16%)	58 (86.57%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	2	80 (23.81%)	1 (50.00%)	67 (23.93%)	12 (22.22%)	0.8628	4	70 (20.77%)	1 (33.33%)	57 (21.59%)	12 (17.14%)	0.5144	5	43 (12.80%)	1 (14.29%)	30 (11.41%)	12 (18.18%)	0.1469
	Yes		256 (76.19%)	1 (50.00%)	213 (76.07%)	42 (77.78%)			267 (79.23%)	2 (66.67%)	207 (78.41%)	58 (82.86%)			293 (87.20%)	6 (85.71%)	233 (88.59%)	54 (81.82%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	2	34 (10.12%)	1 (50.00%)	28 (10.00%)	5 (9.26%)	1.0000	4	32 (9.50%)	0 (0.00%)	26 (9.85%)	6 (8.57%)	0.8264	5	39 (11.61%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (9.51%)	14 (21.21%)	0.0113
	Yes		302 (89.88%)	1 (50.00%)	252 (90.00%)	49 (90.74%)			305 (90.50%)	3 (100.00%)	238 (90.15%)	64 (91.43%)			297 (88.39%)	7 (100.00%)	238 (90.49%)	52 (78.79%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	2	30 (8.93%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (7.14%)	10 (18.52%)	0.0120	4	23 (6.82%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (5.30%)	9 (12.86%)	0.0328	5	47 (13.99%)	2 (28.57%)	33 (12.55%)	12 (18.18%)	0.3164
	Yes		306 (91.07%)	2 (100.00%)	260 (92.86%)	44 (81.48%)			314 (93.18%)	3 (100.00%)	250 (94.70%)	61 (87.14%)			289 (86.01%)	5 (71.43%)	230 (87.45%)	54 (81.82%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	2	1 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.36%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000	4						5					
	Yes		335 (99.70%)	2 (100.00%)	279 (99.64%)	54 (100.00%)			337 (100.00%)	3 (100.00%)	264 (100.00%)	70 (100.00%)			336 (100.00%)	7 (100.00%)	263 (100.00%)	66 (100.00%)	
Degree	MD-only	0	208 (61.54%)	1 (50.00%)	182 (64.54%)	25 (46.30%)	<.0001	0	196 (57.48%)	1 (33.33%)	157 (58.80%)	38 (53.52%)	0.0122	2	172 (50.74%)	7 (77.78%)	140 (53.23%)	25 (37.31%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		41 (12.13%)	0 (0.00%)	26 (9.22%)	15 (27.78%)			60 (17.60%)	1 (33.33%)	38 (14.23%)	21 (29.58%)			90 (26.55%)	2 (22.22%)	57 (21.67%)	31 (46.27%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=338)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=282)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=267)	Female (N=71)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=263)	Female (N=67)	P-value*
	Both		77 (22.78%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (24.47%)	8 (14.81%)			72 (21.11%)	0 (0.00%)	63 (23.60%)	9 (12.68%)			66 (19.47%)	0 (0.00%)	60 (22.81%)	6 (8.96%)	
	Neither		12 (3.55%)	1 (50.00%)	5 (1.77%)	6 (11.11%)			13 (3.81%)	1 (33.33%)	9 (3.37%)	3 (4.23%)			11 (3.24%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (2.28%)	5 (7.46%)	
Degree-MD	No	0	53 (15.68%)	1 (50.00%)	31 (10.99%)	21 (38.89%)	<.0001	0	73 (21.41%)	2 (66.67%)	47 (17.60%)	24 (33.80%)	0.0029	2	101 (29.79%)	2 (22.22%)	63 (23.95%)	36 (53.73%)	<.0001
	Yes		285 (84.32%)	1 (50.00%)	251 (89.01%)	33 (61.11%)			268 (78.59%)	1 (33.33%)	220 (82.40%)	47 (66.20%)			238 (70.21%)	7 (77.78%)	200 (76.05%)	31 (46.27%)	
Degree-Dual	No	0	261 (77.22%)	2 (100.00%)	213 (75.53%)	46 (85.19%)	0.1221	0	269 (78.89%)	3 (100.00%)	204 (76.40%)	62 (87.32%)	0.0458	2	273 (80.53%)	9 (100.00%)	203 (77.19%)	61 (91.04%)	0.0114
	Yes		77 (22.78%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (24.47%)	8 (14.81%)			72 (21.11%)	0 (0.00%)	63 (23.60%)	9 (12.68%)			66 (19.47%)	0 (0.00%)	60 (22.81%)	6 (8.96%)	
Title	L-only	0	56 (16.57%)	0 (0.00%)	47 (16.67%)	9 (16.67%)	0.6473	0	41 (12.02%)	0 (0.00%)	32 (11.99%)	9 (12.68%)	0.9188	1	34 (10.00%)	1 (10.00%)	28 (10.65%)	5 (7.46%)	0.0006
	AR-only		69 (20.41%)	0 (0.00%)	58 (20.57%)	11 (20.37%)			86 (25.22%)	0 (0.00%)	66 (24.72%)	20 (28.17%)			74 (21.76%)	1 (10.00%)	56 (21.29%)	17 (25.37%)	
	Both		177 (52.37%)	0 (0.00%)	151 (53.55%)	26 (48.15%)			155 (45.45%)	1 (33.33%)	124 (46.44%)	30 (42.25%)			196 (57.65%)	1 (10.00%)	164 (62.36%)	31 (46.27%)	
	Neither		36 (10.65%)	2 (100.00%)	26 (9.22%)	8 (14.81%)			59 (17.30%)	2 (66.67%)	45 (16.85%)	12 (16.90%)			36 (10.59%)	7 (70.00%)	15 (5.70%)	14 (20.90%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	105 (31.07%)	2 (100.00%)	84 (29.79%)	19 (35.19%)	0.4306	0	145 (42.52%)	2 (66.67%)	111 (41.57%)	32 (45.07%)	0.5960	1	110 (32.35%)	8 (80.00%)	71 (27.00%)	31 (46.27%)	0.0023
	Yes		233 (68.93%)	0 (0.00%)	198 (70.21%)	35 (64.81%)			196 (57.48%)	1 (33.33%)	156 (58.43%)	39 (54.93%)			230 (67.65%)	2 (20.00%)	192 (73.00%)	36 (53.73%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	92 (27.22%)	2 (100.00%)	73 (25.89%)	17 (31.48%)	0.3950	0	100 (29.33%)	2 (66.67%)	77 (28.84%)	21 (29.58%)	0.9030	1	70 (20.59%)	8 (80.00%)	43 (16.35%)	19 (28.36%)	0.0247
	Yes		246 (72.78%)	0 (0.00%)	209 (74.11%)	37 (68.52%)			241 (70.67%)	1 (33.33%)	190 (71.16%)	50 (70.42%)			270 (79.41%)	2 (20.00%)	220 (83.65%)	48 (71.64%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with last authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.3.4: Percentage of Female Last Author Characteristics (row percentages)

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=304)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=356)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=74)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=69)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	140 (38.89%)	1 (0.71%)	121 (87.05%)	18 (12.95%)	0.5592	0	138 (38.76%)	0 (0.00%)	107 (77.54%)	31 (22.46%)	0.5733	0	139 (38.72%)	6 (4.32%)	112 (84.21%)	21 (15.79%)	0.1760
	2009-2014		120 (33.33%)	1 (0.83%)	101 (84.87%)	18 (15.13%)			118 (33.15%)	0 (0.00%)	91 (77.12%)	27 (22.88%)			120 (33.43%)	4 (3.33%)	87 (75.00%)	29 (25.00%)	
	2015-2019		100 (27.78%)	0 (0.00%)	82 (82.00%)	18 (18.00%)			100 (28.09%)	3 (3.00%)	81 (83.51%)	16 (16.49%)			100 (27.86%)	1 (1.00%)	80 (80.81%)	19 (19.19%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	101 (28.06%)	0 (0.00%)	89 (88.12%)	12 (11.88%)	0.2375	0	210 (58.99%)	1 (0.48%)	162 (77.51%)	47 (22.49%)	0.6009	0	166 (46.24%)	7 (4.22%)	124 (77.99%)	35 (22.01%)	0.4404
	11-20		163 (45.28%)	1 (0.61%)	132 (81.48%)	30 (18.52%)			105 (29.49%)	0 (0.00%)	84 (80.00%)	21 (20.00%)			128 (35.65%)	3 (2.34%)	101 (80.80%)	24 (19.20%)	
	21+		96 (26.67%)	1 (1.04%)	83 (87.37%)	12 (12.63%)			41 (11.52%)	2 (4.88%)	33 (84.62%)	6 (15.38%)			65 (18.11%)	1 (1.54%)	54 (84.38%)	10 (15.63%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	205 (56.94%)	2 (0.98%)	174 (85.71%)	29 (14.29%)	0.5638	0	250 (70.22%)	1 (0.40%)	194 (77.91%)	55 (22.09%)	0.3046	0	107 (29.81%)	2 (1.87%)	86 (81.90%)	19 (18.10%)	0.6142
	Non-US		155 (43.06%)	0 (0.00%)	130 (83.87%)	25 (16.13%)			106 (29.78%)	2 (1.89%)	85 (81.73%)	19 (18.27%)			252 (70.19%)	9 (3.57%)	193 (79.42%)	50 (20.58%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	63 (17.50%)	0 (0.00%)	56 (88.89%)	7 (11.11%)	0.2608	0	241 (67.70%)	1 (0.41%)	187 (77.92%)	53 (22.08%)	0.3611	0	193 (53.76%)	6 (3.11%)	150 (80.21%)	37 (19.79%)	0.9239
	Yes		297 (82.50%)	2 (0.67%)	248 (84.07%)	47 (15.93%)			115 (32.30%)	2 (1.74%)	92 (81.42%)	21 (18.58%)			166 (46.24%)	5 (3.01%)	129 (80.12%)	32 (19.88%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	232 (64.44%)	0 (0.00%)	201 (86.64%)	31 (13.36%)	0.2455	0	195 (54.78%)	3 (1.54%)	156 (81.25%)	36 (18.75%)	0.2102	0	232 (64.62%)	10 (4.31%)	177 (79.73%)	45 (20.27%)	0.8710
	Yes		128 (35.56%)	2 (1.56%)	103 (81.75%)	23 (18.25%)			161 (45.22%)	0 (0.00%)	123 (76.40%)	38 (23.60%)			127 (35.38%)	1 (0.79%)	102 (80.95%)	24 (19.05%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.10±0.57	1.21±1.36	0.75±0.89	0.0026	0	0.64±0.73	0.19±0.08	0.65±0.68	0.64±0.92	0.9949	1	0.85±1.47	0.88±0.71	0.86±1.53	0.79±1.33	0.9563
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (0.68%)	120 (81.63%)	27 (18.37%)	0.3839	15	217 (63.64%)	2 (0.92%)	165 (76.74%)	50 (23.26%)	0.1762	18	46 (13.49%)	2 (4.35%)	35 (79.55%)	9 (20.45%)	0.9740
	Non-US		189 (56.08%)	0 (0.00%)	162 (85.71%)	27 (14.29%)			124 (36.36%)	1 (0.81%)	102 (82.93%)	21 (17.07%)			295 (86.51%)	7 (2.37%)	230 (79.86%)	58 (20.14%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (0.68%)	121 (82.31%)	26 (17.69%)	.	15	216 (63.34%)	2 (0.93%)	165 (77.10%)	49 (22.90%)	.	18	46 (13.49%)	2 (4.35%)	35 (79.55%)	9 (20.45%)	.
	Europe		58 (17.21%)	0 (0.00%)	49 (84.48%)	9 (15.52%)			46 (13.49%)	1 (2.17%)	40 (88.89%)	5 (11.11%)			112 (32.84%)	2 (1.79%)	86 (78.18%)	24 (21.82%)	
	Asia		19 (5.64%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (84.21%)	3 (15.79%)			14 (4.11%)	0 (0.00%)	11 (78.57%)	3 (21.43%)			33 (9.68%)	3 (9.09%)	23 (76.67%)	7 (23.33%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=304)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=356)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=74)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=359)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=279)	Female (N=69)	P-value*
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.37%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (75.00%)	2 (25.00%)			6 (1.76%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (50.00%)	3 (50.00%)			10 (2.93%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (60.00%)	4 (40.00%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.59%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			4 (1.17%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
	Africa		11 (3.26%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (54.55%)	5 (45.45%)			3 (0.88%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)			26 (7.62%)	1 (3.85%)	20 (80.00%)	5 (20.00%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.00%)	0 (0.00%)	82 (90.11%)	9 (9.89%)			55 (16.13%)	0 (0.00%)	45 (81.82%)	10 (18.18%)			110 (32.26%)	1 (0.91%)	91 (83.49%)	18 (16.51%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.50%)	0 (0.00%)	22 (81.48%)	5 (18.52%)	0.7596	2	84 (23.73%)	0 (0.00%)	65 (77.38%)	19 (22.62%)	0.6720	10	41 (11.75%)	2 (4.88%)	31 (79.49%)	8 (20.51%)	0.6331
	Neutral		60 (16.67%)	1 (1.67%)	52 (88.14%)	7 (11.86%)			72 (20.34%)	2 (2.78%)	58 (82.86%)	12 (17.14%)			80 (22.92%)	4 (5.00%)	61 (80.26%)	15 (19.74%)	
	Positive		231 (64.17%)	1 (0.43%)	196 (85.22%)	34 (14.78%)			128 (36.16%)	1 (0.78%)	102 (80.31%)	25 (19.69%)			182 (52.15%)	3 (1.65%)	141 (78.77%)	38 (21.23%)	
	Other		42 (11.67%)	0 (0.00%)	34 (80.95%)	8 (19.05%)			70 (19.77%)	0 (0.00%)	53 (75.71%)	17 (24.29%)			46 (13.18%)	2 (4.35%)	38 (86.36%)	6 (13.64%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=201)	Female (N=38)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=238)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=188)	Female (N=47)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=9)	Male (N=181)	Female (N=50)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	0 (0.00%)	127 (83.55%)	25 (16.45%)	0.8773	0	229 (96.22%)	3 (1.31%)	180 (79.65%)	46 (20.35%)	0.3942	0	212 (88.33%)	8 (3.77%)	159 (77.94%)	45 (22.06%)	0.9767
	101+		88 (36.67%)	1 (1.14%)	74 (85.06%)	13 (14.94%)			9 (3.78%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (88.89%)	1 (11.11%)			28 (11.67%)	1 (3.57%)	22 (81.48%)	5 (18.52%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=205)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=174)	Female (N=29)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=250)	Unknown (N=1)	Male (N=194)	Female (N=55)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=107)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=86)	Female (N=19)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	84 (40.98%)	0 (0.00%)	71 (84.52%)	13 (15.48%)	0.8362	0	81 (32.40%)	0 (0.00%)	70 (86.42%)	11 (13.58%)	0.0811	0	31 (28.97%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (80.65%)	6 (19.35%)	0.7166
	Midwest		28 (13.66%)	1 (3.57%)	22 (81.48%)	5 (18.52%)			40 (16.00%)	0 (0.00%)	31 (77.50%)	9 (22.50%)			13 (12.15%)	1 (7.69%)	11 (91.67%)	1 (8.33%)	
	South		54 (26.34%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (88.89%)	6 (11.11%)			84 (33.60%)	0 (0.00%)	58 (69.05%)	26 (30.95%)			30 (28.04%)	1 (3.33%)	23 (79.31%)	6 (20.69%)	
	West		39 (19.02%)	1 (2.56%)	33 (86.84%)	5 (13.16%)			45 (18.00%)	1 (2.22%)	35 (79.55%)	9 (20.45%)			33 (30.84%)	0 (0.00%)	27 (81.82%)	6 (18.18%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=338)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=282)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=267)	Female (N=71)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=263)	Female (N=67)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	1	222 (65.88%)	2 (0.90%)	185 (84.09%)	35 (15.91%)	1.0000	0	257 (75.37%)	1 (0.39%)	197 (76.95%)	59 (23.05%)	0.1036	3	113 (33.43%)	1 (0.88%)	90 (80.36%)	22 (19.64%)	0.8308
	Non-US	115 (34.12%)	0 (0.00%)	96 (83.48%)	19 (16.52%)	84 (24.63%)			2 (2.38%)	70 (85.37%)	12 (14.63%)	225 (66.57%)			7 (3.11%)	173 (79.36%)	45 (20.64%)		
Continent	North America	1	217 (64.39%)	2 (0.92%)	183 (85.12%)	32 (14.88%)	0.0556	0	256 (75.07%)	1 (0.39%)	197 (77.25%)	58 (22.75%)	0.6604	3	112 (33.14%)	1 (0.89%)	89 (80.18%)	22 (19.82%)	0.6399
	Europe	101 (29.97%)	0 (0.00%)	85 (84.16%)	16 (15.84%)	66 (19.35%)			2 (3.03%)	55 (85.94%)	9 (14.06%)	175 (51.78%)			5 (2.86%)	138 (81.18%)	32 (18.82%)		
	Asia	5 (1.48%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (80.00%)	1 (20.00%)	11 (3.23%)			0 (0.00%)	9 (81.82%)	2 (18.18%)	21 (6.21%)			1 (4.76%)	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)		
	Australia/NZ	10 (2.97%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (80.00%)	2 (20.00%)	5 (1.47%)			0 (0.00%)	3 (60.00%)	2 (40.00%)	19 (5.62%)			0 (0.00%)	14 (73.68%)	5 (26.32%)		
	Central/South America	1 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	1 (0.29%)			0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.30%)			0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)		
	Africa	3 (0.89%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.67%)	1 (0.29%)			0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (2.37%)			1 (12.50%)	6 (85.71%)	1 (14.29%)		
	Other/Unknown					1 (0.29%)			0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.59%)			0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)		
Specialty	CVD	0	74 (21.89%)	0 (0.00%)	67 (90.54%)	7 (9.46%)	0.1690	0	55 (16.13%)	1 (1.82%)	46 (85.19%)	8 (14.81%)	0.6382	0	43 (12.61%)	0 (0.00%)	40 (93.02%)	3 (6.98%)	0.0100
	Neoplasms	37 (10.95%)	0 (0.00%)	33 (89.19%)	4 (10.81%)	23 (6.74%)			0 (0.00%)	18 (78.26%)	5 (21.74%)	19 (5.57%)			0 (0.00%)	18 (94.74%)	1 (5.26%)		
	Infectious Diseases	21 (6.21%)	0 (0.00%)	16 (76.19%)	5 (23.81%)	19 (5.57%)			0 (0.00%)	14 (73.68%)	5 (26.32%)	36 (10.56%)			0 (0.00%)	31 (86.11%)	5 (13.89%)		
	All other	206 (60.95%)	2 (0.97%)	166 (81.37%)	38 (18.63%)	244 (71.55%)			2 (0.82%)	189 (78.10%)	53 (21.90%)	243 (71.26%)			11 (4.53%)	174 (75.00%)	58 (25.00%)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	2	80 (23.81%)	1 (1.25%)	67 (84.81%)	12 (15.19%)	0.8628	4	70 (20.77%)	1 (1.43%)	57 (82.61%)	12 (17.39%)	0.5144	5	43 (12.80%)	1 (2.33%)	30 (71.43%)	12 (28.57%)	0.1469
	Yes	256 (76.19%)	1 (0.39%)	213 (83.53%)	42 (16.47%)	267 (79.23%)			2 (0.75%)	207 (78.11%)	58 (21.89%)	293 (87.20%)			6 (2.05%)	233 (81.18%)	54 (18.82%)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	2	34 (10.12%)	1 (2.94%)	28 (84.85%)	5 (15.15%)	1.0000	4	32 (9.50%)	0 (0.00%)	26 (81.25%)	6 (18.75%)	0.8264	5	39 (11.61%)	0 (0.00%)	25 (64.10%)	14 (35.90%)	0.0113
	Yes	302 (89.88%)	1 (0.33%)	252 (83.72%)	49 (16.28%)	305 (90.50%)			3 (0.98%)	238 (78.81%)	64 (21.19%)	297 (88.39%)			7 (2.36%)	238 (82.07%)	52 (17.93%)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	2	30 (8.93%)	0 (0.00%)	20 (66.67%)	10 (33.33%)	0.0120	4	23 (6.82%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (60.87%)	9 (39.13%)	0.0328	5	47 (13.99%)	2 (4.26%)	33 (73.33%)	12 (26.67%)	0.3164
	Yes	306 (91.07%)	2 (0.65%)	260 (85.53%)	44 (14.47%)	314 (93.18%)			3 (0.96%)	250 (80.39%)	61 (19.61%)	289 (86.01%)			5 (1.73%)	230 (80.99%)	54 (19.01%)		

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=338)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=282)	Female (N=54)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=267)	Female (N=71)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=341)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=263)	Female (N=67)	P-value*
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	2	1 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000	4						5					
	Yes		335 (99.70%)	2 (0.60%)	279 (83.78%)	54 (16.22%)			337 (100.00%)	3 (0.89%)	264 (79.04%)	70 (20.96%)			336 (100.00%)	7 (2.08%)	263 (79.94%)	66 (20.06%)	
Degree	MD-only	0	208 (61.54%)	1 (0.48%)	182 (87.92%)	25 (12.08%)	<.0001	0	196 (57.48%)	1 (0.51%)	157 (80.51%)	38 (19.49%)	0.0122	2	172 (50.74%)	7 (4.07%)	140 (84.85%)	25 (15.15%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		41 (12.13%)	0 (0.00%)	26 (63.41%)	15 (36.59%)			60 (17.60%)	1 (1.67%)	38 (64.41%)	21 (35.59%)			90 (26.55%)	2 (2.22%)	57 (64.77%)	31 (35.23%)	
	Both		77 (22.78%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (89.61%)	8 (10.39%)			72 (21.11%)	0 (0.00%)	63 (87.50%)	9 (12.50%)			66 (19.47%)	0 (0.00%)	60 (90.91%)	6 (9.09%)	
	Neither		12 (3.55%)	1 (8.33%)	5 (45.45%)	6 (54.55%)			13 (3.81%)	1 (7.69%)	9 (75.00%)	3 (25.00%)			11 (3.24%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (54.55%)	5 (45.45%)	
Degree-MD	No	0	53 (15.68%)	1 (1.89%)	31 (59.62%)	21 (40.38%)	<.0001	0	73 (21.41%)	2 (2.74%)	47 (66.20%)	24 (33.80%)	0.0029	2	101 (29.79%)	2 (1.98%)	63 (63.64%)	36 (36.36%)	<.0001
	Yes		285 (84.32%)	1 (0.35%)	251 (88.38%)	33 (11.62%)			268 (78.59%)	1 (0.37%)	220 (82.40%)	47 (17.60%)			238 (70.21%)	7 (2.94%)	200 (86.58%)	31 (13.42%)	
Degree-Dual	No	0	261 (77.22%)	2 (0.77%)	213 (82.24%)	46 (17.76%)	0.1221	0	269 (78.89%)	3 (1.12%)	204 (76.69%)	62 (23.31%)	0.0458	2	273 (80.53%)	9 (3.30%)	203 (76.89%)	61 (23.11%)	0.0114
	Yes		77 (22.78%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (89.61%)	8 (10.39%)			72 (21.11%)	0 (0.00%)	63 (87.50%)	9 (12.50%)			66 (19.47%)	0 (0.00%)	60 (90.91%)	6 (9.09%)	
Title	L-only	0	56 (16.57%)	0 (0.00%)	47 (83.93%)	9 (16.07%)	0.6473	0	41 (12.02%)	0 (0.00%)	32 (78.05%)	9 (21.95%)	0.9188	1	34 (10.00%)	1 (2.94%)	28 (84.85%)	5 (15.15%)	0.0006
	AR-only		69 (20.41%)	0 (0.00%)	58 (84.06%)	11 (15.94%)			86 (25.22%)	0 (0.00%)	66 (76.74%)	20 (23.26%)			74 (21.76%)	1 (1.35%)	56 (76.71%)	17 (23.29%)	
	Both		177 (52.37%)	0 (0.00%)	151 (85.31%)	26 (14.69%)			155 (45.45%)	1 (0.65%)	124 (80.52%)	30 (19.48%)			196 (57.65%)	1 (0.51%)	164 (84.10%)	31 (15.90%)	
	Neither		36 (10.65%)	2 (5.56%)	26 (76.47%)	8 (23.53%)			59 (17.30%)	2 (3.39%)	45 (78.95%)	12 (21.05%)			36 (10.59%)	7 (19.44%)	15 (51.72%)	14 (48.28%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	105 (31.07%)	2 (1.90%)	84 (81.55%)	19 (18.45%)	0.4306	0	145 (42.52%)	2 (1.38%)	111 (77.62%)	32 (22.38%)	0.5960	1	110 (32.35%)	8 (7.27%)	71 (69.61%)	31 (30.39%)	0.0023
	Yes		233 (68.93%)	0 (0.00%)	198 (84.98%)	35 (15.02%)			196 (57.48%)	1 (0.51%)	156 (80.00%)	39 (20.00%)			230 (67.65%)	2 (0.87%)	192 (84.21%)	36 (15.79%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	92 (27.22%)	2 (2.17%)	73 (81.11%)	17 (18.89%)	0.3950	0	100 (29.33%)	2 (2.00%)	77 (78.57%)	21 (21.43%)	0.9030	1	70 (20.59%)	8 (11.43%)	43 (69.35%)	19 (30.65%)	0.0247
	Yes		246 (72.78%)	0 (0.00%)	209 (84.96%)	37 (15.04%)			241 (70.67%)	1 (0.41%)	190 (79.17%)	50 (20.83%)			270 (79.41%)	2 (0.74%)	220 (82.09%)	48 (17.91%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with last authors as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Any Significant Author

Endpoint 1: Gender (female/male)

Tables 2.4.1 and 2.4.2 below showed the descriptive table for publication-level and author-level significant author characteristics by the gender of significant authors in column percentages and row percentages, respectively. More specifically, Tables 2.4.3 and 2.4.4 showed the descriptive tables within each journal.

Table 2.4.1: Percentage of Female Significant Author Characteristics (All journals; column percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=3201)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=2313)	Female (N=842)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	1238 (38.68%)	25 (54.35%)	897 (38.78%)	316 (37.53%)	0.8173
	2009-2014		1068 (33.36%)	10 (21.74%)	774 (33.46%)	284 (33.73%)	
	2015-2019		895 (27.96%)	11 (23.91%)	642 (27.76%)	242 (28.74%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	1407 (43.96%)	23 (50.00%)	959 (41.46%)	425 (50.48%)	<.0001
	11-20		1188 (37.11%)	15 (32.61%)	883 (38.18%)	290 (34.44%)	
	21+		606 (18.93%)	8 (17.39%)	471 (20.36%)	127 (15.08%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	1615 (50.45%)	11 (23.91%)	1153 (49.85%)	451 (53.56%)	0.0884
	Non-US		1586 (49.55%)	35 (76.09%)	1160 (50.15%)	391 (46.44%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	1468 (45.86%)	23 (50.00%)	985 (42.59%)	460 (54.63%)	<.0001
	Yes		1733 (54.14%)	23 (50.00%)	1328 (57.41%)	382 (45.37%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	1957 (61.14%)	36 (78.26%)	1445 (62.47%)	476 (56.53%)	0.0059
	Yes		1244 (38.86%)	10 (21.74%)	868 (37.53%)	366 (43.47%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	3	0.88±1.23	0.82±1.03	0.95±1.31	0.69±0.96	<.0001
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	169	1222 (40.30%)	10 (25.64%)	853 (39.00%)	359 (44.54%)	0.0125
	Non-US		1810 (59.70%)	29 (74.36%)	1334 (61.00%)	447 (55.46%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	169	1219 (40.20%)	10 (25.64%)	853 (39.00%)	356 (44.17%)	<.0001
	Europe		642 (21.17%)	10 (25.64%)	457 (20.90%)	175 (21.71%)	
	Asia		197 (6.50%)	8 (20.51%)	141 (6.45%)	48 (5.96%)	
	Australia/NZ		72 (2.37%)	1 (2.56%)	38 (1.74%)	33 (4.09%)	
	Central/South America		21 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	17 (0.78%)	4 (0.50%)	
	Africa		120 (3.96%)	5 (12.82%)	76 (3.48%)	39 (4.84%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=3201)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=2313)	Female (N=842)	P-value*
	Other/Unknown		761 (25.10%)	5 (12.82%)	605 (27.66%)	151 (18.73%)	
Directionality	Negative	35	454 (14.34%)	7 (15.22%)	306 (13.37%)	141 (16.95%)	0.0339
	Neutral		634 (20.03%)	17 (36.96%)	458 (20.02%)	159 (19.11%)	
	Positive		1615 (51.01%)	13 (28.26%)	1205 (52.67%)	397 (47.72%)	
	Other		463 (14.62%)	9 (19.57%)	319 (13.94%)	135 (16.23%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2142)	Unknown (N=32)	Male (N=1546)	Female (N=564)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	1767 (82.49%)	30 (93.75%)	1239 (80.14%)	498 (88.30%)	<.0001
	101+		375 (17.51%)	2 (6.25%)	307 (19.86%)	66 (11.70%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1615)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=1153)	Female (N=451)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	564 (34.92%)	2 (18.18%)	410 (35.56%)	152 (33.70%)	0.3305
	Midwest		260 (16.10%)	4 (36.36%)	195 (16.91%)	61 (13.53%)	
	South		466 (28.85%)	1 (9.09%)	322 (27.93%)	143 (31.71%)	
	West		325 (20.12%)	4 (36.36%)	226 (19.60%)	95 (21.06%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2839)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=1999)	Female (N=794)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	9	1575 (55.65%)	11 (28.95%)	1094 (54.75%)	470 (59.19%)	0.0363
	Non-US		1255 (44.35%)	27 (71.05%)	904 (45.25%)	324 (40.81%)	
Continent	North America	9	1563 (55.23%)	10 (26.32%)	1089 (54.50%)	464 (58.44%)	0.1950
	Europe		939 (33.18%)	19 (50.00%)	683 (34.18%)	237 (29.85%)	
	Asia		128 (4.52%)	7 (18.42%)	84 (4.20%)	37 (4.66%)	
	Australia/NZ		119 (4.20%)	1 (2.63%)	81 (4.05%)	37 (4.66%)	
	Central/South America		16 (0.57%)	0 (0.00%)	12 (0.60%)	4 (0.50%)	
	Africa		58 (2.05%)	1 (2.63%)	42 (2.10%)	15 (1.89%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2839)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=1999)	Female (N=794)	P-value*
	Other/Unknown		7 (0.25%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (0.35%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	435 (15.32%)	4 (8.70%)	368 (18.41%)	63 (7.93%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms		219 (7.71%)	0 (0.00%)	173 (8.65%)	46 (5.79%)	
	Infectious Diseases		174 (6.13%)	0 (0.00%)	120 (6.00%)	54 (6.80%)	
	All other		2011 (70.83%)	42 (91.30%)	1338 (66.93%)	631 (79.47%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	33	534 (19.03%)	7 (20.59%)	375 (18.87%)	152 (19.36%)	0.7669
	Yes		2272 (80.97%)	27 (79.41%)	1612 (81.13%)	633 (80.64%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	33	310 (11.05%)	4 (11.76%)	216 (10.87%)	90 (11.46%)	0.6528
	Yes		2496 (88.95%)	30 (88.24%)	1771 (89.13%)	695 (88.54%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	33	292 (10.41%)	5 (14.71%)	178 (8.96%)	109 (13.89%)	0.0001
	Yes		2514 (89.59%)	29 (85.29%)	1809 (91.04%)	676 (86.11%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	33	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.05%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000
	Yes		2805 (99.96%)	34 (100.00%)	1986 (99.95%)	785 (100.00%)	
Degree	MD-only	6	1486 (52.45%)	21 (52.50%)	1143 (57.18%)	322 (40.55%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		615 (21.71%)	11 (27.50%)	331 (16.56%)	273 (34.38%)	
	Both		524 (18.50%)	3 (7.50%)	432 (21.61%)	89 (11.21%)	
	Neither		208 (7.34%)	5 (12.50%)	93 (4.65%)	110 (13.85%)	
Degree-MD	No	6	823 (29.05%)	16 (40.00%)	424 (21.21%)	383 (48.24%)	<.0001
	Yes		2010 (70.95%)	24 (60.00%)	1575 (78.79%)	411 (51.76%)	
Degree-Dual	No	6	2309 (81.50%)	37 (92.50%)	1567 (78.39%)	705 (88.79%)	<.0001
	Yes		524 (18.50%)	3 (7.50%)	432 (21.61%)	89 (11.21%)	
Title	L-only	5	299 (10.55%)	4 (9.76%)	219 (10.96%)	76 (9.57%)	<.0001
	AR-only		717 (25.30%)	3 (7.32%)	486 (24.31%)	228 (28.72%)	
	Both		1219 (43.01%)	3 (7.32%)	961 (48.07%)	255 (32.12%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2839)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=1999)	Female (N=794)	P-value*
	Neither		599 (21.14%)	31 (75.61%)	333 (16.66%)	235 (29.60%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	5	1316 (46.44%)	34 (82.93%)	819 (40.97%)	463 (58.31%)	<.0001
	Yes		1518 (53.56%)	7 (17.07%)	1180 (59.03%)	331 (41.69%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	5	898 (31.69%)	35 (85.37%)	552 (27.61%)	311 (39.17%)	<.0001
	Yes		1936 (68.31%)	6 (14.63%)	1447 (72.39%)	483 (60.83%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.4.2: Percentage of Female Significant Author Characteristics (All journals; row percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=3201)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=2313)	Female (N=842)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	1238 (38.68%)	25 (2.02%)	897 (73.95%)	316 (26.05%)	0.8173
	2009-2014		1068 (33.36%)	10 (0.94%)	774 (73.16%)	284 (26.84%)	
	2015-2019		895 (27.96%)	11 (1.23%)	642 (72.62%)	242 (27.38%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	1407 (43.96%)	23 (1.63%)	959 (69.29%)	425 (30.71%)	<.0001
	11-20		1188 (37.11%)	15 (1.26%)	883 (75.28%)	290 (24.72%)	
	21+		606 (18.93%)	8 (1.32%)	471 (78.76%)	127 (21.24%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	1615 (50.45%)	11 (0.68%)	1153 (71.88%)	451 (28.12%)	0.0884
	Non-US		1586 (49.55%)	35 (2.21%)	1160 (74.79%)	391 (25.21%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	1468 (45.86%)	23 (1.57%)	985 (68.17%)	460 (31.83%)	<.0001
	Yes		1733 (54.14%)	23 (1.33%)	1328 (77.66%)	382 (22.34%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	1957 (61.14%)	36 (1.84%)	1445 (75.22%)	476 (24.78%)	0.0059
	Yes		1244 (38.86%)	10 (0.80%)	868 (70.34%)	366 (29.66%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	3	0.88±1.23	0.82±1.03	0.95±1.31	0.69±0.96	<.0001
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	169	1222 (40.30%)	10 (0.82%)	853 (70.38%)	359 (29.62%)	0.0125
	Non-US		1810 (59.70%)	29 (1.60%)	1334 (74.90%)	447 (25.10%)	
	North America	169	1219 (40.20%)	10 (0.82%)	853 (70.55%)	356 (29.45%)	<.0001

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=3201)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=2313)	Female (N=842)	P-value*
Continent of Patient Recruitment	Europe		642 (21.17%)	10 (1.56%)	457 (72.31%)	175 (27.69%)	
	Asia		197 (6.50%)	8 (4.06%)	141 (74.60%)	48 (25.40%)	
	Australia/NZ		72 (2.37%)	1 (1.39%)	38 (53.52%)	33 (46.48%)	
	Central/South America		21 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	17 (80.95%)	4 (19.05%)	
	Africa		120 (3.96%)	5 (4.17%)	76 (66.09%)	39 (33.91%)	
	Other/Unknown		761 (25.10%)	5 (0.66%)	605 (80.03%)	151 (19.97%)	
Directionality	Negative	35	454 (14.34%)	7 (1.54%)	306 (68.46%)	141 (31.54%)	0.0339
	Neutral		634 (20.03%)	17 (2.68%)	458 (74.23%)	159 (25.77%)	
	Positive		1615 (51.01%)	13 (0.80%)	1205 (75.22%)	397 (24.78%)	
	Other		463 (14.62%)	9 (1.94%)	319 (70.26%)	135 (29.74%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2142)	Unknown (N=32)	Male (N=1546)	Female (N=564)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	1767 (82.49%)	30 (1.70%)	1239 (71.33%)	498 (28.67%)	<.0001
	101+		375 (17.51%)	2 (0.53%)	307 (82.31%)	66 (17.69%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1615)	Unknown (N=11)	Male (N=1153)	Female (N=451)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Midwest	0	260 (16.10%)	4 (1.54%)	195 (76.17%)	61 (23.83%)	0.3305
	Northeast		564 (34.92%)	2 (0.35%)	410 (72.95%)	152 (27.05%)	
	South		466 (28.85%)	1 (0.21%)	322 (69.25%)	143 (30.75%)	
	West		325 (20.12%)	4 (1.23%)	226 (70.40%)	95 (29.60%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2839)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=1999)	Female (N=794)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	9	1575 (55.65%)	11 (0.70%)	1094 (69.95%)	470 (30.05%)	0.0363
	Non-US		1255 (44.35%)	27 (2.15%)	904 (73.62%)	324 (26.38%)	
Continent	North America	9	1563 (55.23%)	10 (0.64%)	1089 (70.12%)	464 (29.88%)	0.1950

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2839)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=1999)	Female (N=794)	P-value*
	Europe		939 (33.18%)	19 (2.02%)	683 (74.24%)	237 (25.76%)	
	Asia		128 (4.52%)	7 (5.47%)	84 (69.42%)	37 (30.58%)	
	Australia/NZ		119 (4.20%)	1 (0.84%)	81 (68.64%)	37 (31.36%)	
	Central/South America		16 (0.57%)	0 (0.00%)	12 (75.00%)	4 (25.00%)	
	Africa		58 (2.05%)	1 (1.72%)	42 (73.68%)	15 (26.32%)	
	Other/Unknown		7 (0.25%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	435 (15.32%)	4 (0.92%)	368 (85.38%)	63 (14.62%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms		219 (7.71%)	0 (0.00%)	173 (79.00%)	46 (21.00%)	
	Infectious Diseases		174 (6.13%)	0 (0.00%)	120 (68.97%)	54 (31.03%)	
	All other		2011 (70.83%)	42 (2.09%)	1338 (67.95%)	631 (32.05%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	33	534 (19.03%)	7 (1.31%)	375 (71.16%)	152 (28.84%)	0.7669
	Yes		2272 (80.97%)	27 (1.19%)	1612 (71.80%)	633 (28.20%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	33	310 (11.05%)	4 (1.29%)	216 (70.59%)	90 (29.41%)	0.6528
	Yes		2496 (88.95%)	30 (1.20%)	1771 (71.82%)	695 (28.18%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	33	292 (10.41%)	5 (1.71%)	178 (62.02%)	109 (37.98%)	0.0001
	Yes		2514 (89.59%)	29 (1.15%)	1809 (72.80%)	676 (27.20%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	33	1 (0.04%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000
	Yes		2805 (99.96%)	34 (1.21%)	1986 (71.67%)	785 (28.33%)	
Degree	MD-only	6	1486 (52.45%)	21 (1.41%)	1143 (78.02%)	322 (21.98%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		615 (21.71%)	11 (1.79%)	331 (54.80%)	273 (45.20%)	
	Both		524 (18.50%)	3 (0.57%)	432 (82.92%)	89 (17.08%)	
	Neither		208 (7.34%)	5 (2.40%)	93 (45.81%)	110 (54.19%)	
Degree-MD	No	6	823 (29.05%)	16 (1.94%)	424 (52.54%)	383 (47.46%)	<.0001
	Yes		2010 (70.95%)	24 (1.19%)	1575 (79.31%)	411 (20.69%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=2839)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=1999)	Female (N=794)	P-value*
Degree-Dual	No	6	2309 (81.50%)	37 (1.60%)	1567 (68.97%)	705 (31.03%)	<.0001
	Yes		524 (18.50%)	3 (0.57%)	432 (82.92%)	89 (17.08%)	
Title	L-only	5	299 (10.55%)	4 (1.34%)	219 (74.24%)	76 (25.76%)	<.0001
	AR-only		717 (25.30%)	3 (0.42%)	486 (68.07%)	228 (31.93%)	
	Both		1219 (43.01%)	3 (0.25%)	961 (79.03%)	255 (20.97%)	
	Neither		599 (21.14%)	31 (5.18%)	333 (58.63%)	235 (41.37%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	5	1316 (46.44%)	34 (2.58%)	819 (63.88%)	463 (36.12%)	<.0001
	Yes		1518 (53.56%)	7 (0.46%)	1180 (78.09%)	331 (21.91%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	5	898 (31.69%)	35 (3.90%)	552 (63.96%)	311 (36.04%)	<.0001
	Yes		1936 (68.31%)	6 (0.31%)	1447 (74.97%)	483 (25.03%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.4.3: Percentage of Female Significant Author Characteristics (column percentages)

Variable	Level	NEJM					P-value*	JAMA					P-value*	LANCET					P-value*
		Nmissing	Total (N=1079)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=865)	Female (N=208)		Nmissing	Total (N=1053)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=695)	Female (N=345)		Nmissing	Total (N=1069)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=753)	Female (N=289)	
Time Period	2002-2008	0	419 (38.83%)	5 (83.33%)	337 (38.96%)	77 (37.02%)	0.1604	0	406 (38.56%)	3 (23.08%)	266 (38.27%)	137 (39.71%)	0.9047	0	413 (38.63%)	17 (62.96%)	294 (39.04%)	102 (35.29%)	0.2595
	2009-2014		360 (33.36%)	1 (16.67%)	298 (34.45%)	61 (29.33%)			349 (33.14%)	1 (7.69%)	235 (33.81%)	113 (32.75%)			359 (33.58%)	8 (29.63%)	241 (32.01%)	110 (38.06%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.80%)	0 (0.00%)	230 (26.59%)	70 (33.65%)			298 (28.30%)	9 (69.23%)	194 (27.91%)	95 (27.54%)			297 (27.78%)	2 (7.41%)	218 (28.95%)	77 (26.64%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	302 (27.99%)	2 (33.33%)	232 (26.82%)	68 (32.69%)	0.2837	0	615 (58.40%)	4 (30.77%)	395 (56.83%)	216 (62.61%)	0.1303	0	490 (45.84%)	17 (62.96%)	332 (44.09%)	141 (48.79%)	0.3632
	11-20		489 (45.32%)	2 (33.33%)	397 (45.90%)	90 (43.27%)			315 (29.91%)	4 (30.77%)	212 (30.50%)	99 (28.70%)			384 (35.92%)	9 (33.33%)	274 (36.39%)	101 (34.95%)	
	21+		288 (26.69%)	2 (33.33%)	236 (27.28%)	50 (24.04%)			123 (11.68%)	5 (38.46%)	88 (12.66%)	30 (8.70%)			195 (18.24%)	1 (3.70%)	147 (19.52%)	47 (16.26%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	598 (55.42%)	5 (83.33%)	475 (54.91%)	118 (56.73%)	0.6529	0	726 (68.95%)	3 (23.08%)	461 (66.33%)	262 (75.94%)	0.0025	0	291 (27.22%)	3 (11.11%)	217 (28.82%)	71 (24.57%)	0.1869
	Non-US		481 (44.58%)	1 (16.67%)	390 (45.09%)	90 (43.27%)			327 (31.05%)	10 (76.92%)	234 (33.67%)	83 (24.06%)			778 (72.78%)	24 (88.89%)	536 (71.18%)	218 (75.43%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	188 (17.42%)	3 (50.00%)	139 (16.07%)	46 (22.12%)	0.0650	0	708 (67.24%)	5 (38.46%)	447 (64.32%)	256 (74.20%)	0.0025	0	572 (53.51%)	15 (55.56%)	399 (52.99%)	158 (54.67%)	0.6490
	Yes		891 (82.58%)	3 (50.00%)	726 (83.93%)	162 (77.88%)			345 (32.76%)	8 (61.54%)	248 (35.68%)	89 (25.80%)			497 (46.49%)	12 (44.44%)	354 (47.01%)	131 (45.33%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	695 (64.41%)	4 (66.67%)	574 (66.36%)	117 (56.25%)	0.0105	0	574 (54.51%)	9 (69.23%)	388 (55.83%)	177 (51.30%)	0.2061	0	688 (64.36%)	23 (85.19%)	483 (64.14%)	182 (62.98%)	0.7461
	Yes		384 (35.59%)	2 (33.33%)	291 (33.64%)	91 (43.75%)			479 (45.49%)	4 (30.77%)	307 (44.17%)	168 (48.70%)			381 (35.64%)	4 (14.81%)	270 (35.86%)	107 (37.02%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.30	1.52±1.49	1.20±1.33	0.88±1.13	0.0022	0	0.64±0.73	0.73±1.39	0.66±0.69	0.61±0.78	0.4933	3	0.85±1.47	0.70±0.63	0.93±1.63	0.66±1.00	0.0211
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	69	444 (43.96%)	1 (20.00%)	355 (43.88%)	88 (44.90%)	0.8059	46	640 (63.56%)	6 (50.00%)	399 (60.36%)	235 (70.36%)	0.0031	54	138 (13.60%)	3 (13.64%)	99 (13.81%)	36 (13.04%)	0.7746
	Non-US		566 (56.04%)	4 (80.00%)	454 (56.12%)	108 (55.10%)			367 (36.44%)	6 (50.00%)	262 (39.64%)	99 (29.64%)			877 (86.40%)	19 (86.36%)	618 (86.19%)	240 (86.96%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	69	444 (43.96%)	1 (20.00%)	356 (44.00%)	87 (44.39%)	.	46	637 (63.26%)	6 (50.00%)	398 (60.21%)	233 (69.76%)	0.0683	54	138 (13.60%)	3 (13.64%)	99 (13.81%)	36 (13.04%)	0.0696
	Europe		173 (17.13%)	1 (20.00%)	136 (16.81%)	36 (18.37%)			138 (13.70%)	3 (25.00%)	97 (14.67%)	38 (11.38%)			331 (32.61%)	6 (27.27%)	224 (31.24%)	101 (36.59%)	
	Asia		57 (5.64%)	1 (20.00%)	45 (5.56%)	11 (5.61%)			42 (4.17%)	3 (25.00%)	31 (4.69%)	8 (2.40%)			98 (9.66%)	4 (18.18%)	65 (9.07%)	29 (10.51%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1079)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=865)	Female (N=208)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1053)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=695)	Female (N=345)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1069)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=753)	Female (N=289)	P-value*
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.38%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (1.85%)	9 (4.59%)			18 (1.79%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (1.51%)	8 (2.40%)			30 (2.96%)	1 (4.55%)	13 (1.81%)	16 (5.80%)	
	Central/South America		6 (0.59%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (0.74%)	0 (0.00%)			3 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.30%)	1 (0.30%)			12 (1.18%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (1.26%)	3 (1.09%)	
	Africa		33 (3.27%)	0 (0.00%)	17 (2.10%)	16 (8.16%)			9 (0.89%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (1.06%)	2 (0.60%)			78 (7.68%)	5 (22.73%)	52 (7.25%)	21 (7.61%)	
	Other/Unknown		273 (27.03%)	2 (40.00%)	234 (28.92%)	37 (18.88%)			160 (15.89%)	0 (0.00%)	116 (17.55%)	44 (13.17%)			328 (32.32%)	3 (13.64%)	255 (35.56%)	70 (25.36%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	81 (7.51%)	0 (0.00%)	62 (7.17%)	19 (9.13%)	0.5381	6	251 (23.97%)	2 (15.38%)	165 (23.88%)	84 (24.49%)	0.9151	29	122 (11.73%)	5 (18.52%)	79 (10.79%)	38 (13.52%)	0.7293
	Neutral		180 (16.68%)	3 (50.00%)	144 (16.65%)	33 (15.87%)			216 (20.63%)	6 (46.15%)	144 (20.84%)	66 (19.24%)			238 (22.88%)	8 (29.63%)	170 (23.22%)	60 (21.35%)	
	Positive		693 (64.23%)	2 (33.33%)	564 (65.20%)	127 (61.06%)			378 (36.10%)	4 (30.77%)	251 (36.32%)	123 (35.86%)			544 (52.31%)	7 (25.93%)	390 (53.28%)	147 (52.31%)	
	Other		125 (11.58%)	1 (16.67%)	95 (10.98%)	29 (13.94%)			202 (19.29%)	1 (7.69%)	131 (18.96%)	70 (20.41%)			136 (13.08%)	7 (25.93%)	93 (12.70%)	36 (12.81%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=720)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=577)	Female (N=141)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=707)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=472)	Female (N=225)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=715)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=497)	Female (N=198)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	456 (63.33%)	1 (50.00%)	355 (61.53%)	100 (70.92%)	0.0347	0	680 (96.18%)	10 (100.00%)	449 (95.13%)	221 (98.22%)	0.0280	0	631 (88.25%)	19 (95.00%)	435 (87.53%)	177 (89.39%)	0.4719
	101+		264 (36.67%)	1 (50.00%)	222 (38.47%)	41 (29.08%)			27 (3.82%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (4.87%)	4 (1.78%)			84 (11.75%)	1 (5.00%)	62 (12.47%)	21 (10.61%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=598)	Unknown (N=5)	Male (N=475)	Female (N=118)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=726)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=461)	Female (N=262)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=291)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=217)	Female (N=71)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	240 (40.13%)	1 (20.00%)	186 (39.16%)	53 (44.92%)	0.6579	0	226 (31.13%)	0 (0.00%)	156 (33.84%)	70 (26.72%)	0.0021	0	98 (33.68%)	1 (33.33%)	68 (31.34%)	29 (40.85%)	0.3653
	Midwest		90 (15.05%)	2 (40.00%)	71 (14.95%)	17 (14.41%)			124 (17.08%)	1 (33.33%)	91 (19.74%)	32 (12.21%)			46 (15.81%)	1 (33.33%)	33 (15.21%)	12 (16.90%)	
	South		155 (25.92%)	0 (0.00%)	125 (26.32%)	30 (25.42%)			234 (32.23%)	0 (0.00%)	138 (29.93%)	96 (36.64%)			77 (26.46%)	1 (33.33%)	59 (27.19%)	17 (23.94%)	
	West		113 (18.90%)	2 (40.00%)	93 (19.58%)	18 (15.25%)			142 (19.56%)	2 (66.67%)	76 (16.49%)	64 (24.43%)			70 (24.05%)	0 (0.00%)	57 (26.27%)	13 (18.31%)	

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=915)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=717)	Female (N=192)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1015)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=665)	Female (N=337)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1016)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=711)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	1	574 (62.80%)	5 (83.33%)	450 (62.85%)	119 (61.98%)	0.8644	0	751 (73.99%)	4 (30.77%)	475 (71.43%)	272 (80.71%)	0.0014	8	327 (32.44%)	2 (10.53%)	239 (33.61%)	86 (30.94%)	0.4200
	Non-US	340 (37.20%)	1 (16.67%)	266 (37.15%)	73 (38.02%)	264 (26.01%)		9 (69.23%)	190 (28.57%)	65 (19.29%)	681 (67.56%)	17 (89.47%)		472 (66.39%)	192 (69.06%)				
Continent	North America	1	571 (62.47%)	5 (83.33%)	450 (62.85%)	116 (60.42%)	0.1958	0	743 (73.20%)	3 (23.08%)	470 (70.68%)	270 (80.12%)	0.0278	8	325 (32.24%)	2 (10.53%)	238 (33.47%)	85 (30.58%)	0.1581
	Europe	260 (28.45%)	1 (16.67%)	208 (29.05%)	51 (26.56%)	213 (20.99%)		6 (46.15%)	151 (22.71%)	56 (16.62%)	494 (49.01%)	12 (63.16%)		347 (48.80%)	135 (48.56%)				
	Asia	23 (2.52%)	0 (0.00%)	18 (2.51%)	5 (2.60%)	34 (3.35%)		4 (30.77%)	25 (3.76%)	5 (1.48%)	72 (7.14%)	3 (15.79%)		41 (5.77%)	28 (10.07%)				
	Australia/NZ	38 (4.16%)	0 (0.00%)	27 (3.77%)	11 (5.73%)	15 (1.48%)		0 (0.00%)	10 (1.50%)	5 (1.48%)	68 (6.75%)	1 (5.26%)		46 (6.47%)	21 (7.55%)				
	Central/South America	6 (0.66%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (0.56%)	2 (1.04%)	1 (0.10%)		0 (0.00%)	1 (0.15%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (0.89%)	0 (0.00%)		7 (0.98%)	2 (0.72%)				
	Africa	15 (1.64%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (1.12%)	7 (3.65%)	7 (0.69%)		0 (0.00%)	6 (0.90%)	1 (0.30%)	36 (3.57%)	1 (5.26%)		28 (3.94%)	7 (2.52%)				
	Other/Unknown	1 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.14%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (0.20%)		0 (0.00%)	2 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (0.40%)	0 (0.00%)		4 (0.56%)	0 (0.00%)				
Specialty	CVD	0	209 (22.84%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (25.94%)	23 (11.98%)	<.0001	0	133 (13.10%)	3 (23.08%)	104 (15.64%)	26 (7.72%)	0.0022	0	135 (13.29%)	1 (3.70%)	115 (16.17%)	19 (6.83%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms	108 (11.80%)	0 (0.00%)	88 (12.27%)	20 (10.42%)	56 (5.52%)		0 (0.00%)	41 (6.17%)	15 (4.45%)	65 (6.40%)	0 (0.00%)		53 (7.45%)	12 (4.32%)				
	Infectious Diseases	59 (6.45%)	0 (0.00%)	39 (5.44%)	20 (10.42%)	47 (4.63%)		0 (0.00%)	30 (4.51%)	17 (5.04%)	75 (7.38%)	0 (0.00%)		57 (8.02%)	18 (6.47%)				
	All other	539 (58.91%)	6 (100.00%)	404 (56.35%)	129 (67.19%)	779 (76.75%)		10 (76.92%)	490 (73.68%)	279 (82.79%)	741 (72.93%)	26 (96.30%)		486 (68.35%)	229 (82.37%)				
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	6	210 (23.10%)	2 (50.00%)	164 (22.97%)	44 (23.04%)	1.0000	12	220 (21.93%)	3 (25.00%)	145 (22.04%)	72 (21.62%)	0.9374	15	132 (13.19%)	2 (11.11%)	92 (12.98%)	38 (13.87%)	0.7466
	Yes	699 (76.90%)	2 (50.00%)	550 (77.03%)	147 (76.96%)	783 (78.07%)		9 (75.00%)	513 (77.96%)	261 (78.38%)	869 (86.81%)	16 (88.89%)		617 (87.02%)	236 (86.13%)				
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	6	98 (10.78%)	2 (50.00%)	78 (10.92%)	18 (9.42%)	0.6008	12	109 (10.87%)	1 (8.33%)	68 (10.33%)	40 (12.01%)	0.4559	15	108 (10.79%)	1 (5.56%)	74 (10.44%)	33 (12.04%)	0.4942
	Yes	811 (89.22%)	2 (50.00%)	636 (89.08%)	173 (90.58%)	894 (89.13%)		11 (91.67%)	590 (89.67%)	293 (87.99%)	893 (89.21%)	17 (94.44%)		635 (89.56%)	241 (87.96%)				
Concordance of Specialty	No	6	83 (9.13%)	0 (0.00%)	55 (7.70%)	28 (14.66%)	0.0055	12	78 (7.78%)	0 (0.00%)	44 (6.69%)	34 (10.21%)	0.0591	15	137 (13.69%)	5 (27.78%)	84 (11.85%)	48 (17.52%)	0.0211

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=915)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=717)	Female (N=192)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1015)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=665)	Female (N=337)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1016)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=711)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	Yes		826 (90.87%)	4 (100.00%)	659 (92.30%)	163 (85.34%)			925 (92.22%)	12 (100.00%)	614 (93.31%)	299 (89.79%)			864 (86.31%)	13 (72.22%)	625 (88.15%)	226 (82.48%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	6	1 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.14%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000	12						15					
	Yes		908 (99.89%)	4 (100.00%)	713 (99.86%)	191 (100.00%)			1003 (100.00%)	12 (100.00%)	658 (100.00%)	333 (100.00%)			1001 (100.00%)	18 (100.00%)	709 (100.00%)	274 (100.00%)	
Degree	MD-only	0	572 (62.51%)	3 (50.00%)	470 (65.55%)	99 (51.56%)	<.0001	0	524 (51.63%)	5 (38.46%)	374 (56.24%)	145 (43.03%)	<.0001	6	450 (44.55%)	13 (61.90%)	353 (49.65%)	84 (30.22%)	<.0001
	PhD-only		117 (12.79%)	2 (33.33%)	65 (9.07%)	50 (26.04%)			222 (21.87%)	2 (15.38%)	114 (17.14%)	106 (31.45%)			293 (29.01%)	7 (33.33%)	164 (23.07%)	122 (43.88%)	
	Both		193 (21.09%)	0 (0.00%)	167 (23.29%)	26 (13.54%)			173 (17.04%)	3 (23.08%)	137 (20.60%)	33 (9.79%)			188 (18.61%)	0 (0.00%)	156 (21.94%)	32 (11.51%)	
	Neither		33 (3.61%)	1 (16.67%)	15 (2.09%)	17 (8.85%)			96 (9.46%)	3 (23.08%)	40 (6.02%)	53 (15.73%)			79 (7.82%)	1 (4.76%)	38 (5.34%)	40 (14.39%)	
Degree-MD	No	0	150 (16.39%)	3 (50.00%)	80 (11.16%)	67 (34.90%)	<.0001	0	318 (31.33%)	5 (38.46%)	154 (23.16%)	159 (47.18%)	<.0001	6	372 (36.83%)	8 (38.10%)	202 (28.41%)	162 (58.27%)	<.0001
	Yes		765 (83.61%)	3 (50.00%)	637 (88.84%)	125 (65.10%)			697 (68.67%)	8 (61.54%)	511 (76.84%)	178 (52.82%)			638 (63.17%)	13 (61.90%)	509 (71.59%)	116 (41.73%)	
Degree-Dual	No	0	722 (78.91%)	6 (100.00%)	550 (76.71%)	166 (86.46%)	0.0033	0	842 (82.96%)	10 (76.92%)	528 (79.40%)	304 (90.21%)	<.0001	6	822 (81.39%)	21 (100.00%)	555 (78.06%)	246 (88.49%)	0.0002
	Yes		193 (21.09%)	0 (0.00%)	167 (23.29%)	26 (13.54%)			173 (17.04%)	3 (23.08%)	137 (20.60%)	33 (9.79%)			188 (18.61%)	0 (0.00%)	156 (21.94%)	32 (11.51%)	
Title	L-only	0	119 (13.01%)	1 (16.67%)	93 (12.97%)	25 (13.02%)	<.0001	0	93 (9.16%)	0 (0.00%)	62 (9.32%)	31 (9.20%)	0.0003	5	94 (9.30%)	3 (13.64%)	70 (9.85%)	21 (7.55%)	<.0001
	AR-only		187 (20.44%)	0 (0.00%)	133 (18.55%)	54 (28.13%)			268 (26.40%)	0 (0.00%)	180 (27.07%)	88 (26.11%)			275 (27.20%)	3 (13.64%)	184 (25.88%)	88 (31.65%)	
	Both		504 (55.08%)	0 (0.00%)	426 (59.41%)	78 (40.63%)			344 (33.89%)	1 (7.69%)	252 (37.89%)	91 (27.00%)			453 (44.81%)	2 (9.09%)	356 (50.07%)	95 (34.17%)	
	Neither		105 (11.48%)	5 (83.33%)	65 (9.07%)	35 (18.23%)			310 (30.54%)	12 (92.31%)	171 (25.71%)	127 (37.69%)			189 (18.69%)	14 (63.64%)	101 (14.21%)	74 (26.62%)	
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	292 (31.91%)	5 (83.33%)	198 (27.62%)	89 (46.35%)	<.0001	0	578 (56.95%)	12 (92.31%)	351 (52.78%)	215 (63.80%)	0.0009	5	464 (45.90%)	17 (77.27%)	285 (40.08%)	162 (58.27%)	<.0001
	Yes		623 (68.09%)	1 (16.67%)	519 (72.38%)	103 (53.65%)			437 (43.05%)	1 (7.69%)	314 (47.22%)	122 (36.20%)			547 (54.10%)	5 (22.73%)	426 (59.92%)	116 (41.73%)	
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	224 (24.48%)	6 (100.00%)	158 (22.04%)	60 (31.25%)	0.0079	0	403 (39.70%)	12 (92.31%)	233 (35.04%)	158 (46.88%)	0.0003	5	283 (27.99%)	17 (77.27%)	171 (24.05%)	95 (34.17%)	0.0013

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=915)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=717)	Female (N=192)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1015)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=665)	Female (N=337)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1016)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=711)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
	Yes		691 (75.52%)	0 (0.00%)	559 (77.96%)	132 (68.75%)			612 (60.30%)	1 (7.69%)	432 (64.96%)	179 (53.12%)			728 (72.01%)	5 (22.73%)	540 (75.95%)	183 (65.83%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.4.4: Percentage of Female Significant Author Characteristics (row percentages)

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=1079)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=865)	Female (N=208)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1053)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=695)	Female (N=345)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1069)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=753)	Female (N=289)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	419 (38.83%)	5 (1.19%)	337 (81.40%)	77 (18.60%)	0.1604	0	406 (38.56%)	3 (0.74%)	266 (66.00%)	137 (34.00%)	0.9047	0	413 (38.63%)	17 (4.12%)	294 (74.24%)	102 (25.76%)	0.2595
	2009-2014		360 (33.36%)	1 (0.28%)	298 (83.01%)	61 (16.99%)			349 (33.14%)	1 (0.29%)	235 (67.53%)	113 (32.47%)			359 (33.58%)	8 (2.23%)	241 (68.66%)	110 (31.34%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.80%)	0 (0.00%)	230 (76.67%)	70 (23.33%)			298 (28.30%)	9 (3.02%)	194 (67.13%)	95 (32.87%)			297 (27.78%)	2 (0.67%)	218 (73.90%)	77 (26.10%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	302 (27.99%)	2 (0.66%)	232 (77.33%)	68 (22.67%)	0.2837	0	615 (58.40%)	4 (0.65%)	395 (64.65%)	216 (35.35%)	0.1303	0	490 (45.84%)	17 (3.47%)	332 (70.19%)	141 (29.81%)	0.3632
	11-20		489 (45.32%)	2 (0.41%)	397 (81.52%)	90 (18.48%)			315 (29.91%)	4 (1.27%)	212 (68.17%)	99 (31.83%)			384 (35.92%)	9 (2.34%)	274 (73.07%)	101 (26.93%)	
	21+		288 (26.69%)	2 (0.69%)	236 (82.52%)	50 (17.48%)			123 (11.68%)	5 (4.07%)	88 (74.58%)	30 (25.42%)			195 (18.24%)	1 (0.51%)	147 (75.77%)	47 (24.23%)	
Institution Region (at time of Publication) 2	US	0	598 (55.42%)	5 (0.84%)	475 (80.10%)	118 (19.90%)	0.6529	0	726 (68.95%)	3 (0.41%)	461 (63.76%)	262 (36.24%)	0.0025	0	291 (27.22%)	3 (1.03%)	217 (75.35%)	71 (24.65%)	0.1869
	Non-US		481 (44.58%)	1 (0.21%)	390 (81.25%)	90 (18.75%)			327 (31.05%)	10 (3.06%)	234 (73.82%)	83 (26.18%)			778 (72.78%)	24 (3.08%)	536 (71.09%)	218 (28.91%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	188 (17.42%)	3 (1.60%)	139 (75.14%)	46 (24.86%)	0.0650	0	708 (67.24%)	5 (0.71%)	447 (63.58%)	256 (36.42%)	0.0025	0	572 (53.51%)	15 (2.62%)	399 (71.63%)	158 (28.37%)	0.6490
	Yes		891 (82.58%)	3 (0.34%)	726 (81.76%)	162 (18.24%)			345 (32.76%)	8 (2.32%)	248 (73.59%)	89 (26.41%)			497 (46.49%)	12 (2.41%)	354 (72.99%)	131 (27.01%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	695 (64.41%)	4 (0.58%)	574 (83.07%)	117 (16.93%)	0.0105	0	574 (54.51%)	9 (1.57%)	388 (68.67%)	177 (31.33%)	0.2061	0	688 (64.36%)	23 (3.34%)	483 (72.63%)	182 (27.37%)	0.7461
	Yes		384 (35.59%)	2 (0.52%)	291 (76.18%)	91 (23.82%)			479 (45.49%)	4 (0.84%)	307 (64.63%)	168 (35.37%)			381 (35.64%)	4 (1.05%)	270 (71.62%)	107 (28.38%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.30	1.52±1.49	1.20±1.33	0.88±1.13	0.0022	0	0.64±0.73	0.73±1.39	0.66±0.69	0.61±0.78	0.4933	3	0.85±1.47	0.70±0.63	0.93±1.63	0.66±1.00	0.0211
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	69	444 (43.96%)	1 (0.23%)	355 (80.14%)	88 (19.86%)	0.8059	46	640 (63.56%)	6 (0.94%)	399 (62.93%)	235 (37.07%)	0.0031	54	138 (13.60%)	3 (2.17%)	99 (73.33%)	36 (26.67%)	0.7746
	Non-US		566 (56.04%)	4 (0.71%)	454 (80.78%)	108 (19.22%)			367 (36.44%)	6 (1.63%)	262 (72.58%)	99 (27.42%)			877 (86.40%)	19 (2.17%)	618 (72.03%)	240 (27.97%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	69	444 (43.96%)	1 (0.23%)	356 (80.36%)	87 (19.64%)	.	46	637 (63.26%)	6 (0.94%)	398 (63.07%)	233 (36.93%)	0.0683	54	138 (13.60%)	3 (2.17%)	99 (73.33%)	36 (26.67%)	0.0696
	Europe		173 (17.13%)	1 (0.58%)	136 (79.07%)	36 (20.93%)			138 (13.70%)	3 (2.17%)	97 (71.85%)	38 (28.15%)			331 (32.61%)	6 (1.81%)	224 (68.92%)	101 (31.08%)	
	Asia		57 (5.64%)	1 (1.75%)	45 (80.36%)	11 (19.64%)			42 (4.17%)	3 (7.14%)	31 (79.49%)	8 (20.51%)			98 (9.66%)	4 (4.08%)	65 (69.15%)	29 (30.85%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1079)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=865)	Female (N=208)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1053)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=695)	Female (N=345)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1069)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=753)	Female (N=289)	P-value*
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.38%)	0 (0.00%)	15 (62.50%)	9 (37.50%)			18 (1.79%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (55.56%)	8 (44.44%)			30 (2.96%)	1 (3.33%)	13 (44.83%)	16 (55.17%)	
	Central/South America		6 (0.59%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			3 (0.30%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)			12 (1.18%)	0 (0.00%)	9 (75.00%)	3 (25.00%)	
	Africa		33 (3.27%)	0 (0.00%)	17 (51.52%)	16 (48.48%)			9 (0.89%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (77.78%)	2 (22.22%)			78 (7.68%)	5 (6.41%)	52 (71.23%)	21 (28.77%)	
	Other/Unknown		273 (27.03%)	2 (0.73%)	234 (86.35%)	37 (13.65%)			160 (15.89%)	0 (0.00%)	116 (72.50%)	44 (27.50%)			328 (32.32%)	3 (0.91%)	255 (78.46%)	70 (21.54%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	81 (7.51%)	0 (0.00%)	62 (76.54%)	19 (23.46%)	0.5381	6	251 (23.97%)	2 (0.80%)	165 (66.27%)	84 (33.73%)	0.9151	29	122 (11.73%)	5 (4.10%)	79 (67.52%)	38 (32.48%)	0.7293
	Neutral		180 (16.68%)	3 (1.67%)	144 (81.36%)	33 (18.64%)			216 (20.63%)	6 (2.78%)	144 (68.57%)	66 (31.43%)			238 (22.88%)	8 (3.36%)	170 (73.91%)	60 (26.09%)	
	Positive		693 (64.23%)	2 (0.29%)	564 (81.62%)	127 (18.38%)			378 (36.10%)	4 (1.06%)	251 (67.11%)	123 (32.89%)			544 (52.31%)	7 (1.29%)	390 (72.63%)	147 (27.37%)	
	Other		125 (11.58%)	1 (0.80%)	95 (76.61%)	29 (23.39%)			202 (19.29%)	1 (0.50%)	131 (65.17%)	70 (34.83%)			136 (13.08%)	7 (5.15%)	93 (72.09%)	36 (27.91%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=720)	Unknown (N=2)	Male (N=577)	Female (N=141)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=707)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=472)	Female (N=225)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=715)	Unknown (N=20)	Male (N=497)	Female (N=198)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	456 (63.33%)	1 (0.22%)	355 (78.02%)	100 (21.98%)	0.0347	0	680 (96.18%)	10 (1.47%)	449 (67.01%)	221 (32.99%)	0.0280	0	631 (88.25%)	19 (3.01%)	435 (71.08%)	177 (28.92%)	0.4719
	101+		264 (36.67%)	1 (0.38%)	222 (84.41%)	41 (15.59%)			27 (3.82%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (85.19%)	4 (14.81%)			84 (11.75%)	1 (1.19%)	62 (74.70%)	21 (25.30%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=598)	Unknown (N=5)	Male (N=475)	Female (N=118)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=726)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=461)	Female (N=262)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=291)	Unknown (N=3)	Male (N=217)	Female (N=71)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	Northeast	0	240 (40.13%)	1 (0.42%)	186 (77.82%)	53 (22.18%)	0.6579	0	226 (31.13%)	0 (0.00%)	156 (69.03%)	70 (30.97%)	0.0021	0	98 (33.68%)	1 (1.02%)	68 (70.10%)	29 (29.90%)	0.3653
	Midwest		90 (15.05%)	2 (2.22%)	71 (80.68%)	17 (19.32%)			124 (17.08%)	1 (0.81%)	91 (73.98%)	32 (26.02%)			46 (15.81%)	1 (2.17%)	33 (73.33%)	12 (26.67%)	
	South		155 (25.92%)	0 (0.00%)	125 (80.65%)	30 (19.35%)			234 (32.23%)	0 (0.00%)	138 (58.97%)	96 (41.03%)			77 (26.46%)	1 (1.30%)	59 (77.63%)	17 (22.37%)	
	West		113 (18.90%)	2 (1.77%)	93 (83.78%)	18 (16.22%)			142 (19.56%)	2 (1.41%)	76 (54.29%)	64 (45.71%)			70 (24.05%)	0 (0.00%)	57 (81.43%)	13 (18.57%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=915)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=717)	Female (N=192)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1015)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=665)	Female (N=337)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=1016)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=711)	Female (N=278)	P-value*
US-based	US/Canada	1	574 (62.80%)	5 (0.87%)	450 (79.09%)	119 (20.91%)	0.8644	0	751 (73.99%)	4 (0.53%)	475 (63.59%)	272 (36.41%)	0.0014	8	327 (32.44%)	2 (0.61%)	239 (73.54%)	86 (26.46%)	0.4200
	Non-US		340 (37.20%)	1 (0.29%)	266 (78.47%)	73 (21.53%)			264 (26.01%)	9 (3.41%)	190 (74.51%)	65 (25.49%)			681 (67.56%)	17 (2.50%)	472 (71.08%)	192 (28.92%)	
Continent	North America	1	571 (62.47%)	5 (0.88%)	450 (79.51%)	116 (20.49%)	0.1958	0	743 (73.20%)	3 (0.40%)	470 (63.51%)	270 (36.49%)	0.0278	8	325 (32.24%)	2 (0.62%)	238 (73.68%)	85 (26.32%)	0.1581
	Europe		260 (28.45%)	1 (0.38%)	208 (80.31%)	51 (19.69%)			213 (20.99%)	6 (2.82%)	151 (72.95%)	56 (27.05%)			494 (49.01%)	12 (2.43%)	347 (71.99%)	135 (28.01%)	
	Asia		23 (2.52%)	0 (0.00%)	18 (78.26%)	5 (21.74%)			34 (3.35%)	4 (11.76%)	25 (83.33%)	5 (16.67%)			72 (7.14%)	3 (4.17%)	41 (59.42%)	28 (40.58%)	
	Australia/NZ		38 (4.16%)	0 (0.00%)	27 (71.05%)	11 (28.95%)			15 (1.48%)	0 (0.00%)	10 (66.67%)	5 (33.33%)			68 (6.75%)	1 (1.47%)	46 (68.66%)	21 (31.34%)	
	Central/South America		6 (0.66%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)			1 (0.10%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			9 (0.89%)	0 (0.00%)	7 (77.78%)	2 (22.22%)	
	Africa		15 (1.64%)	0 (0.00%)	8 (53.33%)	7 (46.67%)			7 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (85.71%)	1 (14.29%)			36 (3.57%)	1 (2.78%)	28 (80.00%)	7 (20.00%)	
	Other/Unknown		1 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			2 (0.20%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			4 (0.40%)	0 (0.00%)	4 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	
Specialty	CVD	0	209 (22.84%)	0 (0.00%)	186 (89.00%)	23 (11.00%)	<.0001	0	133 (13.10%)	3 (2.26%)	104 (80.00%)	26 (20.00%)	0.0022	0	135 (13.29%)	1 (0.74%)	115 (85.82%)	19 (14.18%)	<.0001
	Neoplasms		108 (11.80%)	0 (0.00%)	88 (81.48%)	20 (18.52%)			56 (5.52%)	0 (0.00%)	41 (73.21%)	15 (26.79%)			65 (6.40%)	0 (0.00%)	53 (81.54%)	12 (18.46%)	
	Infectious Diseases		59 (6.45%)	0 (0.00%)	39 (66.10%)	20 (33.90%)			47 (4.63%)	0 (0.00%)	30 (63.83%)	17 (36.17%)			75 (7.38%)	0 (0.00%)	57 (76.00%)	18 (24.00%)	
	All other		539 (58.91%)	6 (1.11%)	404 (75.80%)	129 (24.20%)			779 (76.75%)	10 (1.28%)	490 (63.72%)	279 (36.28%)			741 (72.93%)	26 (3.51%)	486 (67.97%)	229 (32.03%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-CVD	No	6	210 (23.10%)	2 (0.95%)	164 (78.85%)	44 (21.15%)	1.0000	12	220 (21.93%)	3 (1.36%)	145 (66.82%)	72 (33.18%)	0.9374	15	132 (13.19%)	2 (1.52%)	92 (70.77%)	38 (29.23%)	0.7466
	Yes		699 (76.90%)	2 (0.29%)	550 (78.91%)	147 (21.09%)			783 (78.07%)	9 (1.15%)	513 (66.28%)	261 (33.72%)			869 (86.81%)	16 (1.84%)	617 (72.33%)	236 (27.67%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Neoplasms	No	6	98 (10.78%)	2 (2.04%)	78 (81.25%)	18 (18.75%)	0.6008	12	109 (10.87%)	1 (0.92%)	68 (62.96%)	40 (37.04%)	0.4559	15	108 (10.79%)	1 (0.93%)	74 (69.16%)	33 (30.84%)	0.4942
	Yes		811 (89.22%)	2 (0.25%)	636 (78.62%)	173 (21.38%)			894 (89.13%)	11 (1.23%)	590 (66.82%)	293 (33.18%)			893 (89.21%)	17 (1.90%)	635 (72.49%)	241 (27.51%)	
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Infectious Diseases	No	6	83 (9.13%)	0 (0.00%)	55 (66.27%)	28 (33.73%)	0.0055	12	78 (7.78%)	0 (0.00%)	44 (56.41%)	34 (43.59%)	0.0591	15	137 (13.69%)	5 (3.65%)	84 (63.64%)	48 (36.36%)	0.0211
	Yes		826 (90.87%)	4 (0.48%)	659 (80.17%)	163 (19.83%)			925 (92.22%)	12 (1.30%)	614 (67.25%)	299 (32.75%)			864 (86.31%)	13 (1.50%)	625 (73.44%)	226 (26.56%)	

Variable	Level	NEJM					P-value*	JAMA					P-value*	LANCET					P-value*	
		Nmissing	Total (N=915)	Unknown (N=6)	Male (N=717)	Female (N=192)		Nmissing	Total (N=1015)	Unknown (N=13)	Male (N=665)	Female (N=337)		Nmissing	Total (N=1016)	Unknown (N=27)	Male (N=711)	Female (N=278)		
Concordance of Specialty with MeSH Category-Any of the above 3	No	6	1 (0.11%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1.0000	12						15						
	Yes		908 (99.89%)	4 (0.44%)	713 (78.87%)	191 (21.13%)			1003 (100.00%)	12 (1.20%)	658 (66.40%)	333 (33.60%)			1001 (100.00%)	18 (1.80%)	709 (72.13%)	274 (27.87%)		
Degree	MD-only	0	572 (62.51%)	3 (0.52%)	470 (82.60%)	99 (17.40%)	<.0001	0	524 (51.63%)	5 (0.95%)	374 (72.06%)	145 (27.94%)	<.0001	6	450 (44.55%)	13 (2.89%)	353 (80.78%)	84 (19.22%)	<.0001	
	PhD-only		117 (12.79%)	2 (1.71%)	65 (56.52%)	50 (43.48%)			222 (21.87%)	2 (0.90%)	114 (51.82%)	106 (48.18%)			293 (29.01%)	7 (2.39%)	164 (57.34%)	122 (42.66%)		
	Both		193 (21.09%)	0 (0.00%)	167 (86.53%)	26 (13.47%)			173 (17.04%)	3 (1.73%)	137 (80.59%)	33 (19.41%)			188 (18.61%)	0 (0.00%)	156 (82.98%)	32 (17.02%)		
	Neither		33 (3.61%)	1 (3.03%)	15 (46.88%)	17 (53.13%)			96 (9.46%)	3 (3.13%)	40 (43.01%)	53 (56.99%)			79 (7.82%)	1 (1.27%)	38 (48.72%)	40 (51.28%)		
Degree-MD	No	0	150 (16.39%)	3 (2.00%)	80 (54.42%)	67 (45.58%)	<.0001	0	318 (31.33%)	5 (1.57%)	154 (49.20%)	159 (50.80%)	<.0001	6	372 (36.83%)	8 (2.15%)	202 (55.49%)	162 (44.51%)	<.0001	
	Yes		765 (83.61%)	3 (0.39%)	637 (83.60%)	125 (16.40%)			697 (68.67%)	8 (1.15%)	511 (74.17%)	178 (25.83%)			638 (63.17%)	13 (2.04%)	509 (81.44%)	116 (18.56%)		
Degree-Dual	No	0	722 (78.91%)	6 (0.83%)	550 (76.82%)	166 (23.18%)	0.0033	0	842 (82.96%)	10 (1.19%)	528 (63.46%)	304 (36.54%)	<.0001	6	822 (81.39%)	21 (2.55%)	555 (69.29%)	246 (30.71%)	0.0002	
	Yes		193 (21.09%)	0 (0.00%)	167 (86.53%)	26 (13.47%)			173 (17.04%)	3 (1.73%)	137 (80.59%)	33 (19.41%)			188 (18.61%)	0 (0.00%)	156 (82.98%)	32 (17.02%)		
Title	L-only	0	119 (13.01%)	1 (0.84%)	93 (78.81%)	25 (21.19%)	<.0001	0	93 (9.16%)	0 (0.00%)	62 (66.67%)	31 (33.33%)	0.0003	5	94 (9.30%)	3 (3.19%)	70 (76.92%)	21 (23.08%)	<.0001	
	AR-only		187 (20.44%)	0 (0.00%)	133 (71.12%)	54 (28.88%)			268 (26.40%)	0 (0.00%)	180 (67.16%)	88 (32.84%)			275 (27.20%)	3 (1.09%)	184 (67.65%)	88 (32.35%)		
	Both		504 (55.08%)	0 (0.00%)	426 (84.52%)	78 (15.48%)			344 (33.89%)	1 (0.29%)	252 (73.47%)	91 (26.53%)			453 (44.81%)	2 (0.44%)	356 (78.94%)	95 (21.06%)		
	Neither		105 (11.48%)	5 (4.76%)	65 (65.00%)	35 (35.00%)			310 (30.54%)	12 (3.87%)	171 (57.38%)	127 (42.62%)			189 (18.69%)	14 (7.41%)	101 (57.71%)	74 (42.29%)		
Title-Leadership Position	No	0	292 (31.91%)	5 (1.71%)	198 (68.99%)	89 (31.01%)	<.0001	0	578 (56.95%)	12 (2.08%)	351 (62.01%)	215 (37.99%)	0.0009	5	464 (45.90%)	17 (3.66%)	285 (63.76%)	162 (36.24%)	<.0001	
	Yes		623 (68.09%)	1 (0.16%)	519 (83.44%)	103 (16.56%)			437 (43.05%)	1 (0.23%)	314 (72.02%)	122 (27.98%)			547 (54.10%)	5 (0.91%)	426 (78.60%)	116 (21.40%)		
Title-Academic Rank	No	0	224 (24.48%)	6 (2.68%)	158 (72.48%)	60 (27.52%)	0.0079	0	403 (39.70%)	12 (2.98%)	233 (59.59%)	158 (40.41%)	0.0003	5	283 (27.99%)	17 (6.01%)	171 (64.29%)	95 (35.71%)	0.0013	
	Yes		691 (75.52%)	0 (0.00%)	559 (80.90%)	132 (19.10%)			612 (60.30%)	1 (0.16%)	432 (70.70%)	179 (29.30%)			728 (72.01%)	5 (0.69%)	540 (74.69%)	183 (25.31%)		

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. For publication-level variables, p-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect; for author-level variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Any Female Significant Authors

If any of 1st/2nd/last author was female, then any female significant authors was defined as “Yes”, otherwise it was either defined as “No” if all significant authors were male or “Unknown” if there existed significant authors with unknown gender. Note that row percentages for No/Yes and p-values comparing Yes vs. No were based on data after excluding “Unknown”.

Table 2.5.1: Publication Characteristics by Any Female Significant Authors (All journals; column percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=26)	No (N=444)	Yes (N=610)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	420 (38.89%)	14 (53.85%)	176 (39.64%)	230 (37.70%)	0.6235
	2009-2014		360 (33.33%)	6 (23.08%)	151 (34.01%)	203 (33.28%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.78%)	6 (23.08%)	117 (26.35%)	177 (29.02%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	482 (44.63%)	11 (42.31%)	173 (38.96%)	298 (48.85%)	0.0009
	11-20		396 (36.67%)	11 (42.31%)	168 (37.84%)	217 (35.57%)	
	21+		202 (18.70%)	4 (15.38%)	103 (23.20%)	95 (15.57%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	502 (46.48%)	14 (53.85%)	169 (38.06%)	319 (52.30%)	<.0001
	Yes		578 (53.52%)	12 (46.15%)	275 (61.94%)	291 (47.70%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	663 (61.39%)	21 (80.77%)	291 (65.54%)	351 (57.54%)	0.0086
	Yes		417 (38.61%)	5 (19.23%)	153 (34.46%)	259 (42.46%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.88±1.23	0.93±1.28	1.12±1.54	0.70±0.89	<.0001
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	61	411 (40.33%)	4 (19.05%)	157 (37.83%)	250 (42.88%)	0.1096
	Non-US		608 (59.67%)	17 (80.95%)	258 (62.17%)	333 (57.12%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	61	410 (40.24%)	4 (19.05%)	158 (38.07%)	248 (42.54%)	0.0003
	Europe		216 (21.20%)	7 (33.33%)	75 (18.07%)	134 (22.98%)	
	Asia		66 (6.48%)	5 (23.81%)	27 (6.51%)	34 (5.83%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.36%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (1.45%)	18 (3.09%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (0.72%)	4 (0.69%)	
	Africa		40 (3.93%)	2 (9.52%)	11 (2.65%)	27 (4.63%)	
	Other/Unknown		256 (25.12%)	3 (14.29%)	135 (32.53%)	118 (20.24%)	
Directionality	Negative	12	153 (14.33%)	1 (3.85%)	58 (13.24%)	94 (15.56%)	0.1874
	Neutral		215 (20.13%)	11 (42.31%)	87 (19.86%)	117 (19.37%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=26)	No (N=444)	Yes (N=610)	P-value*
	Positive		542 (50.75%)	9 (34.62%)	238 (54.34%)	295 (48.84%)	
	Other		158 (14.79%)	5 (19.23%)	55 (12.56%)	98 (16.23%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=720)	Unknown (N=19)	No (N=296)	Yes (N=405)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	595 (82.64%)	17 (89.47%)	229 (77.36%)	349 (86.17%)	0.0025
	101+		125 (17.36%)	2 (10.53%)	67 (22.64%)	56 (13.83%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding “Unknown”. P-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.5.2: Publication Characteristics by Any Female Significant Authors (All journals; row percentages)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=26)	No (N=444)	Yes (N=610)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	420 (38.89%)	14 (3.33%)	176 (43.35%)	230 (56.65%)	0.6235
	2009-2014		360 (33.33%)	6 (1.67%)	151 (42.66%)	203 (57.34%)	
	2015-2019		300 (27.78%)	6 (2.00%)	117 (39.80%)	177 (60.20%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	482 (44.63%)	11 (2.28%)	173 (36.73%)	298 (63.27%)	0.0009
	11-20		396 (36.67%)	11 (2.78%)	168 (43.64%)	217 (56.36%)	
	21+		202 (18.70%)	4 (1.98%)	103 (52.02%)	95 (47.98%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	502 (46.48%)	14 (2.79%)	169 (34.63%)	319 (65.37%)	<.0001
	Yes		578 (53.52%)	12 (2.08%)	275 (48.59%)	291 (51.41%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	663 (61.39%)	21 (3.17%)	291 (45.33%)	351 (54.67%)	0.0086
	Yes		417 (38.61%)	5 (1.20%)	153 (37.14%)	259 (62.86%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.88±1.23	0.93±1.28	1.12±1.54	0.70±0.89	<.0001
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	61	411 (40.33%)	4 (0.97%)	157 (38.57%)	250 (61.43%)	0.1096
	Non-US		608 (59.67%)	17 (2.80%)	258 (43.65%)	333 (56.35%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	61	410 (40.24%)	4 (0.98%)	158 (38.92%)	248 (61.08%)	0.0003
	Europe		216 (21.20%)	7 (3.24%)	75 (35.89%)	134 (64.11%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=26)	No (N=444)	Yes (N=610)	P-value*
	Asia		66 (6.48%)	5 (7.58%)	27 (44.26%)	34 (55.74%)	
	Australia/NZ		24 (2.36%)	0 (0.00%)	6 (25.00%)	18 (75.00%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.69%)	0 (0.00%)	3 (42.86%)	4 (57.14%)	
	Africa		40 (3.93%)	2 (5.00%)	11 (28.95%)	27 (71.05%)	
	Other/Unknown		256 (25.12%)	3 (1.17%)	135 (53.36%)	118 (46.64%)	
Directionality	Negative	12	153 (14.33%)	1 (0.65%)	58 (38.16%)	94 (61.84%)	0.1874
	Neutral		215 (20.13%)	11 (5.12%)	87 (42.65%)	117 (57.35%)	
	Positive		542 (50.75%)	9 (1.66%)	238 (44.65%)	295 (55.35%)	
	Other		158 (14.79%)	5 (3.16%)	55 (35.95%)	98 (64.05%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=720)	Unknown (N=19)	No (N=296)	Yes (N=405)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	595 (82.64%)	17 (2.86%)	229 (39.62%)	349 (60.38%)	0.0025
	101+		125 (17.36%)	2 (1.60%)	67 (54.47%)	56 (45.53%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding “Unknown”. P-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.5.3: Publication Characteristics by Any Female Significant Authors (column percentages)

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=5)	No (N=190)	Yes (N=165)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	No (N=118)	Yes (N=236)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=15)	No (N=136)	Yes (N=209)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	140 (38.89%)	4 (80.00%)	75 (39.47%)	61 (36.97%)	0.4190	0	140 (38.89%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (40.68%)	92 (38.98%)	0.7941	0	140 (38.89%)	10 (66.67%)	53 (38.97%)	77 (36.84%)	0.8156
	2009-2014		120 (33.33%)	1 (20.00%)	67 (35.26%)	52 (31.52%)			120 (33.33%)	1 (16.67%)	41 (34.75%)	78 (33.05%)			120 (33.33%)	4 (26.67%)	43 (31.62%)	73 (34.93%)	
	2015-2019		100 (27.78%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (25.26%)	52 (31.52%)			100 (27.78%)	5 (83.33%)	29 (24.58%)	66 (27.97%)			100 (27.78%)	1 (6.67%)	40 (29.41%)	59 (28.23%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	101 (28.06%)	1 (20.00%)	47 (24.74%)	53 (32.12%)	0.2110	0	214 (59.44%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (58.47%)	145 (61.44%)	0.3527	0	167 (46.39%)	10 (66.67%)	57 (41.91%)	100 (47.85%)	0.3905
	11-20		163 (45.28%)	2 (40.00%)	87 (45.79%)	74 (44.85%)			105 (29.17%)	4 (66.67%)	32 (27.12%)	69 (29.24%)			128 (35.56%)	5 (33.33%)	49 (36.03%)	74 (35.41%)	
	21+		96 (26.67%)	2 (40.00%)	56 (29.47%)	38 (23.03%)			41 (11.39%)	2 (33.33%)	17 (14.41%)	22 (9.32%)			65 (18.06%)	0 (0.00%)	30 (22.06%)	35 (16.75%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	63 (17.50%)	2 (40.00%)	26 (13.68%)	35 (21.21%)	0.0608	0	245 (68.06%)	3 (50.00%)	73 (61.86%)	169 (71.61%)	0.0631	0	194 (53.89%)	9 (60.00%)	70 (51.47%)	115 (55.02%)	0.5178
	Yes		297 (82.50%)	3 (60.00%)	164 (86.32%)	130 (78.79%)			115 (31.94%)	3 (50.00%)	45 (38.14%)	67 (28.39%)			166 (46.11%)	6 (40.00%)	66 (48.53%)	94 (44.98%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	232 (64.44%)	3 (60.00%)	137 (72.11%)	92 (55.76%)	0.0013	0	198 (55.00%)	5 (83.33%)	67 (56.78%)	126 (53.39%)	0.5460	0	233 (64.72%)	13 (86.67%)	87 (63.97%)	133 (63.64%)	0.9497
	Yes		128 (35.56%)	2 (40.00%)	53 (27.89%)	73 (44.24%)			162 (45.00%)	1 (16.67%)	51 (43.22%)	110 (46.61%)			127 (35.28%)	2 (13.33%)	49 (36.03%)	76 (36.36%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.54±1.66	1.33±1.44	0.91±1.09	0.0021	0	0.64±0.73	1.18±1.99	0.72±0.73	0.59±0.68	0.1178	1	0.85±1.47	0.63±0.66	1.17±2.06	0.65±0.91	0.0072
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (25.00%)	75 (42.37%)	72 (46.15%)	0.4881	19	217 (63.64%)	1 (20.00%)	63 (58.33%)	153 (67.11%)	0.1171	19	46 (13.49%)	2 (16.67%)	19 (14.62%)	25 (12.56%)	0.5928
	Non-US		189 (56.08%)	3 (75.00%)	102 (57.63%)	84 (53.85%)			124 (36.36%)	4 (80.00%)	45 (41.67%)	75 (32.89%)			295 (86.51%)	10 (83.33%)	111 (85.38%)	174 (87.44%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (25.00%)	76 (42.94%)	71 (45.51%)	0.0136	19	216 (63.34%)	1 (20.00%)	63 (58.33%)	152 (66.67%)	0.5845	19	46 (13.49%)	2 (16.67%)	19 (14.62%)	25 (12.56%)	0.1133
	Europe		58 (17.21%)	1 (25.00%)	27 (15.25%)	30 (19.23%)			46 (13.49%)	3 (60.00%)	13 (12.04%)	30 (13.16%)			112 (32.84%)	3 (25.00%)	35 (26.92%)	74 (37.19%)	
	Asia		19 (5.64%)	1 (25.00%)	10 (5.65%)	8 (5.13%)			14 (4.11%)	1 (20.00%)	6 (5.56%)	7 (3.07%)			33 (9.68%)	3 (25.00%)	11 (8.46%)	19 (9.55%)	
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.37%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.13%)	6 (3.85%)			6 (1.76%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.85%)	4 (1.75%)			10 (2.93%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.54%)	8 (4.02%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.59%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.13%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.44%)			4 (1.17%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.77%)	3 (1.51%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=5)	No (N=190)	Yes (N=165)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	No (N=118)	Yes (N=236)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=15)	No (N=136)	Yes (N=209)	P-value*
	Africa		11 (3.26%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (1.13%)	9 (5.77%)			3 (0.88%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (0.93%)	2 (0.88%)			26 (7.62%)	2 (16.67%)	8 (6.15%)	16 (8.04%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.00%)	1 (25.00%)	58 (32.77%)	32 (20.51%)			55 (16.13%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (21.30%)	32 (14.04%)			110 (32.26%)	2 (16.67%)	54 (41.54%)	54 (27.14%)	
Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.50%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (7.37%)	13 (7.88%)	0.5933	2	85 (23.74%)	0 (0.00%)	29 (24.79%)	56 (23.83%)	0.8706	10	41 (11.71%)	1 (6.67%)	15 (11.45%)	25 (12.25%)	0.9049
	Neutral		60 (16.67%)	2 (40.00%)	31 (16.32%)	27 (16.36%)			75 (20.95%)	4 (66.67%)	24 (20.51%)	47 (20.00%)			80 (22.86%)	5 (33.33%)	32 (24.43%)	43 (21.08%)	
	Positive		231 (64.17%)	2 (40.00%)	127 (66.84%)	102 (61.82%)			128 (35.75%)	1 (16.67%)	44 (37.61%)	83 (35.32%)			183 (52.29%)	6 (40.00%)	67 (51.15%)	110 (53.92%)	
	Other		42 (11.67%)	1 (20.00%)	18 (9.47%)	23 (13.94%)			70 (19.55%)	1 (16.67%)	20 (17.09%)	49 (20.85%)			46 (13.14%)	3 (20.00%)	17 (12.98%)	26 (12.75%)	

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=2)	No (N=126)	Yes (N=112)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=6)	No (N=81)	Yes (N=153)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=11)	No (N=89)	Yes (N=140)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	1 (50.00%)	75 (59.52%)	76 (67.86%)	0.1827	0	231 (96.25%)	6 (100.00%)	76 (93.83%)	149 (97.39%)	0.2769	0	212 (88.33%)	10 (90.91%)	78 (87.64%)	124 (88.57%)	0.8314
	101+		88 (36.67%)	1 (50.00%)	51 (40.48%)	36 (32.14%)			9 (3.75%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (6.17%)	4 (2.61%)			28 (11.67%)	1 (9.09%)	11 (12.36%)	16 (11.43%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding "Unknown". P-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table 2.5.4: Publication Characteristics by Any Female Significant Authors (row percentages)

		NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=5)	No (N=190)	Yes (N=165)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	No (N=118)	Yes (N=236)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=15)	No (N=136)	Yes (N=209)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	140 (38.89%)	4 (2.86%)	75 (55.15%)	61 (44.85%)	0.4190	0	140 (38.89%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (34.29%)	92 (65.71%)	0.7941	0	140 (38.89%)	10 (7.14%)	53 (40.77%)	77 (59.23%)	0.8156
	2009-2014		120 (33.33%)	1 (0.83%)	67 (56.30%)	52 (43.70%)			120 (33.33%)	1 (0.83%)	41 (34.45%)	78 (65.55%)			120 (33.33%)	4 (3.33%)	43 (37.07%)	73 (62.93%)	
	2015-2019		100 (27.78%)	0 (0.00%)	48 (48.00%)	52 (52.00%)			100 (27.78%)	5 (5.00%)	29 (30.53%)	66 (69.47%)			100 (27.78%)	1 (1.00%)	40 (40.40%)	59 (59.60%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	101 (28.06%)	1 (0.99%)	47 (47.00%)	53 (53.00%)	0.2110	0	214 (59.44%)	0 (0.00%)	69 (32.24%)	145 (67.76%)	0.3527	0	167 (46.39%)	10 (5.99%)	57 (36.31%)	100 (63.69%)	0.3905
	11-20		163 (45.28%)	2 (1.23%)	87 (54.04%)	74 (45.96%)			105 (29.17%)	4 (3.81%)	32 (31.68%)	69 (68.32%)			128 (35.56%)	5 (3.91%)	49 (39.84%)	74 (60.16%)	
	21+		96 (26.67%)	2 (2.08%)	56 (59.57%)	38 (40.43%)			41 (11.39%)	2 (4.88%)	17 (43.59%)	22 (56.41%)			65 (18.06%)	0 (0.00%)	30 (46.15%)	35 (53.85%)	

Variable	Level	NEJM						JAMA						LANCET					
		Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=5)	No (N=190)	Yes (N=165)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=6)	No (N=118)	Yes (N=236)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=360)	Unknown (N=15)	No (N=136)	Yes (N=209)	P-value*
Clinical Trial	No	0	63 (17.50%)	2 (3.17%)	26 (42.62%)	35 (57.38%)	0.0608	0	245 (68.06%)	3 (1.22%)	73 (30.17%)	169 (69.83%)	0.0631	0	194 (53.89%)	9 (4.64%)	70 (37.84%)	115 (62.16%)	0.5178
	Yes		297 (82.50%)	3 (1.01%)	164 (55.78%)	130 (44.22%)			115 (31.94%)	3 (2.61%)	45 (40.18%)	67 (59.82%)			166 (46.11%)	6 (3.61%)	66 (41.25%)	94 (58.75%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	232 (64.44%)	3 (1.29%)	137 (59.83%)	92 (40.17%)	0.0013	0	198 (55.00%)	5 (2.53%)	67 (34.72%)	126 (65.28%)	0.5460	0	233 (64.72%)	13 (5.58%)	87 (39.55%)	133 (60.45%)	0.9497
	Yes		128 (35.56%)	2 (1.56%)	53 (42.06%)	73 (57.94%)			162 (45.00%)	1 (0.62%)	51 (31.68%)	110 (68.32%)			127 (35.28%)	2 (1.57%)	49 (39.20%)	76 (60.80%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	0	1.14±1.31	1.54±1.66	1.33±1.44	0.91±1.09	0.0021	0	0.64±0.73	1.18±1.99	0.72±0.73	0.59±0.68	0.1178	1	0.85±1.47	0.63±0.66	1.17±2.06	0.65±0.91	0.0072
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (0.68%)	75 (51.02%)	72 (48.98%)	0.4881	19	217 (63.64%)	1 (0.46%)	63 (29.17%)	153 (70.83%)	0.1171	19	46 (13.49%)	2 (4.35%)	19 (43.18%)	25 (56.82%)	0.5928
	Non-US		189 (56.08%)	3 (1.59%)	102 (54.84%)	84 (45.16%)			124 (36.36%)	4 (3.23%)	45 (37.50%)	75 (62.50%)			295 (86.51%)	10 (3.39%)	111 (38.95%)	174 (61.05%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	23	148 (43.92%)	1 (0.68%)	76 (51.70%)	71 (48.30%)	0.0136	19	216 (63.34%)	1 (0.46%)	63 (29.30%)	152 (70.70%)	0.5845	19	46 (13.49%)	2 (4.35%)	19 (43.18%)	25 (56.82%)	0.1133
	Europe		58 (17.21%)	1 (1.72%)	27 (47.37%)	30 (52.63%)			46 (13.49%)	3 (6.52%)	13 (30.23%)	30 (69.77%)			112 (32.84%)	3 (2.68%)	35 (32.11%)	74 (67.89%)	
	Asia		19 (5.64%)	1 (5.26%)	10 (55.56%)	8 (44.44%)			14 (4.11%)	1 (7.14%)	6 (46.15%)	7 (53.85%)			33 (9.68%)	3 (9.09%)	11 (36.67%)	19 (63.33%)	
	Australia/NZ		8 (2.37%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (25.00%)	6 (75.00%)			6 (1.76%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (33.33%)	4 (66.67%)			10 (2.93%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (20.00%)	8 (80.00%)	
	Central/South America		2 (0.59%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)			1 (0.29%)	0 (0.00%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (100.00%)			4 (1.17%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (25.00%)	3 (75.00%)	
	Africa		11 (3.26%)	0 (0.00%)	2 (18.18%)	9 (81.82%)			3 (0.88%)	0 (0.00%)	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.67%)			26 (7.62%)	2 (7.69%)	8 (33.33%)	16 (66.67%)	
	Other/Unknown		91 (27.00%)	1 (1.10%)	58 (64.44%)	32 (35.56%)			55 (16.13%)	0 (0.00%)	23 (41.82%)	32 (58.18%)			110 (32.26%)	2 (1.82%)	54 (50.00%)	54 (50.00%)	
	Directionality	Negative	0	27 (7.50%)	0 (0.00%)	14 (51.85%)	13 (48.15%)	0.5933	2	85 (23.74%)	0 (0.00%)	29 (34.12%)	56 (65.88%)	0.8706	10	41 (11.71%)	1 (2.44%)	15 (37.50%)	25 (62.50%)
Neutral			60 (16.67%)	2 (3.33%)	31 (53.45%)	27 (46.55%)			75 (20.95%)	4 (5.33%)	24 (33.80%)	47 (66.20%)			80 (22.86%)	5 (6.25%)	32 (42.67%)	43 (57.33%)	
Positive			231 (64.17%)	2 (0.87%)	127 (55.46%)	102 (44.54%)			128 (35.75%)	1 (0.78%)	44 (34.65%)	83 (65.35%)			183 (52.29%)	6 (3.28%)	67 (37.85%)	110 (62.15%)	
Other			42 (11.67%)	1 (2.38%)	18 (43.90%)	23 (56.10%)			70 (19.55%)	1 (1.43%)	20 (28.99%)	49 (71.01%)			46 (13.14%)	3 (6.52%)	17 (39.53%)	26 (60.47%)	

		NEJM						JAMA					LANCET						
Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=2)	No (N=126)	Yes (N=112)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=6)	No (N=81)	Yes (N=153)	P-value*	Nmissing	Total (N=240)	Unknown (N=11)	No (N=89)	Yes (N=140)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	152 (63.33%)	1 (0.66%)	75 (49.67%)	76 (50.33%)	0.1827	0	231 (96.25%)	6 (2.60%)	76 (33.78%)	149 (66.22%)	0.2769	0	212 (88.33%)	10 (4.72%)	78 (38.61%)	124 (61.39%)	0.8314
	101+		88 (36.67%)	1 (1.14%)	51 (58.62%)	36 (41.38%)			9 (3.75%)	0 (0.00%)	5 (55.56%)	4 (44.44%)			28 (11.67%)	1 (3.57%)	11 (40.74%)	16 (59.26%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding “Unknown”. P-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Proportion of Female among Significant Authors

Proportion of female among significant authors was defined as the number of female significant (1st/2nd/last) authors divided by the number of significant authors with known gender (female/male).

Table 2.6.1: Proportion of Female among Significant Authors by Publication Characteristics (All journals)

Variable	Level	Nmissing	N	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max	IQR	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	420	0.26	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.8309
	2009-2014		360	0.27	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	2015-2019		300	0.28	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	482	0.31	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50	0.0001
	11-20		396	0.25	0.27	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	21+		202	0.22	0.27	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	
Clinical Trial	No	0	502	0.32	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50	<.0001
	Yes		578	0.23	0.26	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
Grant Funding	No	0	663	0.25	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.0071
	Yes		417	0.30	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	.	.	-0.03	0.01	.	.	.	.	<.0001
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	61	411	0.30	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.0118
	Non-US		608	0.25	0.27	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	61	410	0.30	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.0002
	Europe		216	0.27	0.26	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	Asia		66	0.26	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	Australia/NZ		24	0.47	0.36	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50	
	Central/South America		7	0.19	0.18	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.33	
	Africa		40	0.35	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	
	Other/Unknown		256	0.20	0.25	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	
Directionality	Negative	12	153	0.32	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	0.0288
	Neutral		215	0.26	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	Positive		542	0.25	0.27	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	Other		158	0.29	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	N	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max	IQR	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	595	0.29	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	<.0001
	101+		125	0.18	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.67	0.33	

Note: For continuous variables, “Mean” and “Std” were estimated coefficient and standard error in linear regression models.

*: For categorical variables, p-values were based on Welch’s test assuming unequal variances; for continuous variables, p-values were based on linear regression models.

Table 2.6.2: Proportion of Female among Significant Authors by Publication Characteristics

Variable	Level	Journal	Nmissing	N	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max	IQR	P-value*	
Time Period	2002-2008	NEJM	0	140	0.19	0.24	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	0.1571	
				2009-2014	120	0.17	0.21	0.00	0.00	0.67		0.33
				2015-2019	100	0.23	0.27	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.33
	2002-2008	JAMA	0	140	0.35	0.33	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	0.8321	
				2009-2014	120	0.32	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.58
				2015-2019	100	0.33	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.67
	2002-2008	LANCET	0	140	0.26	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.3270	
				2009-2014	120	0.31	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.58
				2015-2019	100	0.26	0.26	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.33
Co-Author Count	0-10	NEJM	0	101	0.23	0.25	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.2579	
				11-20	163	0.18	0.23	0.00	0.00	1.00		0.33
				21+	96	0.17	0.25	0.00	0.00	1.00		0.33
	0-10	JAMA	0	214	0.36	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	0.1549	
				11-20	105	0.31	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.33
				21+	41	0.26	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.33
	0-10	LANCET	0	167	0.29	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.4971	
				11-20	128	0.27	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.33
				21+	65	0.25	0.27	0.00	0.33	1.00		0.33
Clinical Trial	No	NEJM	0	63	0.25	0.26	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.0622	
	Yes			297	0.18	0.24	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33		
	No	JAMA	0	245	0.36	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	0.0058	

Variable	Level	Journal	Nmissing	N	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max	IQR	P-value*
	Yes			115	0.27	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	No	LANCET	0	194	0.28	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.7233
	Yes			166	0.27	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
Grant Funding	No	NEJM	0	232	0.17	0.24	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	0.0118
	Yes			128	0.24	0.24	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	No	JAMA	0	198	0.32	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50	0.2063
	Yes			162	0.36	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	
	No	LANCET	0	233	0.27	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.7441
	Yes			127	0.28	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	NEJM	.	.	-0.03	0.01	.	.	.	.	0.0019
	-	JAMA	.	.	-0.03	0.02	.	.	.	.	0.2387
	-	LANCET	.	.	-0.02	0.01	.	.	.	.	0.0204
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	NEJM	23	148	0.20	0.23	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	0.8202
	Non-US			189	0.19	0.25	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	
	US/Canada	JAMA	19	217	0.37	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	0.0032
	Non-US			124	0.28	0.27	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	US/Canada	LANCET	19	46	0.27	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.7956
	Non-US			295	0.28	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	NEJM	23	148	0.20	0.23	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	0.0109
	Europe			58	0.21	0.23	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	Asia			19	0.19	0.28	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	
	Australia/NZ			8	0.38	0.33	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	
	Central/South America			2	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	
	Africa			11	0.48	0.31	0.00	0.67	1.00	0.33	
	Other/Unknown			91	0.14	0.21	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33	
	North America	JAMA	19	216	0.37	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	0.1291
	Europe			46	0.28	0.25	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	

Variable	Level	Journal	Nmissing	N	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max	IQR	P-value*				
	Asia			14	0.21	0.24	0.00	0.17	0.67	0.33					
	Australia/NZ			6	0.44	0.40	0.00	0.50	1.00	0.67					
	Central/South America			1	0.33	.	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.00					
	Africa			3	0.22	0.19	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.33					
	Other/Unknown			55	0.28	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50					
	North America	LANCET	19	46	0.27	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.0831				
	Europe			112	0.31	0.28	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33					
	Asia			33	0.31	0.32	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67					
	Australia/NZ			10	0.55	0.39	0.00	0.58	1.00	0.67					
	Central/South America			4	0.25	0.17	0.00	0.33	0.33	0.17					
	Africa			26	0.30	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50					
	Other/Unknown			110	0.21	0.25	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33					
	Directionality			Negative	NEJM	0	27	0.23	0.29	0.00		0.00	1.00	0.33	0.5393
				Neutral			60	0.19	0.24	0.00		0.00	1.00	0.33	
Positive		231	0.18	0.23			0.00	0.00	1.00	0.33					
Other		JAMA	2	42	0.23	0.24	0.00	0.33	0.67	0.33	0.9339				
Negative				85	0.35	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67					
Neutral				75	0.32	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33					
Positive		LANCET	10	128	0.33	0.31	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50	0.6745				
Other				70	0.34	0.29	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.50					
Negative				41	0.33	0.32	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67					
Neutral				80	0.26	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33					
Positive				183	0.27	0.26	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33					
Other				46	0.28	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33					
Variable	Level	Journal	Nmissing	N	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max	IQR	P-value*				
	0-100	NEJM	0	152	0.22	0.26	0.00	0.17	1.00	0.33	0.0340				

Variable	Level	Journal	Nmissing	N	Mean	Std	Min	Median	Max	IQR	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	101+			88	0.16	0.20	0.00	0.00	0.67	0.33	
	0-100	JAMA	0	231	0.33	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.67	0.0150
	101+			9	0.15	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.33	
	0-100	LANCET	0	212	0.29	0.30	0.00	0.33	1.00	0.33	0.4593
	101+			28	0.25	0.25	0.00	0.33	0.67	0.33	

Note: For continuous variables, “Mean” and “Std” were estimated coefficient and standard error in linear regression models.

*: For categorical variables, p-values were based on Welch’s test assuming unequal variances; for continuous variables, p-values were based on linear regression models.

Trend Analysis

Trend analysis for female 1st/2nd/last/any significant authors by year was provided within JAMA/LANCET/NEJM/all journals. Note that authors with unknown gender were excluded here. It turned out that no significant trends were found.

Table 2.7.1: Trend for Female 1st authors by Year

Year	JAMA			LANCET			NEJM			All journals		
	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female
2002	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	10 (50.00%)	10 (50.00%)	60	37 (61.67%)	23 (38.33%)
2003	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	60	45 (75.00%)	15 (25.00%)
2004	20	9 (45.00%)	11 (55.00%)	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	60	41 (68.33%)	19 (31.67%)
2005	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	60	43 (71.67%)	17 (28.33%)
2006	19	11 (57.89%)	8 (42.11%)	19	15 (78.95%)	4 (21.05%)	20	19 (95.00%)	1 (5.00%)	58	45 (77.59%)	13 (22.41%)
2007	20	11 (55.00%)	9 (45.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	60	42 (70.00%)	18 (30.00%)
2008	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	17	14 (82.35%)	3 (17.65%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	57	45 (78.95%)	12 (21.05%)
2009	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	19	13 (68.42%)	6 (31.58%)	20	20 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	59	49 (83.05%)	10 (16.95%)
2010	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	11 (55.00%)	9 (45.00%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	60	45 (75.00%)	15 (25.00%)
2011	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	19 (95.00%)	1 (5.00%)	60	49 (81.67%)	11 (18.33%)
2012	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	60	43 (71.67%)	17 (28.33%)
2013	19	13 (68.42%)	6 (31.58%)	20	10 (50.00%)	10 (50.00%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	59	41 (69.49%)	18 (30.51%)
2014	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	60	46 (76.67%)	14 (23.33%)
2015	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	60	44 (73.33%)	16 (26.67%)

	JAMA			LANCET			NEJM			All journals		
Year	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female
2016	20	10 (50.00%)	10 (50.00%)	19	14 (73.68%)	5 (26.32%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	59	42 (71.19%)	17 (28.81%)
2017	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	60	46 (76.67%)	14 (23.33%)
2018	18	10 (55.56%)	8 (44.44%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	58	41 (70.69%)	17 (29.31%)
2019	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	11 (55.00%)	9 (45.00%)	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	60	39 (65.00%)	21 (35.00%)
OR (95% CI)			0.9966 (0.9568, 1.0381)			1.0045 (0.9631, 1.0478)			0.9882 (0.9380, 1.0412)			0.9965 (0.9704, 1.0232)
P-value*			0.8710			0.8332			0.6571			0.7928

*: P-values were based on GEE models with authors as clustering effect.

Table 2.7.2: Trend for Female 2nd authors by Year

	JAMA			LANCET			NEJM			All journals		
Year	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female
2002	18	9 (50.00%)	9 (50.00%)	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	18	14 (77.78%)	4 (22.22%)	56	35 (62.50%)	21 (37.50%)
2003	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	17	10 (58.82%)	7 (41.18%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	57	36 (63.16%)	21 (36.84%)
2004	17	9 (52.94%)	8 (47.06%)	19	13 (68.42%)	6 (31.58%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	56	39 (69.64%)	17 (30.36%)
2005	19	15 (78.95%)	4 (21.05%)	18	12 (66.67%)	6 (33.33%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	57	43 (75.44%)	14 (24.56%)
2006	15	7 (46.67%)	8 (53.33%)	20	11 (55.00%)	9 (45.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	55	35 (63.64%)	20 (36.36%)
2007	17	8 (47.06%)	9 (52.94%)	17	14 (82.35%)	3 (17.65%)	18	12 (66.67%)	6 (33.33%)	52	34 (65.38%)	18 (34.62%)
2008	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	16	10 (62.50%)	6 (37.50%)	19	13 (68.42%)	6 (31.58%)	55	37 (67.27%)	18 (32.73%)
2009	19	12 (63.16%)	7 (36.84%)	16	12 (75.00%)	4 (25.00%)	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	55	37 (67.27%)	18 (32.73%)
2010	19	9 (47.37%)	10 (52.63%)	20	10 (50.00%)	10 (50.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	59	33 (55.93%)	26 (44.07%)
2011	18	11 (61.11%)	7 (38.89%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	58	43 (74.14%)	15 (25.86%)
2012	20	10 (50.00%)	10 (50.00%)	20	9 (45.00%)	11 (55.00%)	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	60	31 (51.67%)	29 (48.33%)
2013	18	9 (50.00%)	9 (50.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	58	41 (70.69%)	17 (29.31%)
2014	17	8 (47.06%)	9 (52.94%)	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	57	37 (64.91%)	20 (35.09%)
2015	18	12 (66.67%)	6 (33.33%)	19	13 (68.42%)	6 (31.58%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	57	39 (68.42%)	18 (31.58%)
2016	20	8 (40.00%)	12 (60.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	60	41 (68.33%)	19 (31.67%)

	JAMA			LANCET			NEJM			All journals		
Year	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female
2017	20	8 (40.00%)	12 (60.00%)	19	13 (68.42%)	6 (31.58%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	59	35 (59.32%)	24 (40.68%)
2018	16	10 (62.50%)	6 (37.50%)	19	12 (63.16%)	7 (36.84%)	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	55	35 (63.64%)	20 (36.36%)
2019	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	10 (50.00%)	10 (50.00%)	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	60	37 (61.67%)	23 (38.33%)
OR (95% CI)			1.0101 (0.9864, 1.0343)			0.9989 (0.9798, 1.0184)			1.0055 (0.9913, 1.0199)			1.0048 (0.9944, 1.0153)
P-value*			0.4068			0.9095			0.4463			0.3640

*: P-values were based on GEE models with authors as clustering effect.

Table 2.7.3: Trend for Female Last authors by Year

Year	JAMA			LANCET			NEJM			All journals		
	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female
2002	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	19	14 (73.68%)	5 (26.32%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	59	44 (74.58%)	15 (25.42%)
2003	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20	19 (95.00%)	1 (5.00%)	20	20 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)	60	56 (93.33%)	4 (6.67%)
2004	19	16 (84.21%)	3 (15.79%)	19	14 (73.68%)	5 (26.32%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	58	47 (81.03%)	11 (18.97%)
2005	19	15 (78.95%)	4 (21.05%)	19	17 (89.47%)	2 (10.53%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	58	48 (82.76%)	10 (17.24%)
2006	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	19	15 (78.95%)	4 (21.05%)	59	49 (83.05%)	10 (16.95%)
2007	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	19 (95.00%)	1 (5.00%)	60	48 (80.00%)	12 (20.00%)
2008	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	16	14 (87.50%)	2 (12.50%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	56	48 (85.71%)	8 (14.29%)
2009	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	16	14 (87.50%)	2 (12.50%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	56	45 (80.36%)	11 (19.64%)
2010	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	19	15 (78.95%)	4 (21.05%)	59	47 (79.66%)	12 (20.34%)
2011	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	60	46 (76.67%)	14 (23.33%)
2012	20	15 (75.00%)	5 (25.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	19 (95.00%)	1 (5.00%)	60	48 (80.00%)	12 (20.00%)
2013	18	15 (83.33%)	3 (16.67%)	20	13 (65.00%)	7 (35.00%)	20	19 (95.00%)	1 (5.00%)	58	47 (81.03%)	11 (18.97%)
2014	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	14 (70.00%)	6 (30.00%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	60	46 (76.67%)	14 (23.33%)
2015	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	19 (95.00%)	1 (5.00%)	60	52 (86.67%)	8 (13.33%)
2016	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	60	52 (86.67%)	8 (13.33%)
2017	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	17 (85.00%)	3 (15.00%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	60	49 (81.67%)	11 (18.33%)
2018	19	17 (89.47%)	2 (10.53%)	19	13 (68.42%)	6 (31.58%)	20	18 (90.00%)	2 (10.00%)	58	48 (82.76%)	10 (17.24%)
2019	18	14 (77.78%)	4 (22.22%)	20	16 (80.00%)	4 (20.00%)	20	12 (60.00%)	8 (40.00%)	58	42 (72.41%)	16 (27.59%)
OR (95% CI)			0.9857 (0.9412, 1.0324)			1.0352 (0.9865, 1.0863)			1.0291 (0.9734, 1.0881)			1.0164 (0.9869, 1.0469)
P-value*			0.5422			0.1594			0.3122			0.2781

*: P-values were based on GEE models with authors as clustering effect.

Table 2.7.4: Trend for Female Significant authors by Year

Year	JAMA			LANCET			NEJM			All journals		
	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female	Known	Male	Female
2002	58	36 (62.07%)	22 (37.93%)	59	40 (67.80%)	19 (32.20%)	58	40 (68.97%)	18 (31.03%)	175	116 (66.29%)	59 (33.71%)
2003	60	44 (73.33%)	16 (26.67%)	57	42 (73.68%)	15 (26.32%)	60	51 (85.00%)	9 (15.00%)	177	137 (77.40%)	40 (22.60%)
2004	56	34 (60.71%)	22 (39.29%)	58	42 (72.41%)	16 (27.59%)	60	51 (85.00%)	9 (15.00%)	174	127 (72.99%)	47 (27.01%)
2005	58	43 (74.14%)	15 (25.86%)	57	44 (77.19%)	13 (22.81%)	60	47 (78.33%)	13 (21.67%)	175	134 (76.57%)	41 (23.43%)
2006	54	34 (62.96%)	20 (37.04%)	59	44 (74.58%)	15 (25.42%)	59	51 (86.44%)	8 (13.56%)	172	129 (75.00%)	43 (25.00%)
2007	57	32 (56.14%)	25 (43.86%)	57	44 (77.19%)	13 (22.81%)	58	48 (82.76%)	10 (17.24%)	172	124 (72.09%)	48 (27.91%)
2008	60	43 (71.67%)	17 (28.33%)	49	38 (77.55%)	11 (22.45%)	59	49 (83.05%)	10 (16.95%)	168	130 (77.38%)	38 (22.62%)
2009	59	43 (72.88%)	16 (27.12%)	51	39 (76.47%)	12 (23.53%)	60	49 (81.67%)	11 (18.33%)	170	131 (77.06%)	39 (22.94%)
2010	59	40 (67.80%)	19 (32.20%)	60	38 (63.33%)	22 (36.67%)	59	47 (79.66%)	12 (20.34%)	178	125 (70.22%)	53 (29.78%)
2011	58	42 (72.41%)	16 (27.59%)	60	49 (81.67%)	11 (18.33%)	60	47 (78.33%)	13 (21.67%)	178	138 (77.53%)	40 (22.47%)
2012	60	37 (61.67%)	23 (38.33%)	60	36 (60.00%)	24 (40.00%)	60	49 (81.67%)	11 (18.33%)	180	122 (67.78%)	58 (32.22%)
2013	55	37 (67.27%)	18 (32.73%)	60	39 (65.00%)	21 (35.00%)	60	53 (88.33%)	7 (11.67%)	175	129 (73.71%)	46 (26.29%)
2014	57	36 (63.16%)	21 (36.84%)	60	40 (66.67%)	20 (33.33%)	60	53 (88.33%)	7 (11.67%)	177	129 (72.88%)	48 (27.12%)
2015	58	41 (70.69%)	17 (29.31%)	59	44 (74.58%)	15 (25.42%)	60	50 (83.33%)	10 (16.67%)	177	135 (76.27%)	42 (23.73%)
2016	60	35 (58.33%)	25 (41.67%)	59	49 (83.05%)	10 (16.95%)	60	51 (85.00%)	9 (15.00%)	179	135 (75.42%)	44 (24.58%)
2017	60	37 (61.67%)	23 (38.33%)	59	47 (79.66%)	12 (20.34%)	60	46 (76.67%)	14 (23.33%)	179	130 (72.63%)	49 (27.37%)
2018	53	37 (69.81%)	16 (30.19%)	58	41 (70.69%)	17 (29.31%)	60	46 (76.67%)	14 (23.33%)	171	124 (72.51%)	47 (27.49%)
2019	58	44 (75.86%)	14 (24.14%)	60	37 (61.67%)	23 (38.33%)	60	37 (61.67%)	23 (38.33%)	178	118 (66.29%)	60 (33.71%)
OR (95% CI)			0.9967 (0.9708, 1.0234)			1.0081 (0.9807, 1.0364)			1.0171 (0.9822, 1.0531)			1.0073 (0.9901, 1.0248)
P-value*			0.8085			0.5651			0.3413			0.4095

*: P-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect.

Figures

Figure 1: Trend for Female 1st/2nd/last/any significant authors by Year

Multivariable regression analysis

Note that authors with unknown gender were excluded in this section.

Table 3.1.1: Estimated odds ratios for female 1st author based on multivariable regression

Variable	Level	OR (95% CI)	P-value*
Clinical Trial	Yes vs No	0.748 (0.535, 1.045)	0.0970
Co-Author Count	11-20 vs 21+	1.098 (0.724, 1.664)	0.2197
	0-10 vs 11-20	1.268 (0.917, 1.753)	
	0-10 vs 21+	1.392 (0.917, 2.112)	
Degree	MD-only vs PhD-only	0.334 (0.221, 0.507)	<.0001
	Both vs PhD-only	0.241 (0.144, 0.404)	
	Neither vs PhD-only	0.620 (0.293, 1.309)	
	MD-only vs Neither	0.540 (0.259, 1.122)	
	Both vs Neither	0.389 (0.175, 0.867)	
	Both vs MD-only	0.722 (0.456, 1.141)	
Grant Funding	Yes vs No	0.993 (0.722, 1.366)	0.9667
Specialty	Infectious Diseases vs All other	1.948 (1.089, 3.485)	0.0072
	CVD vs Neoplasms	0.397 (0.200, 0.788)	
	Infectious Diseases vs Neoplasms	1.263 (0.606, 2.634)	
	CVD vs Infectious Diseases	0.314 (0.156, 0.635)	
	CVD vs All other	0.613 (0.365, 1.028)	
	Neoplasms vs All other	1.542 (0.888, 2.677)	
Title	Both vs Neither	0.724 (0.469, 1.117)	0.2418
	L-only vs Neither	0.763 (0.386, 1.508)	
	Both vs L-only	0.949 (0.514, 1.752)	
	AR-only vs Neither	1.060 (0.677, 1.661)	
	AR-only vs L-only	1.390 (0.727, 2.658)	
	AR-only vs Both	1.465 (0.990, 2.167)	
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada vs Non-US	1.182 (0.828, 1.687)	0.3738

Variable	Level	OR (95% CI)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	US vs Non-US	1.325 (0.906, 1.937)	0.1533
Journal	JAMA vs LANCET	1.052 (0.714, 1.551)	0.1586
	LANCET vs NEJM	1.412 (0.908, 2.195)	
	JAMA vs NEJM	1.486 (0.978, 2.257)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	Unit=1	0.795 (0.658, 0.960)	0.0154

*: P-values were based on type 3 tests in multivariable GEE model with first authors as clustering effect.

Table 3.1.2: Estimated odds ratios for female 1st author based on multivariable regression (2008 forward)

Variable	Level	OR (95% CI)	P-value*
Clinical Trial	Yes vs No	0.710 (0.466, 1.082)	0.1269
Co-Author Count	0-10 vs 21+	1.027 (0.638, 1.654)	0.9943
	11-20 vs 21+	1.019 (0.651, 1.595)	
	0-10 vs 11-20	1.008 (0.682, 1.491)	
Collaborating Author Count	0-100 vs 101+	1.075 (0.688, 1.681)	0.7743
Degree	MD-only vs Neither	0.411 (0.167, 1.009)	<.0001
	Both vs PhD-only	0.237 (0.126, 0.447)	
	Neither vs PhD-only	0.572 (0.234, 1.398)	
	MD-only vs PhD-only	0.235 (0.138, 0.400)	
	Both vs Neither	0.415 (0.158, 1.086)	
	Both vs MD-only	1.009 (0.580, 1.754)	
Grant Funding	Yes vs No	0.937 (0.636, 1.382)	0.7522
Specialty	Infectious Diseases vs Neoplasms	1.338 (0.517, 3.459)	0.0194
	CVD vs All other	0.850 (0.448, 1.614)	
	CVD vs Infectious Diseases	0.282 (0.114, 0.700)	
	CVD vs Neoplasms	0.377 (0.166, 0.855)	
	Neoplasms vs All other	2.254 (1.144, 4.441)	
	Infectious Diseases vs All other	3.015 (1.342, 6.774)	
Title	L-only vs Neither	1.004 (0.418, 2.412)	0.2448
	Both vs Neither	0.591 (0.331, 1.054)	
	AR-only vs Neither	0.877 (0.520, 1.479)	
	AR-only vs L-only	0.873 (0.382, 1.998)	
	AR-only vs Both	1.485 (0.879, 2.508)	
	Both vs L-only	0.588 (0.263, 1.313)	
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada vs Non-US	1.178 (0.778, 1.784)	0.4574

Variable	Level	OR (95% CI)	P-value*
Institution Region (at time of Publication)	US vs Non-US	1.467 (0.903, 2.383)	0.1255
Journal	JAMA vs LANCET	0.921 (0.586, 1.448)	0.1328
	LANCET vs NEJM	1.813 (1.016, 3.234)	
	JAMA vs NEJM	1.670 (0.944, 2.955)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	Unit=1	0.835 (0.703, 0.993)	0.0468

*: P-values were based on type 3 tests in multivariable GEE model with first authors as clustering effect.

Distribution of missing gender data

The numbers of unique 1st/2nd/last/significant authors, as well as those with unknown gender, could be found in the 4th table (i.e., author-level tables) in the descriptive tables in file “TBJ-Preliminary result summary-01142021.docx”. Specifically, there were 46 (1.6% out of 2839, the 4th table in Table 2.4.1/2.4.2) unique significant authors that had missing gender; 10 out of 962 (4th table in Table 2.1.1/2.1.2) unique first authors, 20 out of 1011 (4th table in Table 2.2.1/2.2.2) unique second authors, 16 out of 994 (4th table in Table 2.3.1/2.3.2) unique last authors with missing gender. Note that the total number of unique significant authors 2839 could not be separated into 3 parts as 1st, 2nd, last authors since one author could be having different author roles in different publications.

Since it would be hard to classify one author to be in one specific journal or year (an author may have multiple publications), the table below showed the frequency table of author-publication combinations with unknown/missing gender.

Table 1.1: Frequency table of missing/unknown gender for any significant author position by journal and year

Journal	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	Total
JAMA	0/58	0/60	0/56	0/58	3/57	0/57	0/60	0/59	0/59	0/58	0/60	1/56	0/57	1/59	0/60	0/60	6/59	2/60	13/1053
LANCET	1/60	2/59	1/59	1/58	1/60	1/58	10/59	8/59	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/59	1/60	0/59	1/59	0/60	27/1069
NEJM	2/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	1/60	1/59	1/60	0/60	1/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	0/60	6/1079
Total	3/178	2/179	1/175	1/176	5/177	2/174	11/179	8/178	1/179	0/178	0/180	1/176	0/177	1/178	1/180	0/179	7/178	2/180	46/3201

Based on univariate GEE models with publications as clustering effect, missing gender was significantly associated with journal ($p=0.0025$), but not year ($p=0.2635$) or author position ($p=0.1109$).

Association of study directionality and author gender

Table 2.1-2.3 showed the descriptive tables for 2 directionality classifications by the gender of 1st, last, any significant authors.

Table 2.1: Descriptive table for directionality by gender of first author

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1080)	Unknown (N=10)	Male (N=783)	Female (N=287)	P-value*
Directionality 1	Positive	12	542 (50.75%)	3 (30.00%)	407 (52.52%)	132 (46.64%)	0.1347
	All other		526 (49.25%)	7 (70.00%)	368 (47.48%)	151 (53.36%)	
Directionality 2	Negative	12	153 (14.33%)	3 (30.00%)	99 (12.77%)	51 (18.02%)	0.0630
	All other		915 (85.67%)	7 (70.00%)	676 (87.23%)	232 (81.98%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. P-values were based on GEE models with authors as clustering effect.

Table 2.2: Descriptive table for directionality by gender of last author

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1075)	Unknown (N=16)	Male (N=862)	Female (N=197)	P-value*
Directionality 1	Positive	12	541 (50.89%)	5 (31.25%)	439 (51.47%)	97 (50.00%)	0.6580
	All other		522 (49.11%)	11 (68.75%)	414 (48.53%)	97 (50.00%)	
Directionality 2	Negative	12	152 (14.30%)	2 (12.50%)	118 (13.83%)	32 (16.49%)	0.3229
	All other		911 (85.70%)	14 (87.50%)	735 (86.17%)	162 (83.51%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. P-values were based on GEE models with authors as clustering effect.

Table 2.3: Descriptive table for directionality by gender of any significant author

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=3201)	Unknown (N=46)	Male (N=2313)	Female (N=842)	P-value*
Directionality 1	Positive	35	1615 (51.01%)	13 (28.26%)	1205 (52.67%)	397 (47.72%)	0.0237
	All other		1551 (48.99%)	33 (71.74%)	1083 (47.33%)	435 (52.28%)	
Directionality 2	Negative	35	454 (14.34%)	7 (15.22%)	306 (13.37%)	141 (16.95%)	0.0280
	All other		2712 (85.66%)	39 (84.78%)	1982 (86.63%)	691 (83.05%)	

*: P-values were only among data excluding unknown gender. P-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect.

Which journal(s) are driving gender disparity across journals

Table 2.0: Gender disparity across journals

Author position	Journal	Total	Unknown	Male	Female	P-value* (F vs. M)	P-value* (F vs. M across journals)
1st author	All	1080	10 (0.93%)	783 (73.18%)	287 (26.82%)	<.0001	< 0.0001
	JAMA	360	4 (1.11%)	230 (64.61%)	126 (35.39%)	<.0001	
	LANCET	360	6 (1.67%)	250 (70.62%)	104 (29.38%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	360	0 (0.00%)	303 (84.17%)	57 (15.83%)	<.0001	
2nd author	All	1046	20 (1.91%)	668 (65.11%)	358 (34.89%)	<.0001	< 0.0001
	JAMA	337	6 (1.78%)	186 (56.19%)	145 (43.81%)	0.0030	
	LANCET	350	10 (2.86%)	224 (65.88%)	116 (34.12%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	359	4 (1.11%)	258 (72.68%)	97 (27.32%)	<.0001	
Last author	All	1075	16 (1.49%)	862 (81.40%)	197 (18.60%)	<.0001	0.1378
	JAMA	356	3 (0.84%)	279 (79.04%)	74 (20.96%)	<.0001	
	LANCET	359	11 (3.06%)	279 (80.17%)	69 (19.83%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	360	2 (0.56%)	304 (84.92%)	54 (15.08%)	<.0001	
Significant author	All	3201	46 (1.44%)	2313 (73.31%)	842 (26.69%)	<.0001	< 0.0001
	JAMA	1053	13 (1.23%)	695 (66.83%)	345 (33.17%)	<.0001	
	LANCET	1069	27 (2.53%)	753 (72.26%)	289 (27.74%)	<.0001	
	NEJM	1079	6 (0.56%)	865 (80.62%)	208 (19.38%)	<.0001	

*: For 1st, 2nd, last author, p-values were based on GEE models with authors as clustering effect; for significant author, p-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect.

For 1st author publications, the % female author was significant lower in NEJM compared to JAMA (p<.0001) or LANCET (p=0.0003), while the proportions in JAMA and LANCET were not significantly different at the significance level of 0.05 (p=0.0919). So we could say NEJM is driving the difference.

For 2nd author publications, the % female author in JAMA was significant higher compared to LANCET (p=0.0122) or NEJM (p<.0001), while the proportions in LANCET and NEJM were not significantly different (p=0.1040). So JAMA is driving the difference here.

For any significant author role publications, the % female author in JAMA was significant higher compared to LANCET ($p=0.0121$) or NEJM ($p<.0001$), and the proportions in LANCET was significantly higher than in NEJM ($p<.0001$).

Monthly/quarterly evaluation of the number/% of women in any significant author roles for Lancet since December 2017

Table 5.1: Trend for % female significant authors by month for LANCET since Dec 2, 2017

Month	Known	Male	Female
2017DEC	6	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)
2018FEB	13	7 (53.85%)	6 (46.15%)
2018MAR	6	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)
2018APR	3	3 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)
2018MAY	6	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)
2018JUN	6	5 (83.33%)	1 (16.67%)
2018JUL	3	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)
2018SEP	12	8 (66.67%)	4 (33.33%)
2018NOV	6	6 (100.00%)	0 (0.00%)
2018DEC	3	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)
2019JAN	3	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)
2019FEB	9	5 (55.56%)	4 (44.44%)
2019MAR	9	6 (66.67%)	3 (33.33%)
2019MAY	6	3 (50.00%)	3 (50.00%)
2019JUN	9	5 (55.56%)	4 (44.44%)
2019JUL	3	1 (33.33%)	2 (66.67%)
2019AUG	9	5 (55.56%)	4 (44.44%)
2019SEP	9	8 (88.89%)	1 (11.11%)
2019NOV	3	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)
OR (95% CI)			1.0074 (0.9311, 1.0898)
P-value*			0.8550

*: P-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect.

Table 5.2: Trend for % female significant authors by quarter for LANCET since Dec 2, 2017

Quarter	Known	Male	Female
2017Q4	6	4 (66.67%)	2 (33.33%)
2018Q1	19	11 (57.89%)	8 (42.11%)
2018Q2	15	12 (80.00%)	3 (20.00%)
2018Q3	15	10 (66.67%)	5 (33.33%)
2018Q4	9	8 (88.89%)	1 (11.11%)
2019Q1	21	13 (61.90%)	8 (38.10%)
2019Q2	15	8 (53.33%)	7 (46.67%)
2019Q3	21	14 (66.67%)	7 (33.33%)
2019Q4	3	2 (66.67%)	1 (33.33%)
OR (95% CI)			1.0264 (0.8514, 1.2373)
P-value*			0.7850

*: P-values were based on GEE models with publications as clustering effect.

First/senior author gender concordance

For same-gender mentorship, analysis was only for those 962 unique 1st authors, and their future publications were counted only since their first publications as 1st authors. Note that there were 30 authors that having same-gender mentorship missing in their initial 1st author publications and thus excluded.

	MP	SP	Total	P-value*
Supported	107 (17.29%)	512 (82.71%)	619	0.0006
Unsupported	28 (8.95%)	285 (91.05%)	313	
Total	135	797	932	

*: P-value was based on Chi-square test.

It suggested that 1st authors who were supported with same-gender mentorship were more likely to have future publications compared to those unsupported (17.29% vs 8.95%, p=0.0006).

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	Combination of First/Senior Author Relationships	First	Last	First Author's Senior/Mentor Author's Gender – Concordance Level
1	F-M	Female	Male	Unsupported
2	F-F	Female	Female	Supported
3	M-F	Male	Female	Unsupported
4	M-M	Male	Male	Supported

Note that only 1050 publications having both 1st and last authors with known gender were included in this part of analysis.

Descriptive table of publication characteristics by first author gender-based team dynamics

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=1050)	Supported (N=709)	Unsupported (N=341)	P-value*
Time Period	2002-2008	0	406 (38.67%)	274 (38.65%)	132 (38.71%)	0.8858
	2009-2014		351 (33.43%)	240 (33.85%)	111 (32.55%)	
	2015-2019		293 (27.90%)	195 (27.50%)	98 (28.74%)	
Co-Author Count	0-10	0	464 (44.19%)	299 (42.17%)	165 (48.39%)	0.1034
	11-20		389 (37.05%)	267 (37.66%)	122 (35.78%)	
	21+		197 (18.76%)	143 (20.17%)	54 (15.84%)	
Clinical Trial	No	0	486 (46.29%)	302 (42.60%)	184 (53.96%)	0.0005
	Yes		564 (53.71%)	407 (57.40%)	157 (46.04%)	
Grant Funding	No	0	641 (61.05%)	454 (64.03%)	187 (54.84%)	0.0042
	Yes		409 (38.95%)	255 (35.97%)	154 (45.16%)	
Standardized WOS Citation Count	-	1	0.88±1.23	0.97±1.33	0.70±0.96	0.0002
US-Based Patient Recruitment	US/Canada	53	404 (40.52%)	257 (38.47%)	147 (44.68%)	0.0605
	Non-US		593 (59.48%)	411 (61.53%)	182 (55.32%)	
Continent of Patient Recruitment	North America	53	403 (40.42%)	257 (38.47%)	146 (44.38%)	0.0806
	Europe		210 (21.06%)	145 (21.71%)	65 (19.76%)	
	Asia		62 (6.22%)	45 (6.74%)	17 (5.17%)	
	Australia/NZ		23 (2.31%)	16 (2.40%)	7 (2.13%)	
	Central/South America		7 (0.70%)	6 (0.90%)	1 (0.30%)	
	Africa		38 (3.81%)	19 (2.84%)	19 (5.78%)	
	Other/Unknown		254 (25.48%)	180 (26.95%)	74 (22.49%)	
Directionality	Negative	12	147 (14.16%)	95 (13.53%)	52 (15.48%)	0.5305
	Neutral		204 (19.65%)	146 (20.80%)	58 (17.26%)	
	Positive		533 (51.35%)	359 (51.14%)	174 (51.79%)	
	Other		154 (14.84%)	102 (14.53%)	52 (15.48%)	

Variable	Level	Nmissing	Total (N=698)	Supported (N=473)	Unsupported (N=225)	P-value*
Collaborating Author Count	0-100	0	575 (82.38%)	384 (81.18%)	191 (84.89%)	0.2299
	101+		123 (17.62%)	89 (18.82%)	34 (15.11%)	

Note: For continuous variable, mean and std were shown.

*: For continuous variable, p-value was based on t test assuming unequal variance; for categorical variables, p-values were based on Chi-square tests (with exact p-values from Monte-Carlo simulation if small cell count existed).

Table: Comparison of female 1st/2nd/last/significant author rates by year with AAMC rates

Year	AAMC % Female	1st author		2nd author		Last author		Significant author	
		% Female	P-value* in comparison with AAMC	% Female	P-value* in comparison with AAMC	% Female	P-value* in comparison with AAMC	% Female	P-value* in comparison with AAMC
2002	30.86%	38.33%	0.2101	37.50%	0.2819	25.42%	0.3664	33.71%	0.4135
2003	31.61%	25.00%	0.2712	36.84%	0.3952	6.67%	<.0001	22.60%	0.0100
2004	32.31%	31.67%	0.9157	30.36%	0.7552	18.97%	0.0298	27.01%	0.1356
2005	32.86%	28.33%	0.4556	24.56%	0.1824	17.24%	0.0113	23.43%	0.0079
2006	33.73%	22.41%	0.0684	36.36%	0.6794	16.95%	0.0064	25.00%	0.0155
2007	34.54%	30.00%	0.4597	34.62%	0.9908	20.00%	0.0179	27.91%	0.0675
2008	35.18%	21.05%	0.0255	32.73%	0.7033	14.29%	0.0011	22.62%	0.0007
2009	35.64%	16.95%	0.0027	32.73%	0.6523	19.64%	0.0125	22.94%	0.0006
2010	36.23%	25.00%	0.0705	44.07%	0.2102	20.34%	0.0111	29.78%	0.0735
2011	36.82%	18.33%	0.0030	25.86%	0.0837	23.33%	0.0304	22.47%	<.0001
2012	37.44%	28.33%	0.1451	48.33%	0.0813	20.00%	0.0053	32.22%	0.1484
2013	38.20%	30.51%	0.2238	29.31%	0.1634	18.97%	0.0026	26.29%	0.0012
2014	38.94%	23.33%	0.0132	35.09%	0.5504	23.33%	0.0132	27.12%	0.0013
2015	39.64%	26.67%	0.0400	31.58%	0.2135	13.33%	<.0001	23.73%	<.0001
2016	40.34%	28.81%	0.0713	31.67%	0.1711	13.33%	<.0001	24.58%	<.0001
2017	41.15%	23.33%	0.0051	40.68%	0.9415	18.33%	0.0003	27.37%	0.0002
2018	42.03%	29.31%	0.0497	36.36%	0.3943	17.24%	0.0001	27.49%	0.0001
2019	42.72%	35.00%	0.2269	38.33%	0.4924	27.59%	0.0198	33.71%	0.0151
Total	37.23%	26.82%	<.0001	34.89%	0.1210	18.60%	<.0001	26.69%	<.0001

*: P-values were based on Chi-square tests.